

Report 7.1: A social psychological perspective on trends of radicalisation

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About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and broader social contexts driving radicalisation, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualises this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) to move towards measurable evaluations of de-radicalisation programmes. We intend to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, including a sense of being victimised, being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures and coming under the influence of “us vs them” identity formulations.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts, including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nationalisms. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad labs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion and de-radicalisation.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of seventeen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation-states adapt to new security challenges. Mapping these varieties and their link to national contexts is crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that radicalisation processes often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national justice frameworks. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analysing and devising solutions to online radicalisation is central to the project’s aims.

Executive Summary

The report synthesises the findings of a survey and 15 country reports (Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Kosovo, Poland, Serbia, Slovenia, Turkey, and the United Kingdom). This report argues that research on radicalisation must consider group membership and intergroup context and argues for a processual and relational understanding of radicalisation. Specifically, our findings highlight the importance of felt strong online group identity on radicalisation or support for extremist attitudes. We also find that holding strong beliefs about group hierarchies as an inherent fact of life (social dominance orientation) is an important contributor to endorsing more extremist attitudes. We further find that relational intergroup factors such as the importance of group relative deprivation - to what extent individuals perceive groups they identify with as deprived - can help explain pathways to radicalisation. Other relational intergroup factors, such as beliefs that one's ingroup is superior to other social groups (i.e., collective narcissism) and perceptions that migrants threaten a country's resources, welfare, and majority population's power, all play an important role in predicting endorsement of extremist attitudes. Finally, we also explore an individual's relational vulnerability to find that for our whole sample, experiencing social alienation, which encompasses felt meaninglessness and isolation, was linked with more significant support for extremist attitudes. Given the largely collaborative nature of D.Rad, the current survey study, combined with the partners' unique position to understand the current social and cultural contexts of their countries better than any single partner alone could, offers unique insight into the social psychology of radicalisation by situating findings within their sociopolitical and sociocultural contexts, as well as investigating universal experiences of pathways to endorsing extremist ideologies. Importantly, we highlight that the path to radicalisation is not linear but involves the interplay of many relational factors that can buffer or catalyse progression. Studying the journey in progress allows us to understand radicalisation as a social process and situate individuals within meaningful social groups and social experiences.

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1. Introduction

The goal of this report is synthesising the findings of a survey delivered in 15 countries and prepared within Work Package 7 of the *De-Radicalisation in Europe and Beyond: Detect, Resolve, Reintegrate* (D.Rad) project in the UK, France, Germany, Italy, Austria, Finland, Poland, Hungary, Slovenia, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Georgia, Turkey, and Israel. Work Package 7 aims to develop a processual and relational understanding of radicalisation across the I-GAP (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) spectrum of the (de-)radicalisation process.

The following analysis relies on the D.Rad definition of *radicalisation* as a process involving the increasing rejection of established law, order, and politics and the active pursuit of alternatives in the form of politically driven violence or justification of violence [1]. *De-radicalisation* denotes the processes countering such rejection at the individual (micro), organisational (meso), or societal (macro) levels, resulting in a shift from violent to nonviolent strategies and tactics; de-radicalisation might or might not be an outcome of de-radicalisation programmes.

This report argues that research on radicalisation must move beyond the psychopathological perspectives that have been used to make sense of radicalisation in Europe and elsewhere and that approached radicalisation as an outcome of individual pathologies amplified within specific communities and organisations. Even where research has abandoned psychopathological assumptions, it often still operates with assumptions of individual psychological vulnerability that radicalising communities and organisations take advantage of. This is problematic because it understates the appeal and reach of radicalisation.

Instead, our report argues for a more processual and relational understanding of radicalisation and of the pathways leading to it. This relational perspective challenges the assumptions behind the prevailing approaches to monitor and counter political violence based on the homogenising ways law enforcement agencies use concepts such as radicalisation, extremism, and terrorism. For instance, “terrorism,” according to Europol, “can be considered to be a set of violent tactics employed mainly by extremists” (Europol, 2021, p. 11), while “the underlying causes that lead people to radicalisation and terrorism must be sought in the surroundings (structural factors) and personal interpretations (psychological factors) of the individual” (Europol, 2021, p. 108). In other words, radicalisation is about proceeding down a path to and from radical politics primarily via individual conversion to and from extremist ideologies. In contrast, the relational perspective outlined above warns against treating such conversion as a largely sufficient factor in bringing about radicalisation. Applied to the research carried out in WP7, it calls for researching less about the level of individual indoctrination and more about the relationships and the perceptions that individuals have vis-a-vis groups they identify with.

In particular, rather than insist on the psychological characteristics of individuals, our report shows the importance of felt strong online group identity, collective narcissism towards one’s

ingroup, and preference for group hierarchies within societies on radicalisation or support for extremist attitudes. At the same time, it highlights the importance of group relative deprivation - to what extent individuals perceive groups they identify with as deprived - as an intermediating factor explaining radicalisation. Our report also uses the expertise of D.Rad country teams to make sense of and contextualise our path model's results (introduced below). Given the largely collaborative nature of D.Rad, the current survey study, combined with the partners' unique position to understand the current social and cultural contexts of their countries better than any single partner alone could, has the potential to provide unique insight into the social psychology of radicalisation.

1.2. From psychopathology to a relational approach to radicalisation

Amidst a plethora of research showing that terrorism and radicalisation are not necessarily a result of psychopathology (e.g., Ruby, 2002; Silke, 1998), several authors have provided their contributions towards a more dynamic, comprehensive account of the social and psychological processes leading to radicalisation and terrorism. Moghaddam (2005) compares the radicalisation process towards violent extremism to a narrowing staircase with a ground floor and five higher floors, where individuals can either remain on a particular floor or climb further up, depending not only on the actual shape of the building but on their individual *perception* of it. The ground floor consists of perceptions of fairness and relative deprivation, where individuals seek to improve their situation and achieve greater justice. If they feel they cannot influence injustices, anger and frustration increase, leaving them vulnerable to leaders that gradually engage them in physical violence and an "us-vs-them" mentality.

Borum (2014) explores the propensities and vulnerabilities that may lead people towards extremism. This includes a person's worldview (i.e., the assumptions and presuppositions about how the world works that guide our social interactions, such as beliefs that group hierarchies and the stratification of societies are an inherent fact of life, as reflected in social dominance orientation); the need for personal meaning, identity and belonging; perceived injustice/humiliation; and motivational, attributional, volitional, and attitudinal propensities. Doosje et al. (2016) identify common elements shared across different types of radical groups. These include perceptions of grievance in society; dissatisfaction with how institutions (mainly police and politicians) deal with these problems; consequent low institutional trust and perceptions that authorities are not legitimate; beliefs that their ingroup's norms and values are superior to those of other groups, resulting in an "us-vs-them" distinction; and an embrace of violence-legitimising ideology.

While these contributions steer away from the erroneous view that individuals who have become radicalised have some form of psychopathology, as Schmid (2013) points out, they still largely focus on a person-centred (i.e., a micro-level) approach, mainly exploring how psychologically vulnerable individuals are socialised ideologically by radical groups. Two further levels need further consideration: the meso-level and the macro-level.

Here, we draw on contemporary sociological research that has extensively explored the macro and meso levels and, in particular, on the relational analysis in the study of contentious politics and radicalisation on which Work Package 3 of the D.Rad project was based (Ishchenko and Varga, 2022). The relational approach analyses violence as one of many strategies that individuals develop as part of groups and organisations with historically specific repertoires of violent and non-violent actions (McAdam, Tarrow and Tilly, 2001; Alimi, Bosi and Demetriou, 2015; Bosi, Demetriou and Malthaner, 2016; Della Porta, 2018). Radicalisation is therefore seen not as the result of individual proclivities of actors but of interactions between informal groups and formal organisations, including extreme and centrist political movements/parties, civil society segments, state institutions and elite groups. Radicalisation should, therefore, be approached in the 'ecosystems' of radicalising individuals' various relationships (e.g. cooperation, competition, confrontation) with their front groups, media, social networks of mobilisation, recruitment and sponsorship, 'mainstream' political forces and state institutions.

The macro level brings to the forefront how changes in the political, economic and social structure, both nationally and internationally, contribute to radicalisation. For example, how the transformation of relations between majority and minority groups, particularly diaspora migrants caught between cultures, can complicate the self-identities of majority and minority groups and their relations with their host and indigenous groups. The meso level refers to the study of the dynamic relationships between different - formal and informal - collective actors in national and international politics and how these relationships increase the propensity of individuals to radicalise. At this level, one can study how shifting alliances between political representatives of social groups, or the repression of some or the acquisition of influential allies by others, can contribute to (de)radicalisation.

Returning to social psychology, Schmid (2013) originally stated there is some uncertainty as to what should belong to the meso- and what to the macro-levels- Doosje et al. (2016) provide examples of all levels and simultaneously distinguish 3 phases to radicalisation, explaining how factors at all three levels can play a role at all phases. During phase 1, the sensitivity phase, micro-level factors include the quest for significance and personal uncertainty. Loss of status, poor career prospects, or a strong sense of humiliation can all increase feelings of insignificance that radical groups offer to foster or restore. Meanwhile, because humans are motivated to reduce uncertainty, identifying with a group that provides clear norms and values can become a tempting solution (Hogg et al., 2013). Group-relative deprivation – perceptions that the ingroup one closely identifies with has been treated unjustly or worse than another group – is a meso-level factor. More prominent societal factors, such as accelerating globalisation and worldwide threats – especially those perceived as hurting the ingroup – constitute macro-level factors. During this first phase, individuals with particular propensities and vulnerabilities (such as those explained by Borum, 2014) are easy prey for being drafted into radical groups and climbing further up the staircase towards extremism and terrorism.

The second phase, the group membership phase, begins after the individual has joined a radical group and becomes fused to it and vice versa. At the micro-level, the individual starts as a lower-status member motivated to show loyalty by adhering to the group's norms and

values. This can be done through actions such as downgrading an outgroup in public contexts (Noel, et al., 1995). At the meso-level, ties between the individual and the group are strengthened. This can be done through initiation rituals, training, and coaching or by changing the individual's social environment via physical and psychological isolation, making the ingroup more cohesive (Swann et al., 2012). At the macro-level, global events seen as victories for the ingroup (e.g., the Russia-Ukraine war, far-right political victories) may increase perceived group efficacy or further strengthen an individual's self-identification to the group.

Finally, the third phase proposed by Doosje et al. (2016), the action phase, occurs when the individual is ready to commit violent actions in the name of the ingroup. At the micro-level, individual worldviews such as social dominance orientation may lead someone to choose and justify violent attacks over peaceful protests (Lemieux & Asal, 2010). At the meso level, presenting the outgroup as a threat to the ingroup, such as limiting access to healthcare resources, can be a simple yet effective way to make members justify their violence towards the outgroup and has been mobilised. Finally, at the macro-level, as with the group membership phase, previous successful attacks might motivate the individual to engage in violent acts themselves or, oppositely, defeat of the ingroup may lead the individual to seek revenge on the outgroup.

Given these examples, it should be clearer why research on radicalisation must consider group membership and intergroup context. Given the largely collaborative nature of D.Rad, the current survey study, combined with the partners' unique position to understand the current social and cultural contexts of their countries better than any single partner alone could, has the potential to provide unique insight into the social psychology of radicalisation.

1.3. Proposed Model

We propose the following model to explore individual differences in relational factors, vulnerability (operationalised as perceptions of social cohesion and alienation), political ideologies (operationalised as populism and political attitudes), and intergroup perceptions and attitudes (operationalised as perceptions of anomie, collective narcissism, and perceived relative deprivation) as predictors of endorsing extremism. We also included perceived threat to one's national culture regarding resources, and access to welfare and power (realistic threat) from migrants. Our proposed model is illustrated in Figure 1. To ensure that we captured people's experiences of extremism across the spectrum, extremism was operationalised as idealistic endorsement (and/or pursuit) of comprehensive changes in the status quo (socially, culturally, and societally).

Figure 1. Proposed model of relational factors predicting facets of extremism.

Importantly, this model is founded on the I-GAP spectrum (illustrated in Figure 2) to elucidate people’s experiences across the extremism pathway and explore cross-national similarities and differences. In this way, we probe deeper into the social psychological processes that buffer or catalyse an individual’s journey towards endorsing increasingly extremist attitudes. We use a social lens to highlight the role of one’s social groups and attachments, which are integrated into one’s social identity and sense of self (Haslam, Jetten, Postmes, & Haslam, 2009; Smith & Henry, 1995). Indeed, the need to belong is a fundamental human motivation; failure to build lasting social attachments is associated with several poor psychological outcomes (Baumeister & Leary, 1995).

Additionally, in light of the ensuing war in Ukraine, and to capture potential emerging polarisation, we measured attitudes towards Ukrainian and Russian migrants and attitudes towards Russia (within cultural, social, political, and economic domains) and included our exploratory findings.

Figure 2. Situating our variables within the I-GAP model.

2. Method

2.1. Participants and Procedure

Ethics approval was given by the Ethics Committee of the College of Health, Medicine, and Life Sciences at Brunel University London, by the recommendations of the British Psychological Society. Participants were recruited across 16 national contexts using Qualtrics research panels. Qualtrics recruits representative samples using grassroots organisations within each national context, often drawing on pre-existing participant pools. We requested Qualtrics to provide a representative (approximately 50% split) sample of sex and a range of 18-30 years to focus on young adults. Qualtrics reimburses participants for their participation, and pre-screens participants to increase the likelihood of complete and accurate responses. Qualtrics also pre-screens responses to remove participants who do not complete the survey, go through too quickly (anyone who takes less than half the median completion time, which was 20 minutes), or have identical responses across scales (e.g., selecting “1” for all items). A total of 4,599 ($M_{age} = 24.81$, $SD = 5.28$, Females = 2392, Males = 2200, Non-binary = 7) participants took part.

Participants completed the survey online using the Qualtrics platform. Participants were first provided with a participant information sheet detailing the project and what they would be doing if they agreed to participate; after giving consent, participants completed demographic questions and the measures outlined below. After completion, participants were debriefed and provided with country-specific resources if they required them. Participants completed the measures in the national language of the country they were residing in. Translations were

completed by research partners within each country and compared with their English counterparts.

2.2. Materials

2.2.1. Demographics

We used sex, age (with recruitment selecting participants between 18 and 30 years of age only), residing country, religious affiliation, and belongingness to discriminated groups. For the latter, participants were first asked if they would describe themselves as being members of a group that is discriminated against in the country where they live (“Yes,” “No,” “Don’t know”). If participants selected “Yes”, they were asked to select all the grounds their group was discriminated against (e.g., religion, sexuality, ethnicity).

2.2.2. Social Dominance Orientation (Ho et al., 2015)

Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) is the degree to which an individual approves group-based hierarchies and inequalities. SDO was measured on a 7-point scale with 8 items (e.g., “An ideal society requires some groups to be on top and others to be on the bottom.”), where 1 = strongly opposed, and 7 = strongly favour. Scores across all items were summed such that the possible score range went from 8 to 56. Higher scores correspond to greater SDO.

2.2.3. Collective Narcissism (de Zavala et al., 2009)

Collective narcissism is an exaggerated belief that a main group an individual identifies with or belongs to (i.e., the ingroup) is better than other groups the individual is not part of (i.e., the outgroup). Participants were asked to write down their most important social group and then, with it in mind, complete a 5-point scale with 5 items (e.g., “My group deserves special treatment.”), where 1 = totally disagree, and 5 = totally agree. Scores across all items were summed such that the possible score range went from 5 to 25. Higher scores correspond to greater collective narcissism.

2.2.4. Realistic Threat (Stephan et al., 1998)

Realistic threat is the concern that an outgroup threatens the welfare and resources, the political and economic power, and the physical and material well-being of the ingroup. Realistic threat was measured with a 7-point, 7-item scale (e.g., “[Outgroup members] get more from [ingroup] than they contribute.”), with migrants as the outgroup and the country of residency stated by participants in the demographics questions as the ingroup. The scale was anchored at 1 = totally disagree and 7 = totally agree. Scores across all items were summed such that the possible score range went from 7 to 49. Higher scores correspond to greater perceptions that migrants are a realistic threat.

2.2.5. Extremism (Ozer & Bertelsen, 2018)

Extremism refers to the idealistic endorsement (and/or pursuit) of comprehensive changes in the status quo (socially, culturally, and societally), even at the expense of human coexistence. Support for extremist attitudes was measured on a 7-point, 14-item scale (e.g., “Most people

in this country have a lifestyle and culture that is necessary to change totally.”), where 1 = strongly disagree and 7 = strongly agree. Scores across all items were summed such that the possible score range went from 14 to 98. Higher scores correspond to greater support for extremist attitudes.

2.2.6. Perceived Anomie (Teymoori et al., 2016)

Perceived anomie refers to the perceived breakdown in social fabric (i.e., of moral standards) and in the legitimacy and efficiency of leadership. Perceived anomie was measured on a 7-point, 12-item scale (e.g., “People think that there are no clear moral standards to follow.”), where 1 = strongly disagree and 7 = strongly agree. Scores across all items were summed such that the possible score range went from 12 to 84. Higher scores correspond to greater perceived anomie.

2.2.7. Online Group Identity (Howard & Mage, 2013)

Online group identity is the perceived belongingness and psychological attachment to an online group (i.e., a group of people with a perceived common identity whose main communication is online). Participants were asked to write down which specific online group they most felt they were a part of. They then completed a 7-point, 5-item scale (e.g., “I feel a bond with this online group.”) where 1 = strongly disagree and 7 = strongly agree. Scores across all items were summed such that the possible score range went from 5 to 35. Higher scores correspond to a stronger online group identity.

2.2.8. Populism (Akerman et al., 2014)

Populism is an ideology that considers society to be ultimately separated into two homogenous and antagonistic groups: the people (who are pure and good) and the elite (who are corrupt and evil) and argues that politics should be an expression of the general will of the people. Populism was measured with a 7-point, 6-item scale (e.g., “The politicians in [seat of power of the participant’s country of residence] need to follow the will of the people.”) where 1 = strongly disagree and 7 = strongly agree. Scores across all items were summed such that the possible score range went from 6 to 42. Higher scores correspond to greater populist attitudes.

2.2.9. Perceived Relative Deprivation (Urbanska & Diamong, 2018)

Individual relative deprivation (individual relative deprivation) is when the self is perceived to be worse off in relation to others, while group relative deprivation (group relative deprivation) is when one’s ingroup is perceived to be less fortunate than the outgroup.

Individual relative deprivation was measured with a single item that asked, “If you were to compare your economic situation in comparison to other nationals of the country you live in, would you say your economic situation is...” and was set on a 5-point anchor, where 1 = much better and 5 = much worse. Higher scores correspond to greater individual relative deprivation and can be interpreted as the participant perceiving other nationals as economically better off than them. Group relative deprivation was similarly measured with a single item that asked, “If

you were to compare the economic situation of nationals compared to that of immigrants in the country you live in, where would you place the economic situation of nationals on this scale?” and was set on a 5-point anchor, where 1 = much better and 5 = much worse. Higher scores correspond to greater group relative deprivation and can be interpreted as the participant perceiving immigrants as better off economically than nationals.

2.2.10. Political Attitudes and Practice Measures (European Social Survey, 2018; Haerpfer et al., 2020 World Values Survey)

Political Attitudes

A single 7-point item (“Where would you place your political views on this scale?”), where 1 = Left and 7 = Right, measured participants’ political attitude. A “Don’t know” option was provided and later treated as NULL (or missing) values in statistical analyses, as we cannot know nor assume these participants’ attitudes (e.g., they could be moderates/centrists or entirely apolitical).

Note on the caveat around NULL values: For countries where too many participants (i.e., more than 5%) reported not knowing their political affiliation, it is impossible to include political attitudes in the path model. Firstly, according to proper statistical procedures, when the data are not missing at random, as in this case, and too many participants (i.e., more than 5%) have missing values, omitting these participants leads to biased estimates and incorrect study results. Secondly, even if we could remove these participants from analyses, doing so significantly reduces sample sizes, and complex path models require larger samples of, ideally, approximately 300 participants (200 on the minimum end). The best solution to avoid biased results and retain bigger samples is to remove political attitudes from the path model if the number of participants who reported not knowing their political affiliation exceeds 5%. As such, some partners had political attitudes in their path models, while others did not.

2.2.11. Membership to Organisation

Participants were asked if they were “Active,” “Inactive,” or “Not a member” of several organisations, from political and religious ones to artistic or humanitarian ones.

2.2.12. Political Actions

Participants answered whether they had taken any political actions (e.g., contacted a politician, government, or local government official) during the last 12 months. Options were “Yes,” “No,” and “Don’t know,” the latter of which were treated as NULL values.

2.2.13. Political Trust

Participants answered 10 items on how much they trusted their government and politicians (e.g., “Most politicians are honest and truthful.”), where 1 = strongly disagree and 7 = strongly agree. Scores across all items were summed such that the possible score range went from 10 to 70. Higher scores correspond to greater political trust.

2.2.14. Social Cohesion (Collins, Neal & Neal, 2017)

Social cohesion is the perception of mutual trust, shared values and solidarity among neighbours or community members. Social cohesion was measured with a 7-point, 5-item scale (e.g., “People in this neighbourhood can be trusted.”), where 1 = strongly disagree and 7 = strongly agree. Scores across all items were summed such that the possible score range went from 5 to 35. Higher scores correspond to greater perceptions of social cohesion.

2.2.15. Social Alienation (Middleton, 1963)

Social alienation is the degree to which an individual feels detached and is composed of feelings of powerlessness, meaninglessness, normlessness, isolation, and self-estrangement. Social alienation was measured with a 7-point, 6-item scale (e.g., “There is not much that I can do about most of the important problems that we face today.”), where 1 = strongly disagree and 7 = strongly agree. Scores across all items were summed such that the possible score range went from 6 to 42. Higher scores correspond to greater perceptions of social alienation.

2.2.16. Attitudes towards the Ukraine-Russia Conflict

Attitudes against Russia

Worsening attitudes towards Russia and Russian culture, generated by the research team, were measured on a 5-point, 5-item scale (e.g., “We should break all cooperation with Russian academics, artists, and athletes.”), where 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree. Scores across all items were summed such that the possible score range went from 5 to 25. Higher scores correspond to worsened attitudes towards Russia.

Attitudes towards Russian Migrants

A single 5-point item (“Did your opinion about Russian migrants in your country change this year?”) measured participants’ views on Russian migrants. The scale was anchored at 1 = I think much better about Russian migrants now, and 5 = I think much worse about Russian migrants now, with scores of 3 corresponding to attitudes not having changed. Higher scores correspond to worsened views towards Russian migrants.

Attitudes towards Ukrainian Migrants

A single 5-point item (“Did your opinion about Ukrainian migrants in your country change this year?”) measured participants’ views on Ukrainian migrants. The scale was anchored at 1 = I think much better about Ukrainian migrants now, and 5 = I think much worse about Ukrainian migrants now, with scores of 3 corresponding to attitudes not having changed. Higher scores correspond to worsened views towards Ukrainian migrants.

3. Results

This chapter details the findings of the survey from a universal approach. The model was also tested within each country for a country-specific approach. This allows us to explore which psychological processes and pathways are similar across countries for understanding the

endorsement of extremist attitudes and which are specific to each national context. We first discuss the findings of the hypothesised model for the entire dataset. In the Appendix, we report the findings and their interpretation within the respective national context for each country.

3.1. Hypothesised Model

The original model tested several regression paths using path analysis (see Figure 1). Firstly, we have the relationship between both social dominance orientation and online group identity, and seven mediators which are grouped into three domains: intergroup perceptions and processes (e.g., collective narcissism, perceived anomie, individual relative deprivation, group relative deprivation), vulnerability (feelings of social cohesion and social alienation) and political attitudes (populism). Second, is the relationship of collective narcissism, perceived anomie, individual relative deprivation, and group relative deprivation with perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat. Thirdly, the relationship between realistic threat and support for extremist attitudes. Finally, the relationship of social cohesion, social alienation, and populism with support for extremist attitudes. These 22 regression paths resulted in 14 indirect effects to be tested (e.g., social dominance orientation to collective narcissism to a realistic threat to extremism, social dominance orientation to social cohesion to extremism, etc.). For models that did include political attitudes as exogenous variables (i.e., Austria, Israel, Italy, Kosovo, and Turkey), the total number of regression paths and indirect effects tested was 29 and 21, respectively.

3.2. Model fit

Additionally, for every sample tested, there was a possibility that the hypothesised model would not have a good fit (i.e., the discrepancy between the observed data and the values expected under the hypothesised model would be too great). In such cases, new paths were added based on modification indices – paths that can be added to improve fit – and, more importantly, based on theoretical sense and scientific practices. For example, modification indices may show that adding a direct path from a predictor (e.g., social dominance orientation) to our outcome (i.e., extremism) provides a similar increase in fit as adding a path from one mediator to another (e.g., anomie predicting populism).

However, the parsimony principle states that the simplest one is preferable whenever we have different explanations of the observed data. Adding a direct path from social dominance orientation to extremism would suggest that social dominance orientation directly predicts support for extremist attitudes even beyond its indirect effect on extremism through its relationship with other variables in the model. Adding a path from anomie to populism would suggest that a person's perceived anomie predicts populist attitudes, which in turn predicts endorsement of extremist attitudes. This path addition would also add yet two more indirect effects that would need to be tested: the indirect effect of social dominance orientation on extremism via anomie and subsequently via populism (i.e., social dominance orientation to anomie to populism to extremism) and the indirect effect of online group identity on extremism

via anomie and subsequently via populism (i.e., online group identity to anomie to populism to extremism). Thus, a model with a direct path from social dominance orientation to extremism is more parsimonious than a model with a path from anomie to populism, and we would add the former path first before retesting our model fit. To test the model fit, we inspected several standard indices. The following sections summarise the respecified models for every country and the whole dataset.

Figure 1. Hypothesised model.

3.3. Pan-national dataset

Across the whole dataset ($N = 4,599$), 864 participants (18.79%) reported not knowing their political attitudes. As such, the path model tested on the full dataset did not include it as an exogenous variable.

3.3.1. Predictors of realistic threat

A stronger social dominance orientation was linked with increased perceptions that migrants threatened one's national ingroup regarding access to welfare, resources, and power. Perceiving that one's national ingroup was relatively more deprived compared to migrants was also linked with perceived migrants as a threat. Additionally, experiencing more anomie was also linked to perceiving migrants as a threat.

3.3.2. Direct predictors of extremism

Holding a stronger social dominance orientation attitude was linked with increased endorsement of extremist ideology. Higher collective narcissism was also associated with increased endorsement of extremist ideology. Additionally, perceptions that one's national

group was worse off economically (group relative deprivation) relative to migrants and perceiving that migrants posed a threat to the resources, welfare, and power of one's national group were both linked to increased endorsement of extremism. In terms of political ideologies, greater populism was associated with increased endorsement of extremism. Of the vulnerability variables, experiencing greater social alienation was linked with endorsement of extremism.

3.3.3. Indirect effects on extremism

Social dominance orientation had significant indirect effects on extremist attitudes through social alienation, populism, realistic threat, and group relative deprivation, although these went in different directions. Increased social dominance orientation predicted decreased social alienation and decreased populism, and these two, in turn, predicted decreased support for extremist attitudes (i.e., negative indirect effects). Increased social dominance orientation predicted increased realistic threat and increased group relative deprivation, and these two, in turn, predicted increased support for extremist attitudes (i.e., positive indirect effects). These opposite directionalities considered, the total indirect effect of one's social dominance orientation on extremist attitudes was significant in the negative direction (i.e., increased social dominance orientation, via its combined relationship through the other variables in the model, predicted *decreased* support for extremist attitudes). However, as previously mentioned, increased social dominance orientation was found to have a direct effect on increased support for extremist attitudes, and the total effect (i.e., the sum of the indirect and direct effects) was significantly positive. Importantly, these oppositional relationships provide insight into the protective factors against extremism (addressing social alienation and decreasing populism beliefs) and those factors which increase risk (perceiving migrants as a threat to one's national ingroup).

Online group identity had significant indirect effects on extremist attitudes through social alienation, populism, collective narcissism, and group relative deprivation. The former three were positive, such that a stronger online group identity predicted increased social alienation, increased populism, and increased collective narcissism, all of which, in turn, predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. However, the indirect effect through group relative deprivation was negative: a stronger online group identity predicted decreased group relative deprivation, and a reduced group relative deprivation predicted decreased support for extremist attitudes. Despite this negative indirect effect through group relative deprivation, the total indirect effect of online group identity on extremism was still significantly positive, with a stronger online group identity overall predicting increased support for extremist attitudes. This suggests that despite the protective aspect of a stronger online identity buffering individuals from perceiving less threat from migrants to their national ingroup and, in turn, endorsing extremist attitudes, its link with *greater* social alienation, populism, and collective narcissism is a risk factor for increased endorsement of extremism. These indirect relationships reveal the complex relationships between individual differences in group identities and expectations of group hierarchies and relational, political, and vulnerability variables that, in turn, increase endorsement

of

extremism.

Figure 2. Respecified model for the entire dataset.

3.3.4. Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

As these were exploratory analyses, we entered all of our central model variables as predictors towards attitudes towards vis-a-vis Russian culture and Russian and Ukrainian migrants. For our pan-cultural dataset, we found that stronger beliefs about group hierarchies were associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Additionally, a stronger online group identity was also associated with more negative attitudes towards Russian culture. Perceiving less threat from migrants to one's country was linked with more positive attitudes towards Russian culture. In terms of vulnerability, perceiving both more social alienation and also feeling more social cohesion within one's community were both linked with more negative attitudes towards Russian culture. Endorsing more extremist attitudes was linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Perceiving both more trust in one's respective system of governance and endorsing more populist attitudes were linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants was linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia.

In terms of attitudes towards Russian migrants, supporting more extremist attitudes was linked with improved, more positive attitudes in the past twelve months. More trust in one's system of governance was also linked with improved attitudes. Conversely, feeling both that one's economic situation and that of one's national ingroup were more deprived relative to migrants were both associated with a worsening of attitudes towards Russian migrants in the past twelve months.

Regarding attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants, feeling more embedded in one's community was linked to having improved attitudes in the past twelve months. Additionally, having higher political trust in one's system of governance was also associated with improved attitudes. Interestingly, supporting more extremist attitudes was also linked with improved attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants. Conversely, perceiving migrants to be a threat to one's national ingroup and perceiving that one's economic situation was more deprived relative to migrants were both linked to worsening attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants, specifically in the past twelve months. Finally, more populist attitudes were associated with worsening attitudes over time.

4. Discussion

Our findings indicate that endorsement of extremist attitudes can be understood from a relational perspective, which takes into account individual differences in group identities and how individuals construct their social realities in terms of group hierarchies, intergroup perceptions and processes such as where individuals perceive their social group to be relative to other social groups, social vulnerabilities such as cohesion and alienation, and political ideologies. Our findings also reveal the important role that perceptions of migrants as a threat to a country and its majority ingroup in terms of access to resources, welfare, and power on increased endorsement of extremism is particularly pertinent at a time when approximately over 280 million people - 3.5% of the world's population - are residing in a country outside of their nationality (UN Desa, 2020). We situate our findings within the I-GAP spectrum and discuss their implications for understanding the radicalisation process and extremist attitudes.

4.1. Injustice

Both indicators of injustice, perceived relative deprivation and realistic threat were associated with increased support for extremist attitudes. Indeed, perceptions that one's national group is worse off economically relative to migrants have been linked with increased support and intention to vote for an extreme right party (Urbanska & Guimond, 2018). Experiences of injustice are not based on absolute assessments of fairness but rather on one's experiences of treatment and mismatch with what they perceive they are entitled to, and in turn, comparison between the self and one's ingroup and others and outgroup members (Crosby, 1976). Our findings build on this by linking social dominance orientation first to both realistic threat and perceived relative deprivation and, in turn, to extremist attitudes, thereby highlighting the underlying mechanisms between worldviews and extremist attitudes through injustice.

4.2. Grievance

Individuals who were higher in social dominance orientation - who espoused stratified societies in terms of a preference for a natural hierarchy of groups - were more likely to perceive that they were experiencing injustices (e.g., perceiving migrants as a threat to their respective country and national ingroup in terms of accessing resources, welfare, and power) and in turn were more likely to endorse more extremist attitudes which include the need to dismantle the current status quo. Our findings parallel the link between social dominance

orientation and justification of and even engagement in violence and illegal actions (Lemieux & Asal, 2010). Indeed, a recent analysis of support for extremist far-right groups in the US has found that social dominance orientation accounts in part for the link between white racial identity and support for four far-right groups (Grindal & Haltinner, 2023), which supports our findings of the importance of how individuals conceptualise their social realities in understanding support for extremist ideologies. Although we did not measure support for specific extremist groups, many of the items of the extremism measure are drawn from the central tenets and objectives of extremist groups, such as dismantling existing ways of life. Our findings build on past research which has linked social dominance orientation to tendencies to vote for extreme right-wing political parties via attitudes towards migration and ethnic prejudice (Cornelis & Van Hiel, 2015) by incorporating judgements of the economic welfare of one's ingroup relative to migrant outgroups and perceptions that migrants threaten national resources as mediators, and importantly, through expanding to measure extremism attitudes across the spectrum which may include non-traditional extremist ideologies (e.g., Incels or extreme misogyny).

Relatedly, individuals who perceived their group as superior to other social groups (collective narcissism) were also more likely to endorse extremist attitudes. As individuals were allowed to self-ascribe their most important social group before completing the measures, our findings build on past research linking collective narcissism and increased outgroup prejudice and aggression (Golec de Zavala, Cichocka, Eidelson & Jayawickreme, 2009). Taken together, our findings suggest that the mismatch between grievances and injustices – such as the mismatch between preference for stratified societies, believing one's ingroup to be superior to others, and perceiving that one's national ingroup is economically worse off compared to migrants and that this outgroup poses a realistic threat to one's nation were linked with increased endorsement of extremist attitudes.

4.3. Alienation

In terms of vulnerability, experiencing social alienation, characterised by a lack of meaning, powerlessness, normlessness, and isolation, was associated with increased endorsement of extremism. We argue that social alienation can capture the frustration of the “human quest for personal significance”, one of the basic human needs (Kruglanski, Fernandez, Factor, & Szumowska, 2019, p. 118). Significance quest theory posits that the desire to matter and to be respected by oneself and close group members can underlie goals in extremist behaviour (Kruglanski et al., 2014). In this vein, policies and interventions which target social alienation can ensure that the awakening of this basic need is linked with positive outcomes, such as prosocial behaviour rather than extremism (Kruglanski et al., 2013).

4.4. Polarisation

The indirect effects of strong online group identity on increased support for extremist attitudes through social alienation, populism, and collective narcissism speak to the importance of social networks in the formation of such attitudes. Importantly, social networks can function as informational and normative influences in the maintenance of extremist behaviour and

attitudes by providing social support, validating narratives, and rewarding normative behaviour in aid of a specific goal (Kruglanski, Jasko, Chernikova, Dugas, & Webber, 2018). Indeed, one such narrative that online groups can provide and reinforce, as indicated by our results, is one of in-group superiority relative to other outgroups (collective narcissism), a sense of meaninglessness (social alienation) which must be overcome, and disenfranchisement with the perceived elite political institutions (populism). Taken together, these narratives play a part in motives for endorsing extremist attitudes. Importantly, our findings add to the relatively understudied area of *how* interaction with online spaces plays a role in radicalization and the emergence of extremist beliefs (see Bastug, Douai, & Akca, 2020; Gaudette, Scrivens, & Venkatesh, 2022; Mølmen & Ravndal, 2023) through highlighting the significance of shared group identities and the scripts that they can provide.

4.5. Patterns across our dataset

Some important observations can be made from the frequency with which some effects were consistently observed across countries. Of our I-GAP measures of injustice and grievances, social dominance orientation (SDO) is the strongest predictor of both radicalisation measures - across our model and all the countries included in the survey. Apart from this general effect of SDO, we can speak of two paths to radicalisation (which are not mutually exclusive), each corresponding to a different measure of radicalisation - either perceiving immigrants and minorities as “realistic threats” or expressing extremist attitudes. For the first path, we found that out of our I-GAP measures, one of the polarisation measures (online group identity) strongly predicted extremist attitudes (Italy, Kosovo, Serbia) in several countries. For the second path, data showed a strong connection between the I-GAP injustice measure of group relative deprivation and our radicalisation measure of perceiving migrants as “realistic threats” (for instance, again in Serbia). We emphasise the importance of social dominance orientation (predicting extremism for all 15 countries) and collective narcissism (predicting extremism for 10 countries except Kosovo, Austria, Italy, Finland, France, and Greece) as factors of radicalisation, in contrast to the lesser importance of perceptions of increased anomie. This means that current radicalisation is more often driven by the perceived threat of downward mobility in the social hierarchy than by the perception of a general societal crisis and threat to the social order.

Furthermore, two of our I-GAP measures of alienation - perceptions of increased anomie and breakdown of social norms - in several countries (for instance, Austria and Finland) predicted radicalisation, measured as seeing immigrants as realistic threats in several countries. We interpret this finding as pointing to the processual approach to radicalisation, meaning that perceiving migration as a threat is interwoven with and builds on and feeds other narratives, most prominently the perceived breakdown of social norms.

The importance of our I-GAP polarisation measure for radicalisation and online group identity must be highlighted. It not only predicts extremist attitudes, but the most commonly observed effect was that of a stronger online group identity predicting an increased sense of social cohesion in one’s neighbourhood. This means that the more respondents identified with an

online group, the stronger they perceived their neighbourhoods as cohesive. We could observe this effect in all countries sampled except Georgia (which had the smallest sample size). It should be noted that a stronger online group identity was also linked with increased social alienation in eleven countries (exceptions: Austria, Finland, Kosovo, Serbia, and Georgia). A stronger online group identity also frequently predicted increased collective narcissism across countries except France and Kosovo. Thus, although a strong online identity may have some protective qualities (predicting an increased sense of social cohesion), it is also associated with greater feelings of alienation and is therefore linked with greater vulnerability.

4.6. Attitudes towards Russia, and Russian and Ukrainian migrants

In the context of the extraordinary public focus that the Russia-Ukraine war has had in most European countries since 2022 (at least until the escalation in Palestine), the survey results are counterintuitive. Most of the factors predicting worse attitudes toward cooperation with Russians are typical of xenophobic reactions to other "alien" cultures and are at odds with the supposedly "moral" condemnation of Russia's war of aggression (only the links of feeling more social cohesion and trust in one's system of governance may fit this pattern, although even they are paralleled by contradictory effects of perceiving more social alienation and supporting more populist attitudes). Moreover, in contrast to the association of "pro-Russian" positions in the European context with the parties from the extreme political segments (far right and far left), holding extremist attitudes has a negative impact on the perception of Russia in our sample, which could be a manifestation of the general xenophobia. Even more puzzling is the fact that extremist attitudes are positively associated with improved perceptions of Russian and Ukrainian migrants and refugees. Otherwise, perceptions of both Russians and Ukrainians seem to be predicted by the same factors as perceptions of migrants from other countries. A note of caution should be added regarding the divergent patterns in individual countries, which could be related to the specifics of individual governments' positions on the Russian-Ukrainian war (Hungary, Georgia), the patterns of relocation of Ukrainian and Russian refugees, and similar idiosyncratic factors.

4.7 Conclusion

It is important to note that this study explored attitudinal extremism, which is distinct from behavioural extremism; by capturing attitudes, we were able to draw from the general population and investigate developing dissatisfaction with the status quo and idealistic support of sweeping change, which can both be targeted and exploited by violence-justifying ideologies. Additionally, this survey was a cross-sectional correlational design, providing only a single snapshot. However, our use of path analysis allowed for the investigation of distal mediating relationships, which at times were oppositional, reflecting the complex nature of radicalisation pathways. Indeed, not everyone who experiences grievance or injustice will go on to endorse extremist attitudes. Nonetheless, our findings support the role of extremist attitudes and ideologies as tools for individuals to restore threatened self-significance in their search for meaning (Jasko, LaFree, & Kruglanski, 2017; Kruglanski, et al., 2014). Relational perspectives, which consider social group identities, group-based worldviews, and intergroup

comparisons between one's ingroup and a perceived threatening outgroup, provide essential insight into the interactional underlying factors of radicalisation across the spectrum. Overall, our findings support calls for policies to address social-economic disparities (injustice) and social and existential motives (grievance, alienation, and polarisation) by focusing on social integration and righting discrimination and economic inequalities for youth, in particular, to mitigate the dangers of extremism (Adam-Troian, Tecmen, & Kaya, 2021).

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6. Appendices

6.1. Austria

The sample for Austria consisted of n = 292, of which only 3.77% of participants replied that they did not know their political attitudes. As such, these participants were excluded, and this variable was included in the path model, resulting in a final sample of n = 281.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
24.56 (4.47)	137	46.92	154	52.74	1	0.34

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	176	60.27
Agnostic/Atheist	53	18.15

Muslim	37	12.67
Other	24	8.22
Buddhist	1	0.34
Hindu	1	0.34
Jewish	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	64	21.92
No	207	70.89
Don't know	21	7.19

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Religion	23	35.94
Language	17	26.56
Gender	15	23.44
Sexuality	15	23.44
Colour or race	13	20.31
Nationality	12	18.75
Ethnic group	11	17.19
Age	4	6.25
Disability	4	6.25
Other	2	3.12

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	70	23.97	120	41.10	102	34.93
Sport or recreational organization	132	45.21	57	19.52	103	35.27
Art, music or educational organization	80	27.40	68	23.29	144	49.32
Labour union	51	17.47	84	28.77	157	53.77
Political party	33	11.30	66	22.60	193	66.10

Environmental organization	40	13.70	62	21.23	190	65.07
Professional association	33	11.30	69	23.63	190	65.07
Humanitarian or charitable organization	55	18.84	57	19.52	180	61.64
Consumer organization	40	13.70	58	19.86	194	66.44
Self-help group or mutual help group	40	13.70	63	21.58	189	64.73
Women's group	33	11.30	57	19.52	202	69.18
Other organization	17	5.82	37	12.67	238	81.51

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	56	19.18	205	70.21	31	10.62
Worked in a political party or action group	38	13.01	223	76.37	31	10.62
Worked in another ideological organization	39	13.36	225	77.05	28	9.59
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	44	15.07	205	70.21	43	14.73
Signed a petition	147	50.34	113	38.7	32	10.96
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	66	22.6	190	65.07	36	12.33
Boycotted certain products	95	32.53	152	52.05	45	15.41
Posted or shared anything about politics online	91	31.16	164	56.16	37	12.67

Predictors of realistic threat

Increased social dominance orientation was linked to greater perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat. Additionally, increased perception that one's national ingroup was more deprived economically than migrants was also linked to increased realistic threat. Greater experiences of anomie were also predictive of increased perceptions of threat. Regarding political ideologies, more right-wing political attitudes were also found to predict increased perception of realistic threat. Although we did not hypothesise a relationship between vulnerability and realistic threat, reporting greater social alienation was linked to lower perceived threat from migrants.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding a stronger belief in inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was linked with greater support for extremism. A stronger online group identity was also found to directly predict increased support for extremist attitudes. In terms of relational factors, perceiving that one's economic status was more deprived relative to migrants (individual relative deprivation) was linked with greater support for extremist attitudes. Regarding political ideologies, populism was linked with increased support for extremism. In terms of vulnerability, increased social alienation was linked with increased support for extremist attitudes.

Indirect predictors of extremism

Increased social dominance orientation indirectly predicted decreased support for extremist attitudes via decreased populism. However, the total indirect effect of social dominance

orientation on extremism was not significant, meaning that rather than having an indirect influence on extremism via other variables, greater social dominance orientation mainly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes directly.

Online group identity did not have any indirect effects on support for extremist attitudes. Similar to social dominance orientation, a stronger online group identity directly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes.

Increasingly right-wing political attitudes indirectly predicted increased support for extremism attitudes via increased individual relative deprivation. While the other indirect effects alone were not statistically significant, the total indirect effect was. Increasingly right-wing political attitudes, through their relationship with the mediators, indirectly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Perceiving one's ingroup to be superior to other social groups was linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Feeling less anomie and more trust in the Austrian government were both linked to more negative attitudes towards Russian culture. In terms of attitudes towards Russian migrants, feeling more embedded in one's community was linked with worsened attitudes towards Russian migrants in the past twelve months. Regarding Ukrainian migrants, feelings of anomie and perceptions that one's economic situation was more deprived relative to migrants were both linked to worsening attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the past twelve months.

Figure 3. Respecified model for Austria.

Situating the findings within the Austrian context

This country summary contextualises the D.Rad survey findings for Austria. It starts with giving an overview of the country context of radicalisation before analysing the main findings of the quantitative survey. According to the latest report of the Directorate General for Public Security (DSN 2023), the year 2022 was characterised by uncertainty and multiple crises, such as the Russian war of aggression against Ukraine, the energy crisis and high inflation, and the climate crisis. These crises are seen as “an ideal breeding ground for extremism” as they increase societal tensions and enhance the protest potential vis-à-vis state institutions (ibid., p. 76). The DSN states in its report that it expects the current loss of confidence in state structures to become more pronounced in the next years, whereby the focus areas of the institution lie on right- and left-wing extremism, anti-state associations, and Islamist extremism. Three notable trends have become hot topics: a) cyber security and potential cyberattacks; b) the war in Ukraine and the phenomenon of foreign fighters and foreign volunteers; and c) climate activists that increasingly make use of disruptive actions.

Right-wing extremist groups and anti-state movements have experienced an upswing during the Corona pandemic. The Documentation Centre of Austrian Resistance (DÖW) thereby points to the role of the so-called Corona demonstrations: “The Corona protests have been chalked up as an almost historic success by the Austrian extreme right. Not because they were extreme right-wing in their entirety, but because there were really protests where you could move completely freely and which you could also very strongly shape in the image to the outside world,” according to Bernhard Weidinger of the DÖW. Indeed, people from all walks of life were taking part in these regular demonstrations in the heart of Vienna which

brought about “unlikely coalitions” of esoterics, right-wingers, conspiracy theorists, vaccination opponents and concerned citizens with no pronounced political agenda.

Analysis of survey results

In the Austrian case, a stronger online group identity directly predicts greater support for extremist attitudes. There is a growing strand of research emphasising the role of social media in shaping extremist attitudes, also in the case of Austria, with the increasing importance of common social media platforms and the diminishing role of forums in the darknet. Nicolas Stockhammer, an Austrian terrorism expert, argues that meanwhile, almost 80 percent of those who radicalise in the context of Islamism do so on the Internet, via social media platforms like TikTok and Twitch. There, they find content that is offered in a way suitable for the target audience: The content is always the same, but the presentation is different, and the language of young people is deliberately spoken, according to Stockhammer. Identifying with such content strengthens the belonging and attachment to an online group, also against the background that many from this group have never really arrived in Austrian society or are not accepted.

Furthermore, the contact restrictions during the pandemic hit particularly young people hard. It can be assumed that the general affiliation with online groups has been strengthened during that time. The results of the path model further indicate that a stronger online group identity predicts higher collective narcissism, which comes as no surprise. We have no explanation for why a stronger online group identity predicts stronger feelings of social cohesion in one’s neighbourhood and community, with the expectation being that people drawn to the online world retreat from the offline world. Unfortunately, we found no studies to contextualise this result, but we probably must abandon the black-and-white thinking regarding online/offline realities of belonging.

Higher perceptions of anomie predict stronger perceptions that migrants pose a realistic threat to Austria. In studies on anti-migrant attitudes, this is a frequently found result. Hilde Weiss (2004), whose research results show that “the ‘crisis’ of society and the threat posed by ‘the foreigners’ combine to form a collective interpretation of the state of society’. Such interpretations are offered in political-public discourses and adopted – even when there are no mass individual threats and no immediate economic crisis. The claimed intense threat from foreigners is part of an interpretation that refers to change and modernisation, but at the same time, it is vehemently directed against phenomena of change (Friesl, Renner and Wiesel, 2010). In Austria, as in many other countries, anomie and xenophobia are interrelated. A society characterised by multiple crises, social inequality and economic instability can lead people to look for easy solutions and possibly resort to rejecting “strangers” to channel their fears, insecurities and frustrations.

Higher populism predicts higher support for extremist attitudes. This again comes as no surprise, given the pronounced presence of populist rhetoric in party politics in Austria. The best-known populist party is the FPÖ. It was founded as early as 1956 and has gained considerable influence in recent decades, including participation in previous governments. Due to the FPÖ’s focus on immigration, nationalism, Euroscepticism and rejection of the

Corona measures, the party has gained considerable influence. In current polls, party leader Herbert Kickl is in the lead when it comes to the question of who should be the next chancellor in Austria (next elections on the federal level in 2024). But populist elements can also be found in other (opposition) parties in Austria, which has led to a fragmentation of the political spectrum and a change in the political landscape. Anyway, it is the FPÖ that steers public debates using an aggressive language and hate speech according to linguists and other social scientists (Heinisch, Werner and Habersack, 2020; Wodak, 2018). They fuel xenophobic sentiments, frame immigration as a problem and associate Islam with terrorism (Ajanovic, Mayer and Sauer, 2016).

Increasingly right-wing political attitudes predicted greater individual relative deprivation (individual relative deprivation) *and* greater group relative deprivation (group relative deprivation). Increasingly, right-wing political attitudes also predicted greater perceptions that migrants are a realistic threat. Here, the question arises as to the direction of the influence: Isn't it – at least for the first result – the other way around that a perceived individual deprivation influences political attitudes, i.e., people who feel deprived are more likely to be politically right-wing and prone to populism? This would be in line with election analyses from Austria, which depict that voters for the FPÖ have comparatively low educational levels, and half of them form part of the working class (there is no specific data on income). Regarding salient topics, voters of the FPÖ see immigration as the most important elective motif. This is also mirrored in the party's election campaigns, where the topics of group relative deprivation and anti-immigrant sentiments are often combined. The FPÖ has been repeating this argument like a prayer mill for decades. For example: "More courage for our 'Viennese blood' - Too much foreignness does no one any good" (2010 election poster).

The path model proves that a higher social dominance orientation directly predicts greater support for extremist attitudes. Unfortunately, we have not found any recent research results on this from the Austrian context. Nevertheless, these results align with the outcomes of the Austrian Democracy Monitor, which outlines that satisfaction with the political system and trust in political institutions is decreasing while the desire for a strong leader is rising.

The path model for the Austrian case explained 36.80% of the variability in extremism scores. SDO thereby only had an indirect effect via populism on extremist attitudes. However, while SDO and online group identity did not have a total mediating effect on extremism, a higher SDO and a stronger online group identity both directly predicted more extremist attitudes. Only political attitudes had a total positive mediating effect on extremist attitudes, driven mainly by right-wing attitudes predicting greater individual relative deprivation and, in turn, more extremist attitudes, which is in line with the previous paragraphs.

Due to the small sample size, it is impossible to discern between urban and peri-urban areas in analysing extremist attitudes. A comparison between those living in large cities (Vienna and capital cities of federal provinces) and those living in more rural communities shows no significant differences in political attitudes, populism and extremism. However, the divide between urban and rural areas is increasing, and while extremism and violent acts used to be

present predominantly in cities, the pandemic has made people take to the streets who did not use to express their political opinions publicly.

Attitudes towards Ukrainians and Russians: According to the results of a Eurobarometer survey published in December 2022, 74 per cent of the EU population approve of the European Union's support for Ukraine following Russia's invasion. In Austria, the proportion of supporters, at 60 per cent, was clearly below the EU average. The EU sanctions against Russia were approved by 73 per cent of respondents EU-wide, in Austria only 57 percent. This scepticism in Austria has to be seen in relation to the right-wing FPÖ's stance on the matter, with the party leader Herbert Kickl being against the sanctions targeting Russia and positioning himself as the defender of Austria's everlasting neutrality.

The findings of the D.Rad survey confirm the results of the Eurobarometer. In the past 12 months, attitudes towards Russian migrants have improved slightly. Participants reported that their attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the last 12 months did not change significantly. The somehow neutral attitudes towards Ukrainian refugees can be explained by the general socio-political environment that is marked by anti-immigrant sentiments. Furthermore, individual relative deprivation and group relative deprivation increased strongly since the beginning of the war due to inflation and the energy crisis.

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6.2. Bosnia and Herzegovina

Bosnia and Herzegovina had 33.04% of participants reporting not knowing their political attitudes. These participants were kept, but the variable was removed from the path model, resulting in a sample of $n = 336$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
27.39 (8.59)	159	47.32	177	52.68	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Muslim	195	58.04
Christian	100	29.76
Other	20	5.95
Agnostic/Atheist	20	5.95
Buddhist	1	0.30
Jewish	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	77	22.92
No	212	63.10
Don't know	47	13.99

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Nationality	45	58.44
Religion	44	57.14
Language	17	22.08
Ethnic group	15	19.48
Other	9	11.69

Sexuality	8	10.39
Age	6	7.79
Gender	6	7.79
Disability	3	3.90
Colour or race	0	0.00

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	124	36.90	95	28.27	117	34.82
Sport or recreational organization	96	28.57	86	25.60	154	45.83
Art, music or educational organization	95	28.27	74	22.02	167	49.70
Labour union	46	13.69	91	27.08	199	59.23
Political party	39	11.61	89	26.49	208	61.90
Environmental organization	61	18.15	89	26.49	186	55.36
Professional association	62	18.45	90	26.79	184	54.76
Humanitarian or charitable organization	125	37.20	79	23.51	132	39.29
Consumer organization	39	11.61	83	24.70	214	63.69
Self-help group or mutual help group	50	14.88	69	20.54	217	64.58
Women's group	64	19.05	64	19.05	208	61.9
Other organization	29	8.63	52	15.48	255	75.89

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	79	23.51	230	68.45	27	8.04
Worked in a political party or action group	65	19.35	251	74.70	20	5.95
Worked in another ideological organization	41	12.20	271	80.65	24	7.14
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	51	15.18	260	77.38	25	7.44
Signed a petition	162	48.21	149	44.35	25	7.44
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	87	25.89	224	66.67	25	7.44
Boycotted certain products	120	35.71	187	55.65	29	8.63
Posted or shared anything about politics online	111	33.04	195	58.04	30	8.93

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was linked with perceiving migrants as a threat to one's national ingroup.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. In terms of relational factors, higher collective narcissism and perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants were both associated with increased support of extremist attitudes. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing increased social alienation and decreased social cohesion both predicted greater support for extremist attitudes.

Indirect predictors on extremism

SDO did not have any significant indirect effects on extremist attitudes, nor was the sum of these statistically significant. Rather than indirectly influencing extremism via other variables, greater SDO directly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes.

A stronger online group identity indirectly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes via increased collective narcissism and increased social alienation. On the other hand, a stronger online group identity predicted increased social cohesion and increased social cohesion subsequently predicted decreased support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect of online group identity on support for extremist attitudes was not significant.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

None of the variables of interest (i.e. social dominance orientation, online group identity, collective narcissism, anomie, individual and group relative deprivation, social cohesion, social alienation, populism, political trust, perceptions of migrants as realistic threats, support for extremist attitudes) reliably predicted attitudes towards Russian culture or Russian or Ukrainian migrants.

Figure 4. Respecified model for Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Situating the findings within the Bosnia and Herzegovina context

This report aims to provide information about the sense of discrimination retrieved from the D.Rad survey implemented in Bosnia and Herzegovina. It includes information about the group affiliations of participants and their sense of discrimination. The survey also informs about participants' membership in different religious, cultural, professional, humanitarian or other types of organisations. To provide clear information about the grounds of discrimination, the analysis will also discuss the correlations of the sense of discrimination according to sex, age, and membership of a particular group. The report will also analyse the paths to extremism in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The survey recognises two different types of paths to extremism: direct and indirect pathways to extremism.

Since Bosnia and Herzegovina is a deeply ethnically divided country, which is a direct consequence of the war that took place from 1992 – 1995 and ended with the signing of the Dayton Peace Agreement in November 1995, we still witness discrimination based on ethnical background, which can cause an extremist reaction among members of groups that are being discriminated. Radical right-wing political rhetoric and actions, ethnically divided school curriculums, and high unemployment are certainly all factors that contribute to the rise of extremism in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Pečković 2018, IRI 2017, RAN 2022). Ethnicity or religious affiliation is not the only grounds for discrimination in Bosnia. The LGBT population in Bosnia and Herzegovina is often discriminated against and even physically attacked. For instance, a physical attack happened in Banja Luka (A city in north-west Bosnia and Herzegovina) in March 2023 when several activists were injured (RFE/RL's Balkan Service, 2023).

Introduction

336 participants completed the survey, of which 159 (47.32% of all participants) were male and 177 (52.68%) were female. On average, participants were 27.39 years old. Most participants have declared themselves as Muslims (58.04 %). Christians are in second place (29.76 %). After that are Others and Agnostics/Atheists (both 5.95 %).

A significant number of participants feel that they belong to a group that has been discriminated against. Namely, 22 % of participants say that they belong to a group that has been discriminated against, 63.10 % say that they do not feel that their group has been discriminated and 13.99 % are not sure if their group has been discriminated against. Most participants were discriminated against based on nationality (58.44 %) and religion (57.14 %). At this point, it is important to mention two phenomena: in Bosnia and Herzegovina, religion and nationality are closely connected. In most cases, Serbs are Orthodox Christians, and Bosniaks are Muslims. The other phenomenon is that in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the political rhetoric casts ethnicities as nations. It is a complex historical issue that demands detailed explanation that is not in the scope of this report. 10.39 % of participants feel discriminated against according to their sexuality.

One of the examples of ethnic discrimination is the case of official language used in the Republic of Srpska (One of the two entities in Bosnia and Herzegovina). In Konjević Polje (a town in east Bosnia and Herzegovina, Republic of Srpska) parents of school children from a local school lead a struggle for their children to learn Bosnian, the language in their school, which is one of the three officially recognised languages in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Serb language, Croat language and Bosnian Language). Serb authorities have called this language a “language of Bosniak people”, which the parents strongly object to and feel that they and their children are discriminated against since the Bosnian language is officially recognised in Bosnia and Herzegovina (N1, 2022).

The discrimination against the LGBT population was shown in the case of the physical attack on an LGBT activist in Banja Luka on 18.03.2023. A few hours after the police banned the LGBT event, activists met to discuss further activities. During their meeting, they were attacked, and several activists suffered injuries during the attack (CRD, 2023).

All these facts support the thesis mentioned in the introductory part of this report that says that most discriminations in Bosnia and Herzegovina are based on nationality (ethnicity) and sexual orientation.

Most of the participants have reported to be members of some organisation. A significant number of participants (61.90 %) has said to be a member of some political party. According to the National Youth Survey in Bosnia and Herzegovina implemented by USAID, the “*largest proportion of youth prefer working for the government/public sector (36 %)*” (USAID, 2022). Being a member of a high-ranking political party increases the opportunities to be employed in the public sector, which guarantees high salaries and safer jobs than the private sector. A large number of participants claim to be members of environmental organisations (55.36 %) or organisations such as women's groups (61.9 %), self-help groups, or mutual help groups (64.58 %). This indicates a high level of social consonance among the participants about issues meant to be for the greater good of the community. Many participants are members of

humanitarian or charitable organisations (39.29 %), which indicates an awareness of the necessity to help those in need.

Although 61.09 % of the participants claimed to be a member of some political party, only 19.35 % reported to have worked in a political party or action group in the past 12 months. This could be interpreted as many of them having left the political parties or being inactive members of some political party. The most important political activism of the participants could be seen in the signing of different petitions. Namely, 48,21 % have signed a petition in the past 12 months. These results show low political activism among people in Bosnia and Herzegovina. As the Youth Study in Bosnia and Herzegovina states (2018), the level of trust of Bosnian and Herzegovinian youth towards politicians in Bosnia and Herzegovina is on a very low level. *„Trust in political institutions, including the BiH Presidency, the national Parliament, government and political parties is extremely low. The political system of the country favours informal decision-making between party leaders behind closed doors rather than open and inclusive deliberation, thus limiting avenues for citizens to take direct action“* (Turčilo, 2018)

According to the survey, members of the groups that have been discriminated against reported greater perceptions of individual relative deprivation (Individual relative deprivation) than members of groups that are not discriminated against. This could come from the fact that members of discriminated groups do not belong to the dominant culture in Bosnia and Herzegovina. This, again, means that their nationality is not in the majority in the place where they live; they belong to the LGBT population or some other minority group. Participants from discriminated groups have also reported that they, as a group (group relative deprivation-Group relative deprivation), are worse than the groups that are not discriminated against. This means that they perceive themselves discriminated against both on the individual and the collective level. This, again, leads to the feeling of social alienation of members of discriminated groups, which participants (members of discriminated groups) reported.

Participants from discriminated or socially alienated groups reported greater support for extremist attitudes. Social alienation creates a sense of social injustice and grievance, which are among the main push factors for extremist behaviour or joining extremist and radical groups (Oruč & Obradović, 2020). So, if the individuals do not feel attached to their community and feel isolated, there is a great danger that they will seek validation elsewhere, possibly in some of the radical or extremist groups. Considering the correlations with the age of the participants, the survey has shown that older participants share less right-wing values and have less trust in the national political system.

The survey has shown that discrimination is still widespread in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Discrimination is mainly directed toward minority groups, such as ethnic minorities in different parts of Bosnia and Herzegovina, which is a direct consequence of territorial divisions on the ethnic basis in Bosnia and Herzegovina, or minority groups such as the LGBT or Roma population. All of the above mentioned shows the need to question dominant cultures, such as ethnic superiority culture that believes in having the right to dominate territories that mostly remained on the combat lines from the war during the 90s.

The ethnic divisions in Bosnia and Herzegovina are incorporated in the Bosnian Constitution, based on the Dayton Peace Agreement in distinguishing the three constituent peoples (Serbs, Croats and Bosniaks) from others who, according to the electoral law, cannot run themselves for the presidency of Bosnia and Herzegovina or for the Home of the Peoples. This showcases the institutionalisation of ethnic segregation and discrimination against citizens of Bosnia and Herzegovina who are not members of the three constituent nationalities. Institutionalised ethnic segregation is also present in the education system of Bosnia and Herzegovina in the sense that three different school curriculums are official in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Serb, Croat and Bosnian) depending on which nationality is in the majority in particular part of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

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6.3. Finland

Finland had 25.95% of participants reporting not knowing their political attitudes. This variable was subsequently excluded from the model, keeping all participants and resulting in a final sample of $n = 316$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
24.84 (4.57)	152	48.10	163	51.58	1	0.32

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	240	75.95
Agnostic/Atheist	59	18.67
Other	7	2.22
Jewish	4	1.27
Muslim	4	1.27
Buddhist	2	0.63
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	57	18.04
No	240	75.95
Don't know	19	6.01

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Sexuality	19	33.33
Colour or race	16	28.07
Gender	14	24.56
Nationality	11	19.30
Religion	10	17.54

Language	10	17.54
Age	9	15.79
Ethnic group	7	12.28
Disability	7	12.28
Other	3	5.26

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	58	18.35	150	47.47	108	34.18
Sport or recreational organization	81	25.63	90	28.48	145	45.89
Art, music or educational organization	63	19.94	98	31.01	155	49.05
Labour union	78	24.68	121	38.29	117	37.03
Political party	37	11.71	77	24.37	202	63.92
Environmental organization	50	15.82	72	22.78	194	61.39
Professional association	51	16.14	89	28.16	176	55.70
Humanitarian or charitable organization	40	12.66	84	26.58	192	60.76
Consumer organization	42	13.29	77	24.37	197	62.34
Self-help group or mutual help group	42	13.29	80	25.32	194	61.39
Women's group	46	14.56	76	24.05	194	61.39
Other organization	31	9.81	47	14.87	238	75.32

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	75	23.73	212	67.09	29	9.18
Worked in a political party or action group	55	17.41	236	74.68	25	7.91
Worked in another ideological organization	49	15.51	244	77.22	23	7.28
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	91	28.80	195	61.71	30	9.49
Signed a petition	139	43.99	143	45.25	34	10.76
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	77	24.37	216	68.35	23	7.28
Boycotted certain products	157	49.68	128	40.51	31	9.81
Posted or shared anything about politics online	106	33.54	187	59.18	23	7.28

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was linked with perceiving migrants as a greater threat to one's national ingroup. Stronger feelings of anomie were also linked with increased perceived threat from migrants.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was also linked directly with increased support for extremist attitudes. Interestingly, and in contrast to our predictions, perceiving that one's economic situation was more deprived relative to

migrants was associated with lower support of extremist attitudes. Regarding political ideologies, greater endorsement of populism was linked with more support for extremist ideologies. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing greater social alienation was linked with more support for extremist attitudes.

Indirect predictors on extremism

Increased social dominance orientation indirectly predicted decreased support for extremist attitudes via decreased populism and subsequent decreased support for extremism. On the other hand, increased social dominance orientation also predicted decreased individual relative deprivation, but decreased individual relative deprivation predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect of social dominance orientation on extremist attitudes was not significant, and instead, increased social dominance orientation directly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes.

A stronger online group identity indirectly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes via increased populism. However, the total indirect effect of online group identity was not significant.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

In terms of vulnerability, feeling more embedded in one's community and experiencing more social alienation both separately predicted more negative attitudes towards Russia. Perceiving that one's national ingroup was economically more deprived relative to migrants was also associated with more negative attitudes towards Russian culture. Finally, increased political trust in the Finnish system of governance was predictive of more negative views towards Russia. Regarding attitudes towards Russian migrants, feeling more socially embedded in one's community and endorsing more populist ideology were both separately linked with improved attitudes towards Russian migrants in the past twelve months.

None of the variables of interest (i.e. social dominance orientation, online group identity, collective narcissism, anomie, individual and group relative deprivation, social cohesion, social alienation, populism, political trust, perceptions of migrants as realistic threats, support for extremist attitudes) reliably predicted attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants.

Figure 5. Respecified model for Finland.

Situating the findings within the Finnish context

This chapter contextualises the D.Rad survey findings for Finland, a Nordic welfare state with high political trust (Bäck et al. 2019) and low levels of political violence. In Finland, regional differences are relatively small, and no clear geographic pattern of radicalisation exists. Humanitarian and work- and family-related immigration have increased since the 1980s, impacting particularly big cities. In the 2000s, the traditional consensus-based political model was criticised for being ill-adapted to new issues (Saukkonen 2013). The right-populist Finns Party changed the party landscape in 2011 and moved towards a radical-right stance after it split in 2017 (Palonen 2021). New far-right parties have emerged in the 2020s (Fagerholm 2022) with a pro-Putinist fringe (Lahti & Palonen 2023). The intelligence service considers the far right and radical Islamism as the most prominent terrorism threats (SUPO 2023). When the survey was conducted, Finland prepared for parliamentary elections in April 2023; the first regional elections were held in January 2022. The war in Ukraine had a significant effect on Finnish politics and societal atmosphere with strong pro-Ukraine and pro-NATO undertones. The topic of violent youth gangs, mainly consisting of immigrant youth, was also present in the media (e.g., Kirsi 2021). The elections amplified the political debate on security, economy, social policy, immigration, climate and energy.

316 participants (48.10% male, 51.58% female, 0.32% other), on average 24.84 years old (+/- 4.57 years), completed the survey. While their organisational memberships reflect the Finnish tradition of registered associations (Siisiäinen & Kankainen 2009), the high amount of political party members – almost one in three – is surprising, as the general population amounts to five percent (Helminen 2020). Although the “political” survey topic could have led to an over-representation of party members, a more plausible explanation is a misinterpretation of the question because of the option of choosing between “passive” and “active” (11.71%) membership. The respondents had participated in various political activities during the last 12

months, possibly due to the proximity of several elections. The participants' age may account for the boycotting products (almost half of the respondents) being higher than among the wider population (see Haerpfer et al. 2022).

Approximately one-fifth of the participants described themselves as members of at least one discriminated group. Among these 57 respondents, one-third mentioned sexuality, every fourth race or gender and one-fifth nationality, largely in line with previous research (e.g., Helsingin kaupunki, kaupunginkanslia, osallisuus ja neuvonta 2021). Participants who reported being members of one or more discriminated groups were less right-wing compared to those who did not do so. They also reported lower perceptions of social cohesion (mutual trust, shared values and solidarity) in their neighbourhood and community, which might be related to their feelings of discrimination. They had higher collective narcissism, a belief in the superiority of one's group associated with a need for external validation and sensitivity to perceived threats or criticisms of the group, which can be related to group identity but, in more pronounced forms, can lead to negative outcomes like prejudice, hostility towards outgroups, and intergroup conflict. The results can be compared with a study among Finnish Russian speakers that distinguished more positive forms of ingroup identification from perceived ingroup *superiority* that was negatively associated with outgroup attitudes (Mähönen et al. 2014). In extreme forms, the idea of the ingroup's superiority combined with a sense of victimhood has been visible in Finnish cases of political violence (Lounela et al., 2021).

As in earlier Finnish studies (e.g., Grigaitytė et al. 2019, Benjamin et al. 2023), men had harsher attitudes regarding migrants and social hierarchies and were more prone to extremist views than women. They reported greater political trust, although earlier research has not shown gender differences (Bäck et al. 2019). Women reported stronger populist attitudes than men. All participants were young adults, but older respondents reported lower political trust and stronger attitudes against migrants and Russia than younger ones, while earlier Finnish research on the topic has been mixed (Kuusisto & Kallioniemi, 2014; Grigaitytė et al., 2019; Nshom & Croucher 2017).

The participants' attitudes towards Russian migrants had worsened a little, but those towards Ukrainian migrants had improved in the last 12 months. Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine has affected the political atmosphere in Finland, which has a long border and a history of past wars with Russia. A recent study showed worsened attitudes towards Russia but relatively positive ones towards Russians (Haavisto 2022). Russian speakers form the biggest group of people with a foreign national tongue in Finland (94,000 people or 1.7% of the Finnish population; Official Statistics of Finland n.d.). In a recent survey, four-fifths of Russian speakers in Finland reported not having experienced discrimination or hate speech caused by the war (Cultura-säätiö 2023).

In the D.Rad survey, higher social dominance orientation (SDO, the approval of group-based hierarchies and inequalities) predicted decreased individual relative deprivation (individual relative deprivation; a perception of the self as worse off compared to others) but increased group relative deprivation (group relative deprivation; a perception of one's ingroup as less

fortunate than the outgroup). Neither individual relative deprivation nor group relative deprivation predicted perceptions of migrants as threats. Surprisingly, increased individual relative deprivation predicted *decreased* support for extremist attitudes, as relative deprivation theory typically predicts increased support for extremism among those who feel deprived (Kunst & Obaidi 2020). Higher SDO predicted decreased feelings of social cohesion and decreased populism in one's neighbourhood and community. It also directly predicted greater perceptions of migrants as a threat to Finland and greater support for extremist attitudes. These findings align with studies suggesting that higher SDO correlates with negative attitudes towards outgroups and supports social hierarchies (Benjamin et al., 2023).

Increased social alienation predicted increased support for extremist attitudes, also shown in earlier studies (Bélanger et al. 2019). Populism also predicted increased extremism but had a negative correlation with SDO, although SDO also predicted extremism. As populism refers to an expression of the general will of the people and antagonism between the people and the elite, it can be incoherent with more authoritarian positions despite its anti-establishment character. Increased anomie or the perceived breakdown of social norms predicted a stronger perception of migrants as a threat, in line with studies linking anomie to increased prejudice and hostility towards outsiders (Legge & Heitmeyer 2012). A stronger online group identity was associated with increased collective narcissism, increased perception of social cohesion in one's neighbourhood and community and increased populism. This can be seen as consistent with social identity theory, which suggests that individuals derive self-esteem and identity from their group memberships (Tajfel et al. 2004[1979]).

Higher SDO, increased populism and feelings of social alienation directly predicted greater support for extremist attitudes. While SDO had a direct relationship with extremist attitudes, its indirect effects through populism and individual relative deprivation were complex and ultimately non-significant. This indicates that the preference for social dominance associated with high SDO plays a more direct role in supporting extremism rather than being mediated by feelings of relative deprivation or populist views. The non-significant total indirect effect suggests that other variables not included in this study might impact extremist attitudes. Altogether, 28.90% of the variability in participants' extremist attitudes could be explained by the path model developed in D.Rad.

Finland's characteristics – the Nordic welfare state model, high political trust, a consensual political culture and a low level of political violence – can act as a buffer so that perceived relative deprivation does not lead to a perception of migrants as a threat or to increased extremism. Participants who reported being members of discriminated groups were also less right-wing and did not belong to such groups, possibly affecting the results. In the survey, anomie increased the perception of migrants as a threat, possibly reflecting the political debate on immigrant youth gangs. The connection of SDO with both extremism and views on migrants as a threat aligned with previous research, although the survey did not necessarily capture all the factors at play. Populism correlated negatively with SDO but predicted increased extremism, possibly because of its simultaneous anti-elitist and anti-establishment character.

This finding is also interesting considering a move from an anti-elitist discourse towards a far-right one within the Finnish party populism (Palonen 2021).

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6.4. France

France had 20.36% of participants who did not know their political attitudes. The path model keeps these participants but excludes this variable, having a final sample of $n = 329$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
24.55 (5.01)	154	46.81	174	52.89	1	0.30

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	111	33.74
Muslim	107	32.52
Sikh	46	13.98
Agnostic/Atheist	46	13.98
Other	15	4.56
Jewish	3	0.91
Bahá'í	1	0.30
Buddhist	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	106	32.22
No	198	60.18
Don't know	25	7.60

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Religion	70	66.04
Colour or race	43	40.57
Nationality	36	33.96
Ethnic group	17	16.04
Language	14	13.21

Sexuality	11	10.38
Gender	8	7.55
Other	4	3.77
Age	3	2.83
Disability	1	0.94

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	74	22.49	132	40.12	123	37.39
Sport or recreational organization	95	28.88	104	31.61	130	39.51
Art, music or educational organization	48	14.59	95	28.88	186	56.53
Labour union	46	13.98	73	22.19	210	63.83
Political party	37	11.25	78	23.71	214	65.05
Environmental organization	50	15.20	95	28.88	184	55.93
Professional association	68	20.67	81	24.62	180	54.71
Humanitarian or charitable organization	65	19.76	89	27.05	175	53.19
Consumer organization	51	15.50	79	24.01	199	60.49
Self-help group or mutual help group	65	19.76	93	28.27	171	51.98
Women's group	52	15.81	80	24.32	197	59.88
Other organization	46	13.98	45	13.68	238	72.34

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	89	27.05	186	56.53	54	16.41
Worked in a political party or action group	57	17.33	225	68.39	47	14.29
Worked in another ideological organization	67	20.36	207	62.92	55	16.72
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	85	25.84	189	57.45	55	16.72
Signed a petition	126	38.30	151	45.90	52	15.81
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	149	45.29	136	41.34	44	13.37
Boycotted certain products	142	43.16	144	43.77	43	13.07
Posted or shared anything about politics online	127	38.60	154	46.81	48	14.59

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was linked with increased perceptions of threat from migrants. Although we did not hypothesise any links between political ideologies and perceptions of threat, holding lower populist beliefs predicted lower perceptions of migrants as a threat.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was also associated directly with increased support for extremist attitudes. A stronger online group identity was also directly linked with increased support of extremist attitudes. Perceiving that migrants were a threat to one's national ingroup (realistic threat) was linked with increased support of extremist attitudes. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing more social alienation was associated with increased support for extremism.

Indirect predictors on extremism

Social dominance orientation indirectly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes via increased perceptions of realistic threat. More intricately, increased social dominance orientation predicted decreased populism, decreased populism subsequently predicted increased perceptions of realistic threat, and increased perceptions of realistic threat subsequently predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect of social dominance orientation was not significant; instead, increased social dominance orientation directly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes.

A stronger online group identity predicted increased populism, which subsequently predicted decreased perceptions of realistic threat, which in turn predicted decreased support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect was insignificant; instead, a stronger online group identity directly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Experiencing more social alienation and endorsing more extremist attitudes were both separately associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Regarding Russian migrants, feeling more embedded in one's community (social cohesion) and perceiving migrants in general as a larger threat to France were both separately associated with worsening attitudes towards Russian migrants in the past twelve months. On the other hand, having stronger beliefs about group hierarchies and having greater political trust predicted improved attitudes towards Russian migrants.

None of the variables of interest (i.e. social dominance orientation, online group identity, collective narcissism, anomie, individual and group relative deprivation, social cohesion, social alienation, populism, political trust, perceptions of migrants as realistic threats, support for extremist attitudes) reliably predicted attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants.

Figure 6. Respecified model for France.

Situating the findings within the French context

The survey results corroborate many of the findings in our reports and observations in the French case study.

Disproportionate representation of religious adherence

To contextualise the discussion, it is important to note that there are some surprising results within the survey. Most importantly, the breakdown of the participants by religious affiliation is (very) non-representative of actual religious distribution in France. According to the survey, one-third of its participants identified as Christian, another third as Muslims, only ~14% as atheists/agnostic and another ~14% as Sikh. While the percentage of Christians in the survey reflects their estimated proportion in the population, recent studies of religious affiliation show that 51% of the population aged 18 to 59 in metropolitan France say they have no religion. In contrast, only 10% identify as Muslim, and the Sikh population is estimated to be less than 0.05% of the population (Insee, *Immigrants and descendants of immigrants*, 2023; Bhavya Dore, “France’s Sikh Minority Looks Set to Vote Against Marine Le Pen”, *The Wire*, 2017).

Far-right’s appeal to women

The survey recorded no differences in political attitudes or support of extremist attitudes between men and women. These findings corroborate other studies conducted in France on the far-right’s success in attracting female voters. As we note in WP5.2 on France, far-right movements in France have managed to close the “Radical Right Gender Gap” and find support among women. The major success in attracting female voters was achieved by Marine Le Pen, who has “managed to garner the same level of support in her male and female constituencies” for three consecutive presidential elections (in 2012, 2017, and 2022) (Mayer, 2015, 2022). The fact that an upcoming leader of the far-right, Marion Maréchal (Le Pen) –

the niece of Marine Le Pen and member of the extreme-right political party *Reconquête* led by Eric Zemmour – is female as well, has further consolidated this support among women voters.

There is also no established difference between genders on the range of sensitive political issues, from Russia to migration. This, too, may be tied to the fact that women are strongly represented in the far right and that since 1999, French law has established gender electoral quotas in national and municipal elections (with fines imposed on parties when gender parity is not respected). However, the platform of the far-right is clearly seen as being at least partially hostile to migration since migrants tend to support left-wing politics. This is demonstrated in the platforms where the left and especially the far-left (such as the *La France Insoumise* party founded by Jean-Luc Mélenchon) have been increasingly calling for regularisation of the status of all migrants whereas the far-right and the centre-right has made stopping all migration and controlling migration (respectively) an essential part of their political platform. Thus, Mélenchon has recently declared that as president, he “would start with a wave of massive regularisation” of migrants in France. In contrast, Marion Maréchal considers the EU migration policy as “totally unreasonable” and calls to replace it with the Australian “No Way” uncompromising approach against “families, children, unaccompanied children, qualified workers” (*Immigration: «Si je venais à gouverner, je commencerais par une vague de régularisation massive», annonce Mélenchon*, 2023; *Qu'est-ce que la politique migratoire du « no way » que Marion Maréchal appelle à mettre en place ?*, JDD, 2023).

Discrimination against Muslims

The percentage of Muslim participants in the survey (32.52%) roughly equals the share of participants who identified as belonging to a group discriminated against in France (32.22%). This suggests that the Muslim population is the largest religious group that experiences sentiments of discrimination (primarily in comparison with the French Christian population).

On the other hand, the percentage of participants in the survey reporting that their group is discriminated against on religious grounds (66%) is significantly higher than those recorded in a recent study. A poll conducted in 2019 revealed that only 42% of Muslims in France had experienced at least one form of discrimination linked to their religion (the percentage of Muslims reporting to have experienced discrimination on religious grounds in the five years before the poll was 32%) (Ifop, *Etat des lieux des discriminations et des agressions envers les musulmans de France*, 2019). The survey’s findings match the 2019 data only regarding veiled women, 60% of whom reported having been discriminated against, versus 44% of non-veiled women. The differences in the two sets of data might be partially due to the rise of anti-Muslim sentiment in France or to similar sentiments among other participants in the survey who affiliated as Sikh, Jewish or “Other”.

Discrimination against women

The obtained results are also surprising with respect to the sentiment of discrimination against women in the general population. While more than 50% of the survey’s participants were women, less than 8% reported being discriminated against based on gender. Even when

accounting for the higher proportion of this sentiment among women, this percentage is significantly lower than that obtained in other studies. In a recent survey conducted among a representative sample of the French population on the opinions and knowledge about gender equality, only 8% of the respondents said that “women and men are treated the same”, and 42% of French women (versus 27% of men) said that a lack of laws is a major reason for gender inequality (Focus2030, “*French Views on Gender Equality*”, 2023). Similarly, a 2023 government report on “the state of sexism in France” showed that “situations of discrimination, violence and harassment [against women] are experienced in alarming proportions. The report, based on a representative sample of 2,500 participants, showed that 23% of women have experienced a pay gap with a male colleague in an equal position or with equal skills, and 13% have experienced discrimination in employment, rates that rise to 34% and 21% for managers. Moreover, 37% of the surveyed women reported having experienced non-consensual sexual relations (HCE, “*Rapport annuel 2023 sur l’état des lieux du sexisme en France*”, 2023).

Although the survey allowed them to choose more than one group affiliation based on which they consider themselves to be discriminated against, this discrepancy may be related to the high percentage of participants who experienced discrimination based on their religion. The data may suggest that a strong contingent of Muslim women and women of colour consider that they are discriminated against *more* for their religion and/or race than for their gender.

Participation in social organisations

The high participation in religious, recreational, educational and other associations recorded in the survey corroborates the fact that despite the history of Jacobin centralisation and anti-associationalism in France, the French maintain a very strong inclination towards group affiliation—which has been confirmed in political sociology over the last 40 years (Michel Forsé, “Les créations d’associations : un indicateur de changement social,” *Revue de l’OFCE*, 1984). Financial investment on the part of the state presumably has an important impact on French participation in sports as France devotes most of its money to sports in the European Union (“*Sports Economy*”). This may be reflected in the survey, which shows that more than 60% of the participants say they are actively or inactively involved in a sport or recreational organisation. Sports programs have been an important entry point for deradicalisation programs organised by the state and associations involved in preventing radicalisation in partnership with the government (WP3.1, WP10). This data is also confirmed by a 2005 report according to which “immigrants often engage in cultural associations in France [and] some group members from Arab and Asian origins are also engaged in religious associations” (Ulrike Schuerkens, “*Active Civic Participation of Immigrants in France*”, 2005).

(Dis)trust in political institutions and civic activism

The survey shows that almost one-third of the participants contacted a politician or government official in the last 12 months, which may reflect a certain level of trust in the proper functioning of the country’s political institutions by only 35% of the population. This finding correlates with the data obtained in a recent study by the OpinionWay Institute for the *Centre de Recherches Politiques de Sciences Po*, according to which almost two-thirds of the French

believe that “democracy is not working well”. The study points to “a general decline in the level of confidence in institutions, reaching the lowest point since the Yellow Vests” (Elsa Conesa, “*French distrust of politics back on the rise after Covid hiatus*”, Le Monde, 2023).

Likewise, the survey seems to reflect the longstanding French tradition of active civic engagement and participation in political protests, but also the rising levels of pessimism among the French and the instability in French politics due to the series of reforms advanced by the current administration. According to the survey, more than 45% of the participants have recently taken part in a lawful public demonstration, almost 40% signed a petition, about 25% displayed a campaign badge/sticker, and about 38% posted or shared anything about politics on social media. In the same vein, a recent study has shown that 74% of people say they are pessimistic about their future or that of their children (Ifop, “*L’état d’esprit des Français à la rentrée : optimisme et enjeux prioritaires*”, 2023).

Populism and policies concerning immigrants

According to the survey’s analysis: “SDO was indirectly related to realistic threat, but via populism; a stronger SDO predicted decreased populism, and decreased populism, in turn, predicted *increased* perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat.” This finding corresponds to the centrist political platforms of *Renaissance*, the current party in power led by President Macron, and its larger governing coalition, *Ensemble*, which includes the Democratic Movement (*Modem*), *Horizons*, and the environmentalist party *En Commun*. Their supporters would perceive populism as an extremist – far-right or far-left – mode of political engagement. As a result, this electorate may perceive the Republican centre and centre-right as being anti-populist at the same time that migration increasingly finds its way into the political platforms of these parties. For example, an immigration bill currently presented by Macron’s party aims, according to the French Minister of Interior, to “facilitate deportation, simplify dispute procedures” and to “establish a form of double penalty” against illegal migrants. The bill, however, includes a provision allowing some undocumented migrants to gain full legal status in France. The bill is likely to be approved in the Senate only with the support of the right-conservative party *Les Républicains* whose members are opposed to the proposed regularisation measures and are likely to pressure Macron to remove them from the bill (Clément Guillou and Alexandre Pedro, “*La droite et l’extrême droite invitent l’immigration à la table d’Emmanuel Macron*”, Le Monde, 2023; Pauline Graulle, “*Macron’s immigration bill blocked by row over regularisation of undocumented workers*”, MediaPart, 2023). Hence, the fact that “Increased perceptions of migrants being a threat to the country’s resources predicted greater support for extremist attitudes” correlates to the fact that centre-right parties now see this as a potential area to win elections. In other words, there is a general move on the right toward far-right political positions on migration.

6.5. Georgia

Georgia had 38.57% of participants reporting that they did not know their political attitudes. Thus, this variable was removed from the model, and these participants were kept, resulting in a sample of $n = 140$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
Mean age (SD)	n	%	n	%	n	%
22.62 (3.36)	62	44.28	78	55.71	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	106	75.71
Agnostic/Atheist	28	20.00
Other	6	4.29
Jewish	0	0.00
Muslim	0	0.00
Buddhist	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	25	17.86
No	99	70.71
Don't know	16	11.43

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Gender	17	68.00
Sexuality	11	44.00
Other	4	16.00
Colour or race	1	4.00
Age	1	4.00

Disability	1	4.00
Nationality	0	0.00
Religion	0	0.00
Language	0	0.00
Ethnic group	0	0.00

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	9	6.43	51	36.43	79	56.43	1	0.71
Sport or recreational organization	13	9.29	34	24.29	93	66.43	0	0.00
Art, music or educational organization	46	32.86	36	25.71	57	40.71	1	0.71
Labour union	5	3.57	18	12.86	117	83.57	0	0.00
Political party	4	2.86	14	10.00	122	87.14	0	0.00
Environmental organization	11	7.86	28	20.00	101	72.14	0	0.00
Professional association	13	9.29	19	13.57	108	77.14	0	0.00
Humanitarian or charitable organization	20	14.29	21	15.00	98	70.00	1	0.71
Consumer organization	13	9.29	15	10.71	109	77.86	3	2.14
Self-help group or mutual help group	23	16.43	15	10.71	101	72.14	1	0.71
Women's group	15	10.71	25	17.86	99	70.71	1	0.71
Other organization	9	6.43	13	9.29	98	70.00	20	14.29

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	19	13.57	110	78.57	11	7.86
Worked in a political party or action group	10	7.14	124	88.57	6	4.29
Worked in another ideological organization	11	7.86	122	87.14	7	5.00
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	23	16.43	109	77.86	8	5.71
Signed a petition	78	55.71	58	41.43	4	2.86
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	67	47.86	67	47.86	6	4.29
Boycotted certain products	58	41.43	74	52.86	8	5.71
Posted or shared anything about politics online	67	47.86	62	44.29	11	7.86

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was linked with increased perceptions of migrants as a threat to one's national ingroup regarding access to welfare, resources, and power. Additionally, perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants was also linked to increased perceived realistic threat from migrants. Greater feelings of anomie were also associated with perceiving migrants as a greater threat.

Direct predictors of extremism

In turn, perceiving that migrants were a greater threat to one's national ingroup was associated with greater endorsement of extremist attitudes. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing greater social alienation was also associated with more support for extremism.

Indirect predictors on extremism

The Georgian participant sample was the smallest across our national contexts (please note that the Georgian sample is the only sample which was not collected via Qualtrics, but instead through a local university); this may account for the lack of reported indirect effects, rather than their absence due to meaningful differences with other samples. Increased social dominance orientation had a significant indirect effect on increased support for extremist attitudes via increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat. The total indirect effect of social dominance orientation was not significant.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Endorsing more right-wing and populist attitudes were both separately associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia and Russian culture.

None of the variables of interest (i.e. social dominance orientation, online group identity, collective narcissism, anomie, individual and group relative deprivation, social cohesion, social alienation, populism, political trust, perceptions of migrants as realistic threats, support for extremist attitudes) reliably predicted attitudes towards either Ukrainian or Russian migrants.

Figure 7. Respecified model for Georgia.

Situating the findings within the Georgian context

This report aims to examine and interpret D.Rad survey findings for Georgia. It is important to note that radicalisation trends in Georgia need to be situated within the context of ultraconservative discourse coming from the Georgian Orthodox Church – the most trusted and popular institution in the country, with 91% of Georgians having a favourable attitude towards the Patriarch (IRI 2023, 28). It is even more noteworthy that as Georgia enters the parliamentary elections cycle scheduled for 2024, the current ruling party, Georgian Dream (GD), has also turned to radical, illiberal and ultraconservative discourse. Prime Minister Irakli Gharibashvili even attended the Conservative Political Action Conference (CPAC) in Hungary in May of 2023, leading to the Party of European Socialists (PES) condemning and even suspending GD’s observer member status (PES 2023).

With the Georgian Dream trying to secure power for the fourth time in 2024, political discourse will more likely become even more polarised with the dividing lines between “traditional values” and “liberalism”. These discourses are also very much embedded in Christianity as D.Rad survey also illustrates that more than 75% of the respondents identify as Christians. Orthodox Christianity serves as an important marker for national identity discourse in Georgia, especially those narratives that are ethnic-based and exclusionary.

The survey shows that despite the average age of the participants being only 22.62, the number of those who identify themselves as religious, and specifically as Christians, is relatively high – 75,71%. In comparison, some studies show that most youth in most European countries do not identify with any religion (Sherwood 2018). This suggests that Orthodox

Christianity is still very relevant and plays an important role in the radicalisation processes in Georgia. Yet, it also needs to be noted that while respondents identify as Christians, active membership in the Church is only 6.43%. This shows that social and mass media are more important factors in radicalisation than institutions and attendance of sermons.

The Survey also offers interesting information regarding trust in political parties, government and state institutions. More specifically, data shows that very few in the last 12 months contacted a politician or government official, worked in a political party or action group, worked in another ideological organisation, or displayed a campaign badge/sticker. This is in accordance with larger datasets that show that trust in political parties and state institutions in Georgia remains extremely low (IRI 2023). On the other hand, the D.Rad survey shows that those who have posted something about politics online, boycotted some product, or attended a lawful protest are higher (a bit below half of the respondents), suggesting that it is not so much that young people do not care about issues but it is that they do not feel represented or that state institutions/politicians care about them. And this divide between the people and politicians could push youth towards more radicalisation.

Regarding attitudes toward Russian immigrants, such an increase in right-wing political attitudes and for extreme measures (e.g., “We should break all cooperation with Russian academics, artists, and athletes.”) could be explained by the ontological insecurity of Georgians. To be more exact, as Georgia remains outside NATO and the EU security umbrella and is technically still at war with Russia since the latter keeps violating the cease-fire agreement and occupying Georgian territories, Georgians worry about the Russian influx. Georgia has been one of the main escape points for Russians feeling the war, with various estimates of more than 100,000 Russians currently in Georgia, having a population of barely 4 million (Reuters, 2023). The sudden influx of immigrants has led to inflation, a housing market crisis, and more widespread use of the Russian language than there was before. On top of it, the Georgian government has not introduced any restrictions or visa-related regulations, which has increased fear among many Georgians even further. The low trust in state institutions creates a feeling in the population that they have to take matters into their own hands, hence the increase of right-wing political attitudes in the survey.

The survey also showed that discrimination based on race, age, nationality or disability is not so common in Georgia, while gender and sexuality-based discrimination is more prevalent. This again could be explained because of the conservative discourse that is coming from some of the higher hierarchs of the Georgian Orthodox Church and government officials, and that is borderline homophobia and transphobia.

We can draw a few conclusions. First, Orthodox Christianity remains a dominant discourse in the country, serving as a critical feature of Georgia’s national identity. This, time and again, encourages radical groups to mobilise the masses and harness their popular power to resort to verbal or even physical violence, mainly against sexual minorities. Second, there is widespread alienation from the political class and the policy-making process within the population, including young people. The feelings of being excluded and disenfranchised may

push many young people into a radicalised corner. Third, Georgia is in a vulnerable geopolitical position, exposed to various global risks. The Russian invasion of Ukraine and the times of "Zeitenwende" have further exacerbated the severity or perception of the severity of these risks, such as the influx of Russian migrants, leading to feelings of ontological insecurity among the local population. Coupled with rising living costs and other socio-economic challenges, this may lead to radicalisation and further alienation from the normal political processes for disadvantaged groups in the population.

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6.6. Germany

Given that 15.67% of participants in Germany did not know their political attitudes, this variable was removed from the model, and all participants were kept, resulting in a sample of $n = 300$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
23.44 (3.61)	137	45.67	163	54.33	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	178	59.33
Agnostic/Atheist	47	15.67
Muslim	40	13.33
Other	29	9.67
Buddhist	6	2.00
Jewish	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	74	24.67
No	202	67.33
Don't know	24	8.00

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Religion	25	33.78
Colour or race	21	28.38
Nationality	14	18.92
Language	12	16.22
Ethnic group	12	16.22
Sexuality	10	13.51
Other	9	12.16
Gender	8	10.81
Age	6	8.11
Disability	4	5.41

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	84	28.00	98	32.67	118	39.33
Sport or recreational organization	141	47.00	75	25.00	84	28.00
Art, music or educational organization	70	23.33	76	25.33	154	51.33
Labour union	59	19.67	72	24.00	169	56.33
Political party	34	11.33	57	19.00	209	69.67
Environmental organization	48	16.00	58	19.33	194	64.67

Professional association	35	11.67	65	21.67	200	66.67
Humanitarian or charitable organization	55	18.33	60	20.00	185	61.67
Consumer organization	32	10.67	75	25.00	193	64.33
Self-help group or mutual help group	49	16.33	61	20.33	190	63.33
Women's group	40	13.33	58	19.33	202	67.33
Other organization	21	7.00	35	11.67	244	81.33

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	52	17.33	203	67.67	45	15.00
Worked in a political party or action group	29	9.67	235	78.33	36	12.00
Worked in another ideological organization	51	17.00	211	70.33	38	12.67
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	47	15.67	215	71.67	38	12.67
Signed a petition	129	43.00	129	43.00	42	14.00
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	87	29.00	176	58.67	37	12.33
Boycotted certain products	109	36.33	149	49.67	42	14.00
Posted or shared anything about politics online	94	31.33	168	56.00	38	12.67

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with perceiving migrants as a greater threat to one's national ingroup and its access to resources, welfare, and power. Perceiving that one's national ingroup was economically more deprived than migrants was also associated with perceiving migrants as a greater threat. Experiencing more anomie was linked with perceiving migrants as a greater threat. Although we did not predict a link between political ideology and perceiving migrants as a threat, populism was linked with perceiving migrants as less of a threat to one's national ingroup.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was also associated with increased endorsement of extremist attitudes. Perceiving one's ingroup to be superior to other social groups (collective narcissism) was associated with increased endorsement of extremist attitudes. Regarding political ideology, holding more populist beliefs was associated with greater extremism. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing more social alienation and lower social cohesion were associated with greater support for extremist attitudes.

Indirect predictors on extremism

A stronger online group identity indirectly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes via increased collective narcissism and increased social alienation. Oppositely, a stronger online group identity predicted increased feelings of social cohesion, and these subsequently predicted decreased support for extremist attitudes. Despite the two indirect effects predicting

both an increase (via greater collective narcissism and social alienation) and a decrease (via increased social cohesion) in extremist attitudes, the total indirect effect, which is the sum of all indirect relationships, was positive, meaning that online group identity was associated with greater support for extremist attitudes via three variables.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Endorsing more extremist attitudes and holding more political trust in the German system of governance were both linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia. In terms of attitudes towards Russian migrants, perceiving that one's economic situation was more deprived relative to migrants in general and holding more populist attitudes were both separately associated with a worsening attitude towards Russian migrants in the past year. In contrast, having more extremist attitudes was linked with an improved attitude towards Russian migrants in the past year.

Regarding attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants, perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants in general and holding more populist attitudes were both separately linked with worsening attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the past year.

Figure 8. Respecified model for Germany.

Situating the findings within the German context

This chapter contextualises the D.Rad Survey findings for Germany. It situates the findings in a country context where right-wing populists have entered the federal parliament and all

regional (federal states) parliaments in the late 2010s. The AfD – to name the most important right-wing populist force – entered the federal Parliament with 12,6 % of the national vote in 2017 and is the strongest party in the federal states of Thuringia and Saxony, where roughly one-quarter of the voters support it. It represents the anti-immigration and anti-establishment face of extremism in Germany and is home to a far-right faction called *Der Flügel* (“The Wing”). Although officially disbanded by court order in 2021, the faction is still highly influential and credited with controlling most of the party. The AfD and other far-right parties and groups have also led the protests against COVID-19 measures such as lockdowns, mandatory masks and vaccination programs, and since 2022, also against the country’s support for Ukraine. The AfD receives support from a vocal yet marginalised press segment of similar – far-right – political orientation, with minor to no support in mainstream media. In politics and media, centrist actors have formed a *cordon sanitaire* against the AfD and associated media outlets. Although usually associated with an East German male electorate aged 35-59, the AfD increasingly attracts also younger voters and first voters, in particular, if fearing job loss and economic deprivation (Arzheimer & Berning, 2019; Mitsch, 2020; Kroh and Wittenberg, 2016; Pesthy et al., 2021). It is in this context that we interpret survey findings as follows.

The survey shows a robust correlation between populism and extremism and found only a weak correlation between populism and threat perceptions around immigration. These findings seem contradictory since most European populist parties and voters tend to be right-wing, and the right-wing opposes immigration (Arzheimer & Bering, 2019; Hutter and Kriesi, 2022). While research has shown that AfD voters tend to cast their vote because of identifying with the AfD’s anti-immigration attitudes more than with its populism (Arzheimer & Bering, 2019), the survey results might indicate a so far politically uncaptured potential for extremism.

Relevant in this context is the finding that right-wing political attitudes predicted feeling more economically deprived compared to nationals but not compared to migrants. This makes sense from the perspective of inner-German “East-West” tensions: The AfD’s right-wing populism builds not only on anti-immigrant sentiment but also on East-versus-West resentment, the opposition between the former German Democratic Republic states (GDR or Eastern Germany) and the old federal states of West Germany (Federal Republic of Germany). Ever since the mid-2010s, it is the AfD that has sought to channel the discontent in the former GDR over the GDR-FRG reunification (Pesthy et al., 2021). Given that the AfD builds on resentment vis-a-vis western federal states, it is likely that AfD supporters in states corresponding to former East Germany compare themselves with West Germans (and consider that they are treated worse) and less with immigrants. The latter are grossly underrepresented in the East German federal states: 96% of immigrants live in West German federal states, and in the five East German federal states, immigrants (“naturalised” individuals holding German citizenship and residents without German citizenship) only make up around 5% of the population, as opposed to 28% in the West-German federal state of Hessen, for instance (Schmitz & Heinz, 2017).

The weak relationship between right-wing attitudes and economic deprivation vis-à-vis immigrants receives support from the finding that a right-wing political orientation is also

directly related to stronger perceptions that migrants pose a realistic threat to Germany; thus, right-wing supporters are critical of immigration but not due to felt economic deprivation. For instance, right-wing supporters might perceive immigration as threatening because they fear demographic change and a dilution of the ethnic majority, a standard far-right fear and argumentation going back to language and ideas used by the Nazis in the interwar period (Glathe and Varga, 2021).

Note that this perception of immigration does not seem to apply to the Ukrainians and Russians fleeing war and military conscription since 2022. Respondents tend to report improved attitudes to both Ukrainians and Russians, despite expectations in the media of the growing resentment vis-à-vis Ukrainians connected to the rising energy costs and inflation, which some expected that the public would blame Ukrainians for. Thus, media and politics predicted a “hot autumn” of AfD-driven protests against sanctions and associated increased energy bills in 2022, a “hot autumn” that did not materialise across the country. However, surveys indicated early on – around mid-2022– that the Eastern German population is less likely to support sanctions if they make it worse off. Protests peaked on October 3, 2022, when 100,000 protesters demonstrated against the sanctions in former GDR federal states (dpa-infocom, 2022; infratest dimap, 2022). Noteworthy, the more “populist” the D.Rad-survey respondents were, the worse their reported attitude to both Ukrainians and Russians. They do not make any political distinction between these national categories, which may be interpreted as some general anti-migration or anti-refugee sentiment unrelated to felt economic deprivation (see discussion above). Extremism’s impact on the attitudes towards Ukrainian and Russian refugees is quite puzzling. Reporting worsening attitudes towards Russia but improving attitudes towards refugees/migrants from Russia (most of whom flee now because they oppose the war and conscription) would be rather typical for the centrist and left-liberal segments of the German public. These segments, corresponding to social democratic, Christian-democratic, liberal, and green parties, support sanctions against Russia (infratest dimap, 2022) and possibly also welcome immigrants fleeing conscription in Russia.

While right-wing political attitudes predicted more perceived economic deprivation vis-a-vis nationals but not migrants and stronger threat perceptions vis-a-vis migrants, they did not predict stronger extremism. This indicates that publicly, right-wing discourse, as voiced by the AfD - and possibly adopted by respondents - rarely comes over as “extremist” (as captured by the “extremism”-measure used in the D.RAD-survey). This means that it rarely calls for the exclusion of other groups or for abolishing democracy. Instead, it claims that other groups – such as people practising Islam – are alien to Germany as they allegedly do not share the country’s culture and democratic values. They are also victimising Germans for allegedly not being able anymore to rule in their “own” country and calling for “better treatment” of their own supporters and ethnic group (Helstermann & Hoven, 2020; Lehmann and Zehnter, 2022).

Note that two measures of collective identification directly predict extremism, suggesting that extremism results from the strength of group identities and less from how respondents position themselves politically on the left-vs-right continuum: collective narcissism and social dominance orientation (SDO) are positively and directly related to extremism, for SDO with

higher values for men. It is also important to note that online group identity also indirectly affects extremism via alienation and populism; this might indicate how online group identity impacts extremism by strengthening feelings of alienation and support for populist positions and calls for strong leaders. In contrast, the social cohesion measure attenuates the effect of strong online group identity on extremism. These findings possibly reflect arguments and findings in media and research emphasising that far-right parties in Germany reach supporters almost exclusively online - including for organising violent demonstrations offline (Krüger, 2018; Schelter & Kunegis, 2017).

The strong effects of SDO and collective narcissism on extremism, in turn, also reflect that far-right media usually mobilises by conjuring up the image of a threatened yet deserving collective (German) self. This image builds on beliefs that the ethnic and titular majority needs to “lead” in its “own” country, as its culture is deemed superior to those of immigrants (Glathe and Varga, 2021; Helstermann & Hoven, 2020). However, the extremism scale that the D.Rad survey uses might measure extremism from both right and left depending on what respondents perceive as problematic about the majority. For instance, it could also capture the societal mainstream critique coming from within younger generations and rejecting the lifestyles and attitudes of older generations. The former hold the latter accountable for various developments, from tolerating racism to facilitating climate crisis (a critique and rejection that mainstream media often amplifies by deriding younger people as “pupils”, “dreamers” etc; Bergmann and Ossewaarde, 2020).

The tentative conclusion highlights that the D.Rad survey on Germany strongly linked extremism to collective identification measures and less to political attitudes. We interpret this as a possible manifestation of the “culture wars” that Germany is also undergoing, in which one side perceives the majority as “alienated”, ‘infiltrated’ by immigrants and facing national dissolution (that is, too far from a national-native utopia). The other side perceives the majority as still too ‘native’ and inherently superior, too close to a national-native dystopia. Furthermore, the strong impact of collective identification measures on extremism highlights the need to focus de-radicalisation efforts on encouraging people to question collective identification or to re-cast identities in ways that avoid hierarchies and feelings of superiority. In other words, such measures should show how belonging to groups or broader entities (subcultures, cultures, etc.) can work without equating belonging to superiority and exclusion (see Ghorashi, 2010).

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6.7. Hungary

In Hungary, 25.47% of participants reported not knowing their political attitudes. Thus, this variable was removed, all participants were kept, and the final sample was $n = 318$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
Mean age (SD)	n	%	n	%	n	%
24.59 (4.80)	154	48.43	164	51.57	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	225	70.75
Agnostic/Atheist	64	20.13
Other	25	7.86
Buddhist	3	0.94
Muslim	1	0.31
Jewish	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	48	15.09
No	212	66.67
Don't know	58	18.24

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Colour or race	10	20.83
Gender	9	18.75
Nationality	8	16.67
Sexuality	8	16.67
Disability	8	16.67
Other	7	14.58
Religion	5	10.42

Ethnic group	4	8.33
Language	3	6.25
Age	2	4.17

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	64	20.13	103	32.39	151	47.48
Sport or recreational organization	105	33.02	70	22.01	143	44.97
Art, music or educational organization	77	24.21	71	22.33	170	53.46
Labour union	47	14.78	68	21.38	203	63.84
Political party	38	11.95	66	20.75	214	67.30
Environmental organization	51	16.04	76	23.90	191	60.06
Professional association	52	16.35	70	22.01	196	61.64
Humanitarian or charitable organization	51	16.04	66	20.75	201	63.21
Consumer organization	60	18.87	63	19.81	195	61.32
Self-help group or mutual help group	48	15.09	65	20.44	205	64.47
Women's group	52	16.35	56	17.61	210	66.04
Other organization	22	6.92	47	14.78	249	78.30

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	53	16.67	211	66.35	54	16.98
Worked in a political party or action group	27	8.49	243	76.42	48	15.09
Worked in another ideological organization	32	10.06	241	75.79	45	14.15
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	39	12.26	235	73.90	44	13.84
Signed a petition	125	39.31	154	48.43	39	12.26
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	70	22.01	209	65.72	39	12.26
Boycotted certain products	46	14.47	228	71.70	44	13.84
Posted or shared anything about politics online	86	27.04	198	62.26	34	10.69

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs supporting inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with perceiving migrants as a greater threat to one's national ingroup and its access to resources, welfare, and power. Additionally, perceiving one's national ingroup to be more economically deprived relative to migrants was also linked to perceiving migrants as a greater threat.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was also associated with increased support for extremist attitudes. Perceiving migrants as a greater threat to one's national ingroup was, in turn, linked with greater support for extremist attitudes. Relatedly, perceiving one's ingroup as more economically deprived relative to migrants was also linked with greater support for extremist attitudes. Believing that one's ingroup was superior to other social groups (collective narcissism) was associated with support for extremist attitudes. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing more social alienation was associated with greater support for extremist attitudes.

Indirect predictors on extremism

Stronger social dominance orientation had indirect effects on increased support for extremist attitudes via increased collective narcissism and increased perceptions of realistic threat. Simultaneously, increased social dominance orientation indirectly affected decreased support for extremist attitudes via decreased populism, predicting decreased support. The total indirect effect was not significant.

A stronger online group identity had indirect effects on increased support for extremist attitudes via increased collective narcissism and increased social alienation. Similarly, the total indirect effect was statistically significant in a positive direction.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Feelings of social alienation and endorsement of extremist attitudes were both separately associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia and Russian culture. Greater feelings of anomie and perceptions of migrants in general as a threat to Hungary were linked with improved attitudes towards Russia. None of the variables of interest (i.e. social dominance orientation, online group identity, collective narcissism, anomie, individual and group relative deprivation, social cohesion, social alienation, populism, political trust, perceptions of migrants as realistic threats, support for extremist attitudes) reliably predicted attitudes towards Russian migrants.

In terms of Ukrainian migrants, holding more populist attitudes and perceiving migrants in general as a greater threat to Hungary were both separately linked with worsening attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the past twelve months. Conversely, holding more extremist attitudes was linking with improved opinions towards Ukrainian migrants in the past twelve months.

Figure 9. Respecified model for Hungary.

Situating the findings within the Hungarian context

The following summary aims to identify and contextualise radicalisation in Hungary. Our findings are based on the D.Rad Survey collected in Hungary with 318 participants. We interpret the survey findings in the following context. In the past 13 years, the right-wing Fidesz government has caused polarisation within the society, where already marginalised groups became further marginalised, and intersectionality has also become a growing issue in rural Hungary. While the Fidesz government has built up a conservative, populist, illiberal system in every aspect, there is a rising right-wing/far-right support in the country, which enabled them to win four consecutive terms with a supermajority in the Hungarian Parliament. Previous D.Rad reports have found that the government is a stakeholder in radicalisation as it prevents de-radicalisation measures, and by law-making and communication, they actively participate in radicalising the public. Their prevention of anti-polarisation or de-radicalisation measures in schools, for instance, is often explained by the government that they refuse to educate children with the “woke, Western liberal” propaganda. In a country where certain books and ideas are banned from education, television networks and now even bookstores, and where 80 per cent of the media landscape is de facto controlled by the government (Reporters without borders, 2023) it is almost impossible to carry out significant changes and de-radicalisation measures. Ever since the COVID-19 pandemic, the Hungarian government has been operating with special powers, extending the rule-by-decree many times based on the alleged emergency situation caused by the war in Ukraine. In this political and law-making climate, the opposition has no added value to work in the Hungarian Parliament, and the Fidesz government, with a supermajority, controls the jurisdiction.

The survey shows that the Hungarian society is polarised on many levels, reinforcing the findings of previous D.Rad reports. One of the most intriguing findings of this study pertains to the subject of discrimination. Previous D.Rad reports on Hungary have often linked discrimination to politically incited discrimination and social inclusion against marginalised groups. However, the survey results revealed that merely 15.09% of the participants perceived themselves as belonging to a discriminated group in Hungary. An additional 18.24% responded uncertainly, indicating "Don't know" to the same query. This is a contradictory finding with the current marginalising narrative of the Hungarian government that mainly focuses on supporting Hungarian families with good financial backgrounds while secluding "the Others" from any support and continuing to curb their rights (Amnesty International, 2022).

When respondents were questioned about the characteristics of their perceived discriminated social group, 20.83% attributed their discrimination to factors related to colour and race. Gender came next with 18.75%, while nationality, sexuality, and disability received similar scores at 16.67%. Importantly, participants were allowed to select multiple grounds for discrimination, which opens avenues for further investigation into intersectionality.

Although the figure of 20.83% reporting discrimination based on colour and race might seem paradoxical in a predominantly homogenous society like Hungary, except for a significant Roma minority (Dessewffy, Nagy 2021), a thorough analysis of the raw data and qualitative responses unravelled the underlying reasons.

Roughly half of those who responded "Yes" to the question of whether they feel discriminated against in Hungary seemed to be part of a minority group, including women, people with Roma ethnicity or Ukrainian and Romanian nationals. Out of those who described their self-identity or characteristics as LGBTQ, only one answered "No" to discrimination. At the same time, 8 responded that they feel discriminated against based on their sexuality and 8 mentioned being discriminated against based on their disability. Those participants who feel discriminated against in their language live close to the Hungarian border. Participants who reported being a member of at least one group that is discriminated against perceived less social cohesion in their neighbourhood and community than participants who were not members of any discriminated groups. We can conclude that, in general, discriminated people feel more excluded from society.

Surprisingly, the other half (over 50 per cent) of the participants who claimed discrimination based on race or skin colour were white, Christian, heterosexual males with conservative values. This discovery stood out as an anomaly in the discrimination section of the survey. The following observation can explain it. These individuals may have chosen to answer affirmatively to the discrimination question and selected colour and race as the grounds for their perceived discrimination, possibly due to their sense of exclusion from the prevailing liberal discourse, which highlights the experiences of other marginalised groups.

In Hungary, the "Western liberal agenda" has been a prioritised hate-inciting narrative by the governing Fidesz party. Their right-wing characteristics include heightened EU scepticism,

anti-LGBTQ sentiments, general xenophobia and strong nationalism. When focusing on the participants who answered positively to being discriminated against on the grounds of colour and race, we found that further, their answers were in line with the Fidesz narrative; for example, most of them responded negatively on whether they think Russia has caused the war in Ukraine.

This finding can be linked to another attribute in the survey. Contrary to expectations, increased collective narcissism did not predict increased perceptions of migrants as realistic threats. Instead, increased collective narcissism predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. For example, Fromm (1964/2010) understood narcissism as self-admiration and over-evaluation of one's subjective perspective, also marked by a "blindness" to objective reality. From narcissism to collective narcissism, the interpretation (Millon, 2006) was rewritten to refer to group-related beliefs rather than the individual (e.g., "I insist upon getting the respect that is due to me" was transformed to "I insist upon my group getting the respect that is due to it"; Golec de Zavala et al., 2009). People who score high on the Collective Narcissism Scale believe that others do not sufficiently recognise the importance of their in-group and that their in-group deserves special treatment (Forgas, Lantos 2020).

The other interesting finding includes Online Group Identity and Social Dominance Orientation (SDO). A higher social dominance orientation (SDO) predicted increased collective narcissism, decreased anomie, and decreased populism. Higher SDO directly predicted stronger perceptions that migrants pose a realistic threat to Hungary and its resources, rather than SDO being indirectly related to realistic threat through other variables such as collective narcissism, anomie, or perceived individual or group relative deprivation (individual relative deprivation and group relative deprivation). Importantly, higher SDO directly predicted greater support for extremist attitudes. The effect of SDO on extremist attitudes was mediated by collective narcissism, perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat, and populism. An increased SDO predicted decreased populism and decreased populism predicted decreased support for extremist attitudes. Thus, increased SDO indirectly predicted decreased support for extremist attitudes via populism. A stronger online group identity predicted increased collective narcissism, increased feelings of social cohesion in one's neighbourhood and community, and increased social alienation. Increased social alienation is a strong narrative in Hungary, as it is the stronger perceptions that migrants pose a realistic threat to the nation and its resources, which is linked to higher SDO. Participants who did not belong to any discriminated groups showed a higher SDO than people who reported belonging to or more discriminated groups. Also, participants who belonged to one or more groups that were discriminated against had a stronger online identity (mainly Reddit and Facebook) than participants who did not belong to any discriminated groups.

The qualitative data demonstrates the current Injustice-Grievance-Alienation-Polarisation (I-GAP) index in Hungary. To the question asking participants to "Name the most consequential event of extreme-right violence that took place in Hungary in the past twenty years", we were able to measure how each participant responded among those who also felt discriminated. The most mentioned events were in the following topics: violent demonstrations and police

brutality taking place in Budapest in 2006 (12), the Roma killings, the rising visibility and threat of the neo-Nazi group called the Hungarian Guards before 2010 (15), general anti-Orbán remarks (6), anti-LGBTQ laws (6) and migration (1). Other than the topics mentioned above, most participants answered with remarks that enable us to conclude that the country has a general political apathy. While there were many indifferent remarks for political questions, we saw a large portion of the participants who responded positively to taking political actions: 39.31 per cent of participants said that they had signed a petition, 22.01 per cent indicated that they had taken part in a lawful demonstration and 27.04 per cent responded that they have posted or shared anything about politics online in the last 12 months.

The survey on Hungary reinforces the previous D.Rad reports and their findings. In conclusion, the data reveals a deeply polarised society, with the right-wing Fidesz government's policies exacerbating marginalisation. Surprisingly, discrimination is not solely limited to traditionally marginalised groups, as some conservative, white, Christian males also perceive discrimination, potentially due to their sense of exclusion from the prevailing liberal discourse. Collective narcissism predicts extremist attitudes, while social dominance orientation relates to perceptions of migrants as threats. Increased support for populism and extremist ideas correlated with higher collective narcissism scores. The findings highlight Hungary's I-GAP index and citizen engagement in political actions. Addressing media control and discrimination and fostering dialogue are crucial for promoting inclusivity and countering radicalisation in Hungary.

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6.8. Israel

Only 3.07% of participants in Israel did not know their political attitudes. These participants were removed, the variable retained, and the final sample was $n = 315$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
24.40 (4.95)	155	47.69	169	52.00	1	0.31

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Jewish	259	79.69
Christian	23	7.08
Muslim	21	6.46
Agnostic/Atheist	18	5.54
Other	3	0.92
Bahá'í	1	0.31
Buddhist	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	88	27.08
No	196	60.31
Don't know	41	12.62

**Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against
On what grounds is your group discriminated against?**

	n	%
Religion	46	52.27
Gender	15	17.05
Nationality	13	14.77
Language	13	14.77
Ethnic group	12	13.64

Colour or race	10	11.36
Disability	9	10.23
Other	7	7.95
Age	6	6.82
Sexuality	5	5.68

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	115	35.38	103	31.69	107	32.92
Sport or recreational organization	108	33.23	116	35.69	101	31.08
Art, music or educational organization	85	26.15	116	35.69	124	38.15
Labour union	84	25.85	120	36.92	121	37.23
Political party	43	13.23	149	45.85	133	40.92
Environmental organization	59	18.15	136	41.85	130	40.00
Professional association	74	22.77	123	37.85	128	39.38
Humanitarian or charitable organization	66	20.31	125	38.46	134	41.23
Consumer organization	63	19.38	116	35.69	146	44.92
Self-help group or mutual help group	67	20.62	134	41.23	124	38.15
Women's group	65	20.00	124	38.15	136	41.85
Other organization	46	14.15	108	33.23	171	52.62

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	73	22.46	232	71.38	20	6.15
Worked in a political party or action group	51	15.69	261	80.31	13	4.00
Worked in another ideological organization	48	14.77	253	77.85	24	7.38
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	75	23.08	232	71.38	18	5.54
Signed a petition	129	39.69	173	53.23	23	7.08
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	76	23.38	228	70.15	21	6.46
Boycotted certain products	122	37.54	180	55.38	23	7.08
Posted or shared anything about politics online	114	35.08	200	61.54	11	3.38

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with greater perceptions of threat to one's national ingroup from migrants. Feelings of anomie were also associated with greater perceived threat. Although we did not have predictions about vulnerability and perceptions of realistic threat, experiencing social alienation was linked with lower perceptions of threat from migrants.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was also linked directly with increased support for extremist attitudes. A stronger online group identity was also directly associated with greater support for extremist attitudes. Perceiving that one's ingroup was superior to other social groups was linked with greater support for extremism. Additionally, perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants was also linked with greater support for extremism. Regarding political ideology, populism was associated with greater support for extremism. In terms of vulnerability, feeling more socially alienated was linked with increased endorsement of extremism.

Indirect predictors on extremism

Increased social dominance orientation had an indirect effect on increased support for extremist attitudes via increased group relative deprivation. However, it also indirectly affected lower support for extremism via decreased populism. The total indirect effect of social dominance orientation was not significant.

A stronger online group identity had indirect effects on increased support for extremist attitudes via increased social alienation, increased populism, and increased collective narcissism. The total indirect effect was not statistically significant.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Holding stronger beliefs about group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) and endorsing more extremist attitudes were both separately associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Additionally, perceiving migrants in general as a threat to Israel and its resources was linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Conversely, experiencing greater anomie was associated with more positive attitudes towards Russia.

Perceiving that one's individual economic situation was more deprived relative to migrants in general and that migrants are a threat to Israel and its resources were both separately associated with worsened attitudes towards Russian and Ukrainian migrants. Additionally, holding more populist beliefs was linked with worsened attitudes towards Russian migrants in the past twelve months.

Figure 10. Respecified model for Israel.

Situating the findings within the Israeli context

This report seeks to explain the survey results through the socio-political complexity of Israeli society. Several processes have been taking place in recent years, which have raised significant concerns about the relationship between the democratic regime and the citizens. After a short introduction (1), the first part (2.1) deals with the processes that undermined the trust between the citizens and the government while referring to the activity of civil society and the recent protests against the current government. In the case of Israel, political instability and multiple election systems led to deep polarisation between political camps and different social groups.

The second part (2.2) deals with the various practices used by the various political forces, such as online personalisation and populism, as tactics of separation between "us" and "them" and their possible effect on extremist tendencies. As found in the survey, a more robust online group identity predicted greater collective narcissism, stronger feelings of social cohesion in one's neighbourhood and community, stronger feelings of social alienation, and decreased populism. This part of the report includes attention to the role of the online space and political processes. It shows that the leaders' personalities have become central in the eyes of the Israeli voting public while politicians are expressing extreme positions online. As such, social networks also significantly influence trends of radicalisation. Therefore, the survey results might reflect the tendency to "normalise" discriminatory posts, thus creating feelings of discrimination and inequality in addition to the existing polarisation.

Section 2.3 offers some background to the dominance of women shown in the results. The current fear of reducing women's rights, which is reflected ambiguously, goes in parallel to the

fact that they constitute a majority in Israeli society (51%). It forms the feeling of dominance among women, who respond through civil society to what they perceive as an attempt to reduce their rights and the female space in light of the collaboration of far-right parties in the coalition. This is also part of a process of regression that has been occurring since 2015 concerning gender equality in society.

The following section (2.4) refers to the Russian invasion of Ukraine and its outcomes, in context to the vast Jewish population still living there, others who immigrated to Israel during the war, and the Russian-Ukrain Jewish population who came to Israel in the 90s. Contrary to expectations, greater collective narcissism did not predict greater perceptions of migrants as realistic threats. Instead, increased collective narcissism directly predicted more significant support for extremist attitudes without having to pass through perceptions of migrants as threats. Increased feelings of social alienation predicted a *decreased* perception of migrants being a realistic threat but *increased* support for extremist attitudes.

Section 2.5 attends to the fact that Political attitudes had no relationship (either direct or indirect) to support extremist attitudes. It might suggest that societal polarisation holds grave importance for the public and is not necessarily dependent on political affiliation. We relate it to the cost of living and the economic situation following the Corona crisis, raising the tendency towards extreme positions unaffected by political partisanship. The division of the geographic periphery is reflected in the absence of voting in areas with low socio-economic classification, which continues a trend of mistrust in the political system over the years. In addition, it shows that right-wing representation is more common in peri-urban environments, which some consider part of the lower socio-economic clusters.

Finally, section 3 offers concluding remarks, emphasising that the connection between online activity and extremism can be related to the rise of online political personalisation and progressing populist practices, leading to further radicalisation.

Introduction

The proportion of those who believe that 'Israeli democracy is in grave danger' is just over half, according to the Israel Democracy Institute 2022 survey. It is a factor in increased domestic polarisation. Over a third of the interviewees (35.5%) reported having experienced sharp disagreements with family members or co-workers regarding the latest legislative changes and the 'judicial overhaul' protests. It turns out that the differences of opinion permeate the daily lives of Israel's citizens to a significant extent. This experience is not the property of only one political camp among the Jewish majority; the political left, centre, and right share it. The IDI survey has also reflected concerns regarding translating this polarising conflict into a violent clash between citizens. Accordingly, only a minority predicts a high probability of a violent civil war in the future (Jews 39.5%, Arabs 45%). Segmentation by political camps (Jews) shows that fear is the highest on the left and the lowest on the right (Herman and Anavi, 2023).

This report offers an explanatory analysis of D.Rad survey results. The empirical information obtained from the study was cross-referenced with theories and other empirical findings to

draw appropriate insights in light of the latest developments in Israeli society. The materials used for this analysis include academic studies on Israeli society, surveys conducted by research institutes and government institutions on socio-economic, gender and relations between the government and citizens, and reports from reliable media.

The following sections will provide possible explanations for the survey findings, considering the social structure, cultural texture and political conflicts that characterise Israeli society in recent years. Section 2.1 pays particular attention to political participation issues and the democratic framework. Section 2.2 examines the issue of extremism through practices of populism and online personalisation, taking into account the effect of social media on both. Section 2.3 discusses some reflections regarding the results showing gender-based differences between the participants' political agendas.

Section 2.4 concerns the answers given in the survey regarding the Russian invasion of Ukraine while examining the local context of immigration. Section 2.5 briefly explains the connection between voting patterns and socio-economic clusters in Israeli society, which might indicate political tendencies. The final section (3) will present a summary of the explanatory analysis of the survey and conclusive remarks.

Explanatory analysis

Political participation and the democratic discourse

According to our survey, only 13% of the participants identified themselves as "active members" of a political party, and 45.85% were inactive. 39.69% of the participants said they had signed a petition, while 23.38% participated in a public protest. 35.08% have posted a publication that involves political content. This data can be explained by civic society tendencies, characterised by widespread involvement in everyday life.

The "cost of living" national protest of 2011 is considered a landmark in the political history of Israeli society. It has changed the population's political involvement since it has increased the activity of civil society and reflected the decrease in trust in political entities. It has expressed a crisis of representation of the modern political system against the failure of the postmodern political culture to communicate inequality in the socio-economic field (Ram and Filc, 2017). The protest has shown that hundreds of thousands sought representation outside the political system. It illustrated that the parties lost their central role as mediators between the citizens and the state, leaving the political arena open to competition (Ibid, 75-78).

The lack of trust was connected to the political protests in 2020, named "the Balfour demonstrations" against the prime Minister's indictment on three criminal charges (Gorali, 2020). The 2022 elections, fifth in number since 2019, established a full-right-wing coalition that holds the majority of the public's votes. The expectation was that Israeli society would drift away from the intense political polarisation it has been experiencing for quite a while. However, the coalition includes the electorates of three extremist parties, holding an ethno-religious, nationalist, far-right agenda, endangering the hopes for social solidarity: "Jewish Power" party (Otzma Yehudit) led by the Minister of national security, Itamar Ben Gvir; Religious Zionist party (Ha'Zionot Ha'Datit) led by the Minister of Treasury Betzalel Smotrich; and "Noam" party,

characterised as 'messianic', anti-LGBTQ+ communities, and Ultra-ethnocentric led by Knesset Member Avi Maoz (Vertman and Elran, 2022; see also: D3.2).

Political stability is questionable, given the social influences of the extreme-religious parties on the public atmosphere. Decisions on sensitive issues such as security, minority rights and equality seriously affect existing conflicts, such as the Israeli-Palestinian shareholder on holy places in Jerusalem and issues in the West Bank. The 2022 election results and voting rates can explain the need for more trust in political parties. It reflects on the voices that were **not** heard and did not come into representation, such as the liberal party of "Meretz", which failed to pass the electorate threshold for the first time in its history (Ben Chaim and Keynan, 2022). Meretz's agenda is to advance human rights, equality, and conflict solutions through peace.

The fact that the rate of electorates was low compared to earlier years and held 70.6% out of eligible votes shows the weakness of leftist parties, which were considered the parliamentary response to the extremist ones from the right wing. In the Arab sector, the voting rate was only 53.2%. In parallel to extreme parties, the Ultra-orthodox parties have also increased their number of electorates. Still, the far-right religious Zionist parties, which have joined forces into one joint list, increased their power by more than 10%. (Vertman and Elran, 2022, 2). Meretz had the chance to follow the same path of a shared list but was rejected by the Labour Party (Azoulay, 2023).

Vertman and Elran (2022) explain the increased power of the far right as caused by the diffusion of the religious Zionist mainstream parties and other sectorial parties over the years. The leftist bloc of parties has decreased its power to 38.3% compared to the right-wing bloc led by Benjamin Netanyahu, with 49.6% of the party electorates. The two mentioned that the complex of far-right religious parties could result in a critical main challenge, emphasised in two fields. Firstly, the relations between Jews and Arabs inside the state also show benefits to the West Bank settlers rather than cultivating ties with the Palestinians. The second concerns the USA officials and the American-Jewish community's reactions to these potentials, seeing radical agendas as a significant part of the Israeli government coalition. It can affect Israel's identity as both Jewish and democratic (Ibid, p. 3).

The last IDI annual report shows that public trust in state institutions decreased, while parliament and the political parties suffered the lowest trust rate of 10% (Israeli Democracy Index, 2022, 5). On the topic of "The strongest tension in Israeli society today", 34% showed that they see it coming from the far-right threat, while 61% said it is the tension between Jews and Arabs (Ibid, 6). When asked about the state and religion ratio, 51% of the seculars supported the dominancy of the democratic component, while 58.5% of the conservative religious participants supported the Jewish one (Ibid, 8). Compared to the global index that measures democratic characteristics, Israel is high in political participation (95-100 per cent from the OECD average), and most parameters have remained stable (Ibid, 11).

At the beginning of 2023, hundreds of thousands from the Israeli public joined the growing weekly mass protests, which originated at the Kaplan junction in the centre of Tel Aviv and spread across 150 locations in the country. The Israelis participating in the demonstrations come from different sectors, political parties and classes. Their main claim is that democracy

is at risk due to the "judicial overhaul", meaning the coalition's attempts to pass judicial laws aim to weaken the judicial system, enabling the government more power. Dozens of civic and private organisations joined forces following this primary claim: "*If the reform gets underway, there is only one authority left: the government [...] this is how Israel will change the form of the regime from democracy to dictatorship.*"(Restart-Israel, 2023). The continued protests demand to stop the legislation as it shatters the traditional construction of Israel as a democracy.

Populism, personalisation, and extremism

As a fundamental premise, the dominance of the Jewish majority in Israel was well reflected in the identity of our survey participants. 79.69% were identified as Jews (by religion), while only 13% were Christians and Muslims. According to our survey results, an online group identity significantly indirectly affected extremist attitudes via collective narcissism, social alienation and populism. However, as with SDO, the total indirect effect was not significant. As with SDO, the full impact and direct effects were significant. A more robust online group identity predicted increased collective narcissism, increased feelings of societal alienation, and populism. In turn, an increase in these variables predicted a rise in support for extremist attitudes. SDO had a significant indirect effect on extremist attitudes via populism and group relative deprivation, although the combined indirect effects were insignificant. The total effect (i.e., the sum of indirect and direct effects) was significant: greater SDO predicted more substantial support for extremist attitudes. However, the relationship seems mainly driven by the immediate effect, independent of the influence through other variables.

During the years of the Netanyahu regime, the 'exclusionary' path has been central in fulfilling polarised politics, which extremists have adopted (Hoffstein, 2023). The rise of populist practices can explain it. Populism sees "the people" as the source of good and truth. Populist movements tend to explain and understand society as priorly polarised, divided into 'them' and 'us'. 'They' are mainly "the elites", seen as disconnected from "the people". The anti-elitism approach often goes hand in hand with xenophobia, nationalism and other exclusive paths. The democratic concept of the populist movements emphasises that democracy is, first and foremost, people's sovereignty by governing themselves (Mudde, 2017). The division of "us" (the people) and "them" (the others) is leaning either on an inclusive approach or an exclusive one through three dimensions: symbolic, material, and political. Exclusionary populism symbolises "them" as those who are not part of the people and should be cast out from material rights by political delegitimation (Filc, 2006).

In Israel, political populism divides Jews and Arabs, Israelis and Palestinians, Right and Left, religious and seculars, women and men, and more. What assists it is that a large portion of the political activity has been transferred to the online arena, amplifying the ability to reach vast crowds exposed to intense content (Zamir and Rahat, 2019). The online populist practice undermines liberal values such as tolerance, affecting democracies globally (ISOC-IL, 2020, pp. 20-21). In 2014, the Knesset passed a law in which the blocking percentage was increased from 2% to 3.25% to prevent extremist parties from taking control and entering the parliament. It created the opposite effect of the growth of extremism since it did not prevent the global rise of populism and its influence on radicalisation (Retig-Gour, 2022).

Our survey showed that online group identity significantly indirectly affected extremist attitudes via collective narcissism, social alienation and populism. However, as with SDO, the total indirect effect was not significant. As with SDO, the total effect and direct effects were significant. A stronger online group identity predicted stronger support for extremist attitudes. However, the relationship is mainly driven by the direct effect (70% of the total effect) and not by the indirect influence of online group identity on other variables (30% of the total effect). Political attitudes had no relationship (either direct or indirect) to support for extremist attitudes.

Patterns of political personalisation can also be pinpointed as a process in which the political weight of the only player, such as the party leader, rises. At the same time, the importance of the group goes down (Zamir and Rahat, 2019, p. 7). A study of online political habits showed that Israeli surfers' consumption of social networks presents a preference to follow the politicians' Facebook pages and Twitter accounts, especially of their leaders and parties. Israel is a case-in-point of extreme personalisation compared to other countries (Ibid 8-9). The relationship between the parties and the citizens experiencing a weakening manifests itself in a decrease in loyalty to parties, membership in parties, trust in the parties and even in the participation rates in the elections. This space is filled with Politicians as individuals and mainly, but not only, the parties' leaders. It is part of the phenomena of the "individualisation" of politics (Ibid, 13-14). Personalisation progresses populist leaders whose discourse may weaken the gatekeepers of democracy (Ibid, 15-16). Social media and digital online networks encourage personalisation, providing opportunities for politicians to stand out more than their parties due to direct interaction with civilians (Ibid, 23).

An additional aspect of online development is the ability to spread "fake news" and propagate populism and other agendas more easily and quickly, thus enabling the spread of extremist views. Fake news can bring the sinking of the concept of truth, creating a crisis of decreased trust in democratic institutions (Karniel and Lavie-Dinor, 2022). Fake news enables doubts and facts, leaning on a blurring line between legal-scientific and spiritual-subjective truth. Alternative facts are created, supporting "conspiracy" theories (e.g., COVID-19) (Ibid, 116-118, 120-123). Social networks enhance the perception of trust as a question of faith, asking those who represent "my truth" (124-126).

Our survey also explained 38.60% of the variability in extremism scores (i.e., 38.60% of the variability in participants' extremist attitudes can be explained by our model). SDO had a significant indirect effect on extremist attitudes via populism and group relative deprivation, although the combined indirect effects were insignificant. Beyond any indirect effects, greater SDO directly affected more significant support for extremist attitudes. The total impact (i.e., the sum of indirect and direct effects) was significant: greater SDO predicted stronger support for extremist attitudes.

The fact that only 35% of the respondents to our survey said they had an affiliation to a religious organisation like a church, mosque or synagogue means that most religious discriminated participants had no affiliation to such institution and that the impression of inequality was not necessarily attached to a specific practice. According to the above, the perception of Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) was higher among those who did not come

from discriminated groups. Participants who identified as discriminated against had stronger online identities than those who were not, alongside lower collective narcissism. Those who do not belong to a discriminated-against group showed higher individual relative deprivation than those who felt discriminated.

The above can be explained by the contemporary political atmosphere. As recently noted by USA President Joe Biden: *"Netanyahu has some of the most extreme government members I have ever seen, and I go back in time to Golda Meir. Smotrich and Ben Gvir are part of the problem in the West Bank."* (cited in Bar, 2023). In the Arab public, the large majority opposes Minister Smotrich's statement that "There are no Palestinian people". The Jewish public is divided on this matter while on the left, the majority contends; in the centre, slightly more than half; on the right, only a tiny minority disagrees with the Minister's statement (Herman and Anavi, 2023).

Gender

Our survey reflected that women reported a stronger social dominance orientation (SDO) compared to men, as 39.31% expressed it against 36.59% among men. This is particularly interesting for Israel as research has consistently found that men typically score higher on SDO across cultures than women. Women also expressed stronger online identity (17.41%) than men (14.63%). Women had greater political trust (47.25%) than men (45.35%).

This can be explained by the simple fact that Women make up 51% of the total population in Israel compared to 49% of men (Carmel, 2023). and still. Inequality characterises the socio-gender relations in Israeli society. According to Chazan (2018), Israel has always been a gendered society. Gender gaps have taken on different forms over time. "With all the considerable progress gained by women in education, health, the workplace, and recently even in the political realm, women, however, empowered, still do not enjoy substantial power." (Chazan, 2018, 141).

Since 2015, Israeli politics and society have experienced regression in equality under the leadership of the right-wing parties: "ushered in a right-wing government that is bent on changing the rules of the game by defying Israel's commitment not only to coexistence with its neighbours, but also to basic notions of religious pluralism, social equity, and solidarity. It has promoted a monolithic, ethnocentric interpretation of the country's identity and aspirations, fueling social divisions and exacerbating internal friction. [...] This toxic mixture of intolerance, authoritarianism, and populism emanating from the top" affects gender relations (e.g., excluding women from public events). (Chazan, 2018, 149).

The feminist struggle in Israel has re-awakened in the past year; some would say it is due to a lack of representation. According to the Knesset research division, in the 2022 elections, only 29 female Knesset members were elected, which is 24% of all elected Knesset members. The number of elected representatives has remained unchanged since 2015 (Avgar, 2022). Various feminist organisations have joined the anti-judicial overhaul protests, captured as an authoritarian coup that will harm women's rights by narrowing the judicial system's authority. The judicial overhaul reflects it. Among the Jewish population, women reported higher rates of sharp disagreements in their immediate environment than men (respectively 45% vs. 33%).

Among the voters of the Arab parties, only a minority experienced such differences of opinion (Herman and Anavi, 2023).

A central initiative presents a weekly march of the women in red inspired by "The Handmaid's Tale" TV show, based on Margaret Atwood's novel. The affiliation is based on the idea that under the leadership of extremists, the USA is becoming an extreme and class-based halachic state where women lose their achievements (Yael, 2023). Atwood herself wrote on her Twitter account how astonishing and overwhelming the protests are (Walla, 2023). The March is organised by the "Building an Alternative" foundation, which brings together women from all sectors: secular, religious, traditional, Haredi, Arab, Muslim, Christian, Druze, and Jewish. Its main claim is that gender equality is going through an opposite process of declining women's rights. The foundation sees it as a fight that includes the women of the State of Israel 2023, which "grew up free, with almost equal rights, served in the army, developed professionally, sat in the Knesset, served, headed a party and even had a prime minister." (Yael, 2023)

Immigration

Our survey examined reflections regarding the Russia-Ukraine war. Participants reported that their attitudes towards Russian migrants in the last 12 months had not changed significantly. However, participants reported their attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the previous 12 months to have improved slightly. Increased SDO, individual relative deprivation, and support for extremist attitudes significantly predicted worsened attitudes against Russia (e.g., "We should break all cooperation with Russian academics, artists, and athletes."). According to the survey, contrary to expectations, greater collective narcissism did not predict greater perceptions of migrants as realistic threats. Instead, increased collective narcissism directly predicted more significant support for extremist attitudes without having to pass through perceptions of migrants as threats. Increased feelings of social alienation predicted a *decreased* perception of migrants being a realistic threat but *increased* support for extremist attitudes.

Immigration from the former Soviet Union should be considered under context. In Ukraine and Russia, Jewish communities handle ties with families and friends who immigrated to Israel after the fall of the Soviet Union at the beginning of the '90s. According to Shumsky (2001), hundreds of thousands of immigrants from Russian communities had to adjust to Israeli culture. They were seen as "others" many times until they developed, among others, political strength. The Jewish ethnicity was less critical than the ability to connect to the Israeli Zionist nationality and be part of its secular formation.

The Russia-Ukraine war has raised the number of immigrants to Israel, which holds a tight immigration policy that benefits Jews. According to the Knesset research division, immigration to Israel in 2022 from Ukraine and Russia was greatly affected by the war between the two countries. The Russian invasion resulted in an extraordinary wave of migration of Ukrainian citizens, especially women and children, who fled to other countries in Europe and different regions. The war in Ukraine led to a significant increase in the number of people interested in immigrating to Israel from Ukraine and Russia, in the number of actual immigrants, and in the number of citizens who sought to change their status in Israel to immigrants (Eliyahu, 2022).

The only criterion for checking eligibility for immigration is full compliance with the Law of Return. According to the "Law of Return, 1950": "A Jew is one who was born to a Jewish mother or who converted and is not a member of another religion" (Eliyahu, 2022, 3). Before and during the actual fighting (January-October 2022), 38,047 requests for immigration were received in Russia, Ukraine and Belarus. This number is more than twice the number of applications received in 2021. From March to October 2022, about 44,000 immigrants from Russia, Ukraine and Belarus immigrated to Israel - 29,133 from Russia, 13,570 from Ukraine and 1,580 from Belarus. The Ministry of Welfare assisted 12,877 citizens of Ukraine who were not entitled to immigrate to Israel during the war (Ibid, 6-8).

Urban/ Peri-urban

Radicalisation does not necessarily reflect a political preference since some perpetrators and extremists do not believe in political parties (see D3.2). However, voter trends in Israel differentiate between the low-class population, who usually live in peripheral areas, and the high classes, who typically vote for centre leftist parties. The Central Bureau of Statistics (CBOS) uses the socio-economic rate to produce data that can be of value to social development. The rate is determined by several measures, in which each municipality is ranked averagely by clusters, in which "1"- is the lowest, and "10" is the highest (Agmon, 2016)

The elections of 2019, for example, showed that the bigger parties get the majority of the votes, as the highest support rate for the Likud party was also recorded in the last elections in localities and regions with a socio-economic rating of 6-4. The highest support rate for the Blue-White party was also recorded, this time in localities and areas with a rating of 8-10 (Hoffman-Dishon, 2019). The general votes for right-wing parties were among clusters 4-7, while some Jewish-zionists were also in clusters 8-10.

The 2022 elections showed a similar notion, in which voting tendencies in Israel are attached to socio-economic class divisions, which are accumulated in the living area. Within the middle class (clusters 4-7), it was found that every third voter supports the right-wing "Likud" party, almost double that of the second largest centre party, "Yesh Atid". In addition, most religious Zionist parties come from the same clusters, as the party of Smotrich and Ben Gvir are third in size with the support of 13.5% of the votes. Among areas which compare clusters 1-3, the vote rate is generally the lowest. The clusters contain religious and Arab municipalities, in which most of the votes were given to sectorial parties, and only 10% voted for the Likud party.

The political processes in Israeli society, directly and indirectly, reflect the survey results, although no direct influence of the participants' political or ideological positions was found. From the analysis of the voter turnout according to clusters, the wealthy localities vote more than the average turnout. There is a correlation between the economic cluster of the locality and the decrease in the turnout, except in the lower group, where the turnout is 1% higher than the average. At the same time, only 112,000 votes came from Cluster 1, against almost 404,000 from Cluster 9 (Racover and Kaspin, 2022). If anything, even if it can be said that radicalisation might derive from peri-urban areas, the data above indicate that it does not necessarily verify one's affiliation to political power. Here, it shows that not voting is a more common trend in peripheral areas among lower economic classes.

The survey proposes some correlations between the socio-political tensions of Israeli society and its polarised views affected by populism and political personalisation. The connection between online activity and extremism can be related to the rise of online political personalisation and progressing populist practices, leading to further radicalisation.

The survey results showed a connection between online activity and a tendency towards extreme positions. The political extremism present in Israel also reflects the use of different practices (e.g., populism) in ambivalence to the extensive civil society activity against the current administration, which it claims promotes extremism. For example, the data showed a female predominance among the survey respondents. At the same time, socio-political events indicate a regression in granting rights to women and a fear of the reduction of equality between women and men in light of the political administration that changed in 2022.

The results of the survey testify to the deep polarisation that exists in Israeli society through the tendency to go in radical directions, probably under the influence of the political instability in Israel, the multitude of election systems, and security and economic instability, respectively, which started even after the outbreak of the Corona epidemic. A significant percentage felt that they were discriminated against, which links to trends of polarisation and violence and a feeling of institutionalised discrimination.

Above all, it can be said that the lack of trust in the political systems in Israel, which characterises the last decade through struggles of the cost of living and socio-economic differentiation between the periphery and the centre, can explain the tendency towards extremism and populism that centres on the concept of "the people" and its welfare. Cross-checking the data with the abstention from voting in areas geographically distant from the central and more affluent regions showed that despite political personalisation by parties, a significant part of the public did not go to vote at all. This point is also coherent with the finding that political attitudes had no relationship (either direct or indirect) to support extremist attitudes.

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6.9. Italy

Since only 3.14% of participants in Italy did not know their political attitudes, the variable was kept, and these participants were removed, resulting in a final sample of $n = 308$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
24.22 (4.20)	154	48.43	164	51.57	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	208	65.41
Agnostic/Atheist	90	28.30
Muslim	9	2.83
Other	6	1.89
Buddhist	2	0.63
Jewish	1	0.31
Bahá'í	1	0.31
Sikh	1	0.31
Hindu	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	69	21.70
No	229	72.01
Don't know	20	6.29

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Sexuality	31	44.93
Gender	21	30.43
Age	12	17.39
Other	10	14.49
Nationality	8	11.59

Disability	8	11.59
Religion	6	8.70
Language	6	8.70
Colour or race	5	7.25
Ethnic group	4	5.80

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	75	23.58	142	44.65	101	31.76
Sport or recreational organization	116	36.48	99	31.13	103	32.39
Art, music or educational organization	102	32.08	101	31.76	115	36.16
Labour union	31	9.75	130	40.88	157	49.37
Political party	50	15.72	107	33.65	161	50.63
Environmental organization	81	25.47	98	30.82	139	43.71
Professional association	68	21.38	104	32.70	146	45.91
Humanitarian or charitable organization	76	23.90	112	35.22	130	40.88
Consumer organization	58	18.24	102	32.08	158	49.69
Self-help group or mutual help group	66	20.75	100	31.45	152	47.80
Women's group	80	25.16	100	31.45	138	43.40
Other organization	41	12.89	61	19.18	216	67.92

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	68	21.38	234	73.58	16	5.03
Worked in a political party or action group	29	9.12	268	84.28	21	6.60
Worked in another ideological organization	40	12.58	262	82.39	16	5.03
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	85	26.73	218	68.55	15	4.72
Signed a petition	190	59.75	109	34.28	19	5.97
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	142	44.65	164	51.57	12	3.77
Boycotted certain products	73	22.96	219	68.87	26	8.18
Posted or shared anything about politics online	168	52.83	133	41.82	17	5.35

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with a greater perceived threat from migrants to one's national ingroup and its access to resources, welfare, and power. In contrast to our predictions, believing one's ingroup to be superior to others (collective narcissism) was linked with a lower perceived threat from migrants. Regarding political ideology, more right-wing attitudes were linked with higher perceived threat from migrants.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was directly linked with increased support for extremist attitudes. Greater perceived threat to one's national ingroup from migrants (realistic threat) and perceiving one's national ingroup to be more economically deprived relative to migrants were both linked with greater support for extremism. Regarding political ideology, holding more populist beliefs was linked with increased extremist beliefs. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing more social alienation was also associated with greater support for extremism.

Indirect predictors on extremism

Increased social dominance orientation had indirect effects on increased support for extremist attitudes via increased perceptions of realistic threat and increased group relative deprivation. Still, it also had a negative effect on decreased support via decreased populism. The total indirect effect of social dominance orientation was not significant.

A stronger online group identity had indirect effects on increased support for extremist attitudes via increased social alienation and increased populism. The total indirect effect was significant.

Increasingly right-wing political attitudes had an indirect effect on increased support for extremist attitudes via increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat. However, the total indirect effect was not significant.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Experiencing more social alienation was linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Perceiving migrants in general as more of a threat to Italy and its resources was linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Additionally, endorsing more extremist attitudes was linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia. In contrast, holding more right-wing political attitudes was associated with more positive attitudes towards Russia. In terms of attitudes towards Russian migrants, feeling more embedded in one's community (social cohesion) and experiencing more social alienation were both separately linked with worsened attitudes towards Russian migrants in the past twelve months. In contrast, greater political trust predicted more improved opinions towards Russian migrants.

Regarding Ukrainian migrants, endorsing more populist ideologies was linked with worsened attitudes in the past twelve months. Conversely, holding more extremist attitudes predicted an improvement in attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants.

Figure 11. Respecified model for Italy

Situating the findings within the Italian context

This chapter contextualises the D.Rad Survey findings for Italy. It situates the findings in the current Italian political context, where the centre-right coalition, led by Giorgia Meloni, gained the highest number of votes (approximately 44%) in the last parliamentary elections in 2022. This victory granted the coalition an absolute majority in both chambers. Within the coalition, Meloni's party, Fratelli d'Italia, emerged as the leading party with 26% of the votes. Fratelli d'Italia has been increasingly moving towards right-wing populism under Meloni (Donà 2022). Notwithstanding this rise in the popularity of far-right ideologies, with tangible impacts on the political agenda (AGI 2023) and on society (ilSole24Ore 2023), the most recent 2023 Europol TE-SAT report (Europol 2023) has highlighted how also left-wing extremism seems on the rise. A comparison with the previous year (Europol 2022) can show how the number of arrests in left-wing and anarchist-related offences doubled in one year. Instead, arrests of right-wing extremists dropped by two-thirds in the same period.

The survey shows that having a higher social dominance orientation (SDO) predicts increased group relative deprivation (group relative deprivation) and greater support for extremist attitudes. At the same time, a higher SDO directly predicted stronger perceptions that migrants pose a realistic threat to Italy and its resources. Similarly, increased perceptions that migrants pose a realistic threat to Italy and its resources predicted greater support for extremist attitudes. Furthermore, increasingly right-wing political attitudes predicted decreased anomie. Indeed, the alleged presence of different advantaged groups, lobbies and/or 'the powers that be' (*poteri forti*), as well as a general breakdown of social standards and legitimacy of the political leadership, has been endorsed and exploited several times by far-right politicians, especially before the right-wing coalition won the 2022 elections. The main narratives in this regard concern, for instance, the supposed advantages of immigrants in the request of some

welfare services (ilGiornale 2023), the claimed wealth of those operating in the ‘migration business’ (ilGiornale 2020), the activities of the so-called LGBTQIA+ lobby (laRepubblica 2022), and the so-called ‘Great Replacement’/*sostituzione etnica* (Avvenire 2023). Nevertheless, it is also underlined that members of the governing coalition, particularly Meloni, have softened their stance on other topics, such as Euroscepticism (ilFoglio 2022), after the electoral success.

Regarding online group identity, the survey shows that a stronger online group identity predicted stronger feelings of collective narcissism, stronger feelings of social cohesion in one’s neighbourhood and community, stronger feelings of social alienation, and increased populism. These findings again underscore digital environments’ polarising and alienating power, especially regarding social media (among others, Tokita, Guess & Tarnita 2021; although there are also dissenting views – see, for instance, Nordbrandt 2021). Indeed, this issue has already been pointed out in D.Rad’s report 5.2 (Crepaz 2023).

Social media intensify so-called echo chambers: “environments in which the opinion, political leaning, or belief of users about a topic gets reinforced due to repeated interactions with peers or sources having similar tendencies and attitudes” (Cinelli et al., 2021). Group polarisation theory (Sunstein 2002) states that echo chambers can drive groups towards more extreme opinions. Ranking algorithms lead to filter bubbles (Pariser 2011): users are no longer exposed to dissenting views but continue in a reinforcement and polarisation spiral. As Robert Putnam argues (2000: 178), fundamental world interactions often force us to deal with diversity, while the virtual world may be more homogeneous. This characteristic, referred to by Sunstein (2018) as “enclave deliberation”, comprises both a blessing and a curse: it allows marginalised populations to create shared safe spaces online, where they can gather and mobilise (see also the agents of de-radicalisation presented below). However, it also leads to more and more polarisation and radicalisation in political discourse and society, with anti-vax communities as the most recent prominent example.

Accordingly, this polarising effect of social media interplays with other survey results, namely that increased feelings of social alienation predict higher support for extremist attitudes and, consequently, that increased populism predicted greater support for extremist attitudes. Although other research is necessary, the survey may suggest a direct path of radicalisation that starts with online polarisation, continues with support for populist ideas and ends with the endorsement of more extremist ideologies.

The survey also shows that increased collective narcissism predicted decreased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat. This correlation can be explained by resorting to the concept of *radical chic*, *gauche caviar*, *champagne socialist* or to the alleged – although declining – moral superiority of left-wing parties, their ideologies and their rhetoric (ilFattoQuotidiano 2023; Domani 2022; Panorama 2021). Such moral superiority does not correlate with education imbalances between right- and left-wing electorates – as Fratelli d’Italia was first party among both graduated and ungraduated voters (SkyTg24 2022) – but it can be linked to

a potential class divide since the former left-wing ruling party *Partito Democratico* has increasingly been linked to a specific section of the left-wing electorate, namely the (mainly urban) upper middle class (De Sio 2018)

The D.Rad survey on Italy confirms the ongoing polarisation in society and alienation between specific segments of the population and more moderate political elites, as pointed out in the introduction. On the one hand, the extremist rhetoric used by the right-wing coalition to gain support for the 2022 elections has had a lasting impact on public opinion, even after Meloni and her allies softened their stances on many former right-wing core issues. On the other hand, left-wing voting is becoming increasingly embedded in class dynamics, to the point that left-wing parties have lost their representative role for the lower classes (both educated and non-educated) and have become parties of the elite, with an apparent detachment from the most pressing needs, concerns, and fears of the broader population. Against this backdrop, much political communication and debate has shifted to online arenas, mainly social networks, whose algorithms may boost an already polarised and alienated society.

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6.10. Kosovo

Only 0.96% of participants in Kosovo did not know their political attitudes. Thus, these participants were dropped, and the variable was kept, resulting in a sample of $n = 103$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
27.28 (7.30)	45	43.27	59	56.73	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Muslim	97	93.27
Agnostic/Atheist	4	3.85
Christian	2	1.92
Other	1	0.96
Jewish	0	0.00
Buddhist	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	15	14.42
No	73	70.19
Don't know	16	15.38

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Religion	3	20.00
Language	3	20.00
Gender	3	20.00
Other	3	20.00
Nationality	2	13.33
Sexuality	2	13.33

Colour or race	1	6.67
Ethnic group	1	6.67
Age	1	6.67
Disability	1	6.67

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	9	8.65	24	23.08	71	68.27
Sport or recreational organization	14	13.46	27	25.96	63	60.58
Art, music or educational organization	20	19.23	27	25.96	57	54.81
Labour union	13	12.50	28	26.92	63	60.58
Political party	7	6.73	39	37.50	58	55.77
Environmental organization	9	8.65	26	25.00	69	66.35
Professional association	20	19.23	19	18.27	65	62.50
Humanitarian or charitable organization	20	19.23	27	25.96	57	54.81
Consumer organization	8	7.69	30	28.85	66	63.46
Self-help group or mutual help group	11	10.58	27	25.96	66	63.46
Women's group	18	17.31	22	21.15	64	61.54
Other organization	5	4.81	25	24.04	74	71.15

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	20	19.23	71	68.27	13	12.50
Worked in a political party or action group	20	19.23	74	71.15	10	9.62
Worked in another ideological organization	11	10.58	82	78.85	11	10.58
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	12	11.54	82	78.85	10	9.62
Signed a petition	52	50.00	41	39.42	11	10.58
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	28	26.92	67	64.42	9	8.65
Boycotted certain products	63	60.58	32	30.77	9	8.65
Posted or shared anything about politics online	31	29.81	58	55.77	15	14.42

Predictors of realistic threat

Feelings of anomie were correlated with a greater perceived threat to one's national ingroup from migrants in terms of resources, welfare, and access to power. As for vulnerability, social cohesion was a protective factor in that reporting more social cohesion was linked with less perceived threat from migrants.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was linked directly with greater support for extremist attitudes. A stronger online group identity was also associated with greater support for extremist attitudes. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing more social alienation was linked with greater support for extremist attitudes.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

A stronger online group identity was associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia and Russian culture, as well as Russian migrants. Holding more extremist attitudes was linked with improved attitudes towards Russian migrants in the past twelve months. Regarding Ukrainian migrants, greater trust in the government predicted improved attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the past twelve months.

Figure 12. Respecified model for Kosovo

Situating the findings within the Kosovan context

The following chapter analyses the D.Rad findings for Kosovo, contextualising them within the country's socio-political landscape before and during the period when the survey was conducted. During this period, Kosovo experienced a tumultuous political and institutional crisis amid the COVID-19 pandemic. In late March 2020, just after the first case of COVID-19 was registered, the coalition government in Kosovo, composed of the Vetëvendosje (Self-Determination Movement) and LDK (Democratic League of Kosovo), was ousted through a vote of no-confidence in the Kosovo Assembly. Subsequently, a new government led by LDK

and its coalition partner was established in early June 2020 (Elshani, Avdiu and Balaj, 2022). However, this coalition government proved short-lived, as new snap elections were declared shortly after that, culminating in the electoral win of the Self-Determination Movement. The latter won a landslide victory, winning over 50 percent of the vote (“Kosovo’s left-wing opposition party sees landslide win”, 2021). This marked the first instance where an opposition party secured a substantial win. The Self-Determination Movement is a left-wing party, and its triumph in the elections was propelled by a promise to combat organised crime and corruption, revive Kosovo’s economy, and fight the pandemic. The party’s roots as a populist movement that began as a youth-driven initiative garnered support from a broad spectrum of groups in Kosovo, including youth, the unemployed and other marginalised population segments (Onorato and Scott, 2021). While negotiations on normalising relations with Serbia did not figure high on the party’s agenda, they remained a key and highly debated topic in the months following the election. Unfortunately, reaching a resolution between the two countries, mediated by the EU, has become increasingly challenging, resulting in a protracted stalemate. Meanwhile, inter-ethnic tensions have been on the rise since August 2022, significantly impacting relations between the Kosovo Serb and Kosovo Albanian communities (Ozturk, 2023).

The data indicates that Kosovars tend to be more engaged in civil society organisations, such as women's groups or humanitarian and charitable initiatives, rather than displaying significant involvement in political activism, which challenges the conventional belief that there is high political activism among the population. However, it is worth noting that there is a prevalent negative perception of political parties among the people, leading to reluctance to identify with them when questioned (“Kosovo Citizen Perceptions Of Political Parties”, 2022). This sentiment arises from the widespread public opinion in Kosovo that views political parties as disconnected from everyday citizens and primarily serving the interests of select groups and loyal members. This perspective may help explain why, as highlighted above, in the 2021 national elections, a political party representing marginalised segments of society achieved an unprecedented 51% of the vote.

This pattern in political engagement may shed light on the age-related correlations observed in the findings, specifically the tendency for older participants to express lower levels of trust in the national political system. The current ruling party predominantly appeals to a younger electorate, while older voters tend to exhibit more traditional voting behaviour and hold political beliefs that align with the previous establishment. Young people's support for a party that advocates for a more balanced position for Kosovo in regional and international arenas further underscores this generational divide in political preferences.

Regarding various political actions participants reported engaging in over the past year, the majority mentioned boycotting specific products as the predominant form of political activism. This aligns with a campaign that emerged in early 2023 in response to heightened inter-ethnic tensions between Kosovo and Serbia. The 'Don't Buy Serbian Products' campaign encouraged Kosovo businesses to stop selling Serbian products. Its goal was to discourage

Kosovo citizens from supporting Serbia economically and instead promote buying locally, thereby keeping money within the Kosovo economy (Taylor, 2023).

Regarding participants' responses concerning their attitudes towards Russia and their views on Russian and Ukrainian immigrants, the findings align with the prevailing sentiment in Kosovo, characterised by a pro-European and pro-Ukraine stance. As a collective, participants indicated that their attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the past year had improved, while conversely, they reported a decline in their views towards Russian migrants. This shift can be attributed to the geopolitical context, as Russia is seen as an ally of Serbia, thereby positioning them as a direct adversary to Kosovo. In many ways, Kosovars perceive that the relationship between Russia and Ukraine parallels the historical relationship between Serbia and Kosovo (Nuqi, 2022).

The study also revealed that increased political trust in the government was associated with more favourable opinions towards Ukrainian migrants over the past year. The pro-Ukrainian stance of the current Kosovo government and previous administrations can explain this correlation. The Kosovo government has consistently supported Ukraine since the onset of the war, including by adopting the EU sanctions against Russia, hosting Ukrainian journalists through the Journalists-in-Residence Kosovo Programme, and providing monetary support to the country (Bami, 2022).

Another notable finding of the report is related to online group identity. The finding that a stronger online group identity predicts greater support for extremist attitudes is particularly relevant in the context of Kosovo, where online platforms have played a significant role in the dissemination of radical and extremist views. This trend has been especially evident with the rise of ethno-political radicalisation, exacerbated by online engagement with radical communities. The unresolved dispute between Serbia and Kosovo has created an environment where online narratives promoting ethno-political radicalisation thrive (Ilazi and Orana, 2022).

The D.Rad findings for Kosovo provide a glimpse into the country's socio-political landscape marked by escalating inter-ethnic tensions, exacerbated by a stagnant Kosovo-Serbia dialogue and lingering wounds from the war. The age-related disparities revealed in the study underscore a significant generational shift in perspectives across a range of critical issues, such as migration, trust in public institutions, and more. This shift was prominently displayed during the 2021 parliamentary elections, where the younger generation demonstrated their capacity to hold previous governments accountable and demand a better future. The study's findings underscore the significant role played by the online sphere, serving as a platform for both fostering solidarity and perpetuating divisive narratives of "us versus them," thereby fueling extremist ideologies. Like elsewhere, people in Kosovo increasingly turn to online platforms and social media to seek validation for their viewpoints and amplify their opinions. Social media has become the primary battleground where individuals propagate inter-ethnic hatred and divisive narratives, particularly following increased tensions between Kosovo and Serbia in recent years.

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6.11. Poland

Poland had 30.75% of participants reporting not knowing their political attitudes. This variable was subsequently excluded from the model, keeping all participants and resulting in a final sample of $n = 322$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
24.49 (6.72)	151	46.89	171	53.10	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	244	75.78
Agnostic/Atheist	69	21.43
Other	4	1.24
Buddhist	3	0.93
Jewish	1	0.31
Muslim	1	0.31
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	60	18.63
No	241	74.84
Don't know	21	6.52

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Gender	24	40.00
Sexuality	21	35.00
Religion	12	20.00
Colour or race	7	11.67
Other	6	10.00

Nationality	4	6.67
Age	4	6.67
Language	2	3.33
Disability	2	3.33
Ethnic group	1	1.67

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	114	35.40	128	39.75	80	24.84
Sport or recreational organization	103	31.99	82	25.47	137	42.55
Art, music or educational organization	94	29.19	84	26.09	144	44.72
Labour union	83	25.78	81	25.16	158	49.07
Political party	32	9.94	100	31.06	190	59.01
Environmental organization	67	20.81	80	24.84	175	54.35
Professional association	67	20.81	77	23.91	178	55.28
Humanitarian or charitable organization	83	25.78	86	26.71	153	47.52
Consumer organization	62	19.25	75	23.29	185	57.45
Self-help group or mutual help group	79	24.53	75	23.29	168	52.17
Women's group	72	22.36	75	23.29	175	54.35
Other organization	26	8.07	51	15.84	245	76.09

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	75	23.29	217	67.39	30	9.32
Worked in a political party or action group	28	8.70	261	81.06	33	10.25
Worked in another ideological organization	31	9.63	259	80.43	32	9.94
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	56	17.39	236	73.29	30	9.32
Signed a petition	149	46.27	143	44.41	30	9.32
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	95	29.50	196	60.87	31	9.63
Boycotted certain products	95	29.50	180	55.90	47	14.60
Posted or shared anything about politics online	116	36.02	176	54.66	30	9.32

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with perceiving migrants as a larger threat to one's national ingroup and its access to resources, welfare, and power. Additionally, perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants was also associated with increased perceived threat from migrants.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with increased support for extremist attitudes. Perceiving one's ingroup as being superior to other social groups (collective narcissism) was also linked with increased support for extremist attitudes. Additionally, perceiving that one's ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants was also associated with increased support for extremist attitudes. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing greater social alienation was associated with higher support for extremism; in contrast, experiencing more social cohesion was a protective factor in that experiencing more social cohesion was linked with decreased support for extremism.

Indirect predictors on extremism

Online group identity had an indirect effect on extremist attitudes via collective narcissism and social alienation. A stronger online group identity predicted increased collective narcissism and increased feelings of being socially alienated. These increases, in turn, predicted stronger support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect of online group identity (i.e., the sum of *all* indirect effects through other variables, even if these were not statistically significant on their own) was significant; a stronger online group identity predicted increased support for extremist attitudes via the combination of its relationship to the mediating variables in the model (though note this total indirect effect is mainly driven by the indirect effects of collective narcissism and social alienation).

Figure 14. Respecified model for Poland

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Feelings of social alienation and endorsing more populist attitudes were both separately associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Perceiving that migrants are more of a threat to Poland and its resources was, in contrast, linked with more positive views towards Russia. Regarding attitudes towards Russian migrants, endorsing more populist attitudes was associated with worsened opinions towards Russian migrants in the past twelve months. Perceiving that migrants were a greater threat to Poland was linked to worsened opinions towards Ukrainian migrants in the past twelve months.

Situating the findings within the Polish context

This chapter situates the findings of the D.Rad questionnaire in the political context of Poland. While other societal and individual aspects are relevant to explaining extremism and radicalisation on an individual or societal level, as evidenced in the literature, the political context is one of the most important macro factors.

The D.Rad survey was conducted in Poland while the country was governed by a right-wing coalition led by Prime Minister Mateusz Morawiecki from the conservative *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* party. Besides *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość*, which held 237 seats (43.6%), other parliamentary parties were the liberal *Koalicja Obywatelska* (27.4% - 133 seats), the left-wing *Lewica* (12.6% - 47 seats), the agrarian *Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe* (8.6% - 31 seats), the far-right *Konfederacja Wolność i Niepodległość* (6.8% - 11 seats) and *Mniejszość Niemiecka* – a German minority party (0.2% - 1 seat). The last parliamentary elections in Poland took place on October 15, 2023, ending the rule of *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość*.

Typically, in Poland, urban areas are left-wing oriented compared to peri-urban areas. The larger the urban centre, the more support there is for *Koalicja Obywatelska*. *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* won the 2018 parliamentary elections in the peri-urban with a result of 56.2%, and the *Koalicja Obywatelska* received 16.7% of the votes. Also, in small towns (up to 50,000 inhabitants), *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* won with the support of 41.7%, while 28.2% voted for *Koalicja Obywatelska*. In the largest cities (over 500,000 inhabitants), 41.1% voted for *Koalicja Obywatelska* and for *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* – 26.9%. Naturally, *Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe* found the most voters in rural areas; the least support came from urban voters. *Konfederacja* achieved equal results in urban and peri-urban areas.

In terms of the voting patterns in Poland, what is particularly relevant is, although unofficial and oversimplified, the widely recognised and examined distinction between Poland "A" and Poland "B". The region west of the Vistula River, known as Poland "A", has been acknowledged as more developed economically than Poland "B", the part of Poland east of the river. Since the 1990s, Poland "A" tended to support secular and liberal political parties, while voters from Poland "B" (excluding Warsaw) parties represented Christian and conservative political agendas.

The survey indicated that increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat predicted worsened opinions towards Ukrainian migrants in the past year. In contrast, increased populism predicted worsened opinions towards Russian migrants in the past year. This is consistent with current trends in Poland, particularly within right-wing circles. Polish right-wing populism builds on anti-immigrant sentiment. This was particularly evident during the migration wave and EU 'crisis', which invoked Eurosceptic and anti-German views in Poland (Stojarová, 2018). However, this sentiment does not apply equally to all migrants. As a result of the violation of Ukraine's territorial integrity, the position of political parties (both the ruling centre-right and the mainstream opposition parties) regarding the assessment of the political situation was relatively uniform. It included a call for multidimensional aid for Ukraine, condemnation of the aggression, and sanctions against Russia (Sokół, 2022). The contacts between representatives of Polish political parties and political circles in Ukraine intensified - *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* politicians were active, especially during Euromaidan, and other political elites (especially *Platforma Obywatelska* and *Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe*) were in favour of supporting Ukraine's pro-European aspirations (Mrozek, 2015). The mainstream political circles in Poland had a very clear assessment that the victims of Russian aggression need comprehensive assistance (humanitarian, financial, and military).

In this context, it is also noteworthy to point out Russian propaganda activities in Poland aiming to discredit refugees from Ukraine to create conflicts between Poles and Ukrainian migrants, presenting the latter as a threat to Polish society. As the Government Plenipotentiary for the Security of the Information Space of the Republic of Poland points out (2023), the Kremlin seeks to create an impression that there is widespread opposition in Europe to supporting Ukraine's defence efforts, inspires groups pretending to be a pacifist in various places, as well as spreads disinformation:

The Russians constantly monitor the Polish-language information environment. They are able to dynamically manage the context and give actual events their interpretations to discredit Ukraine or Ukrainians in the eyes of Poles. (...) The Legionella infection in Rzeszów was used by Russian propaganda to attack the perception of Ukraine and the USA by the Poles. The Russians promoted the lie that the bacterium was brought by refugees from Ukraine and that it was the product of experiments in American laboratories.

Relevant is also the finding that increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat predicted improved attitudes towards Russia. It is worth pointing out that the more populist and socially alienated the D.Rad-survey respondents were, the worse was their perception towards Russia (e.g., "We should break all cooperation with Russian academics, artists, and athletes."). Most political parties in Poland supported sanctions against the aggressor and aid for Ukraine and its citizens, which was manifested in the documents submitted by the parliamentary majority since the beginning of 2022. Nevertheless, this was not the case with some political circles, such as *Konfederacja*, that lacked broad public support and the ability to influence Polish foreign policy. Despite internal differences, some MPs critiqued the political

mainstream's policy towards Ukraine and Ukrainian citizens in Poland, and one member of this party even initiated a 'stop Ukrainization' campaign.

Significant in the context are the findings of the D.Rad survey that showed that age was negatively correlated with extremism, such that older participants had lower support for extremist attitudes. These findings are consistent with what is known about Polish parties associated with extreme political opinions, as the age cohort most supportive of *Konfederacja* is mainly young men. Moreover, the survey showed that men reported more support for extremist attitudes than women did. This finding is also consistent with the factual situation as Poles arrested for extremism, similar to other parts of the world, also tend to be younger and male (Agency of Interior Security, 2023), with perpetrators representing both right-wing and left-wing political extremism.

Wiech (2023), explaining the popularity of *Konfederacja* among young Polish men, pointed out that this group has been virtually unnoticed by all major political forces in recent years. The Programme 500 Plus, which gained votes for *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość*, among other groups, is not appealing to young men who either do not have children yet or believe these kinds of social programs are unfair towards them. The popularity of *Konfederacja* is also the result of the anti-campaign by *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* and *Koalicja Obywatelska*, who limited their campaign to threatening scenarios of what will happen if the opponent stays in power or gains it. Wiech further clarifies that *Konfederacja* managed to understand the needs of young men who enter the labour market and run a campaign of promises accordingly. These promises are largely unrealistic ('low and simple taxes', 'voluntary social insurance', rejection of the EU's climate policy) and do not seem concerned about financing, the long-term effects, or even legal mechanisms for their implementation. At the same time, they can reach frustrated young males skillfully through social media, TikTok or organising pub meetings with party leaders.

The results of the D.Rad survey that increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat predicted improved attitudes towards Russia could be interpreted in the context of Kremlin propaganda and lack of empathy coupled with displaying anxiety over scarce economic resources. What is more, the participants who belonged to discriminated groups reported more improved opinions towards Ukrainian migrants in the last 12 months than participants who did not belong to discriminated groups did, whose opinions remained primarily unchanged. While society has been divided over the issues of migration and relation towards the EU, the issue of Ukrainian migrants seems less polarising. There is no doubt that Polish-Ukrainian relations in previous years were present both in official party programs and in the statements of party leaders with the same postulates (Sokol, 2022).

The interpretation of the D.Rad survey was conducted here in the context of the political situation, which helped to evaluate the most important macro factors. However, it is also worth pointing out that other relevant factors are likely to have an impact. Moreover, the political climate, consisting of the views of individual political parties on many issues, is not constant

but transforms depending on the changing international situation and the internal situation in other countries, e.g., Ukraine.

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6.12. Serbia

Serbia had 29.22% of participants reporting not knowing their political attitudes. This variable was subsequently excluded from the model, keeping all participants and resulting in a final sample of $n = 332$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
25.30 (4.34)	165	49.70	166	50.00	1	0.30

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	283	85.24
Agnostic/Atheist	27	8.13
Other	13	3.92
Muslim	9	2.71
Jewish	0	0.00
Buddhist	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	50	21.92
No	255	70.89
Don't know	27	7.19

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Nationality	18	36.00
Religion	16	32.00
Gender	13	26.00
Language	10	20.00
Sexuality	10	20.00
Colour or race	8	16.00
Ethnic group	5	10.00
Other	5	10.00
Age	4	8.00
Disability	0	0.00

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	120	36.14	107	32.23	105	31.63
Sport or recreational organization	97	29.22	77	23.19	158	47.59
Art, music or educational organization	94	28.31	79	23.80	159	47.89
Labour union	38	11.45	83	25.00	211	63.55
Political party	26	7.83	70	21.08	236	71.08
Environmental organization	56	16.87	70	21.08	206	62.05
Professional association	33	9.94	62	18.67	237	71.39
Humanitarian or charitable organization	102	30.72	61	18.37	169	50.90
Consumer organization	40	12.05	63	18.98	229	68.98
Self-help group or mutual help group	42	12.65	63	18.98	227	68.37
Women's group	45	13.55	61	18.37	226	68.07
Other organization	25	7.53	39	11.75	268	80.72

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	56	16.87	242	72.89	34	10.24
Worked in a political party or action group	39	11.75	267	80.42	26	7.83
Worked in another ideological organization	29	8.73	273	82.23	30	9.04
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	39	11.75	267	80.42	26	7.83
Signed a petition	197	59.34	110	33.13	25	7.53
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	78	23.49	232	69.88	22	6.63
Boycotted certain products	123	37.05	185	55.72	24	7.23
Posted or shared anything about politics online	105	31.63	200	60.24	27	8.13

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was linked with greater perceptions of threat to one's national ingroup from migrants regarding access to resources, wealth, and power. Perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived than migrants was associated with perceiving more threat. Greater feelings of anomie also predicted perceiving more threat from migrants to Serbia and its resources.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with more support of extremist attitudes. Perceiving one's social group to be superior (collective narcissism) was linked with increased support of extremist attitudes. In addition, perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants (group relative deprivation) was also linked with greater support for extremism. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing more social alienation was linked with increased endorsement of extremist attitudes.

Indirect predictors on extremism

The effect of social dominance orientation on support for extremist attitudes was mediated by collective narcissism: a higher social dominance orientation predicted increased collective narcissism, which in turn predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect (i.e., the sum of all indirect effects, be these statistically significant or not) of social dominance orientation on extremist attitudes was non-significant, which suggests the combination of all the influences of social dominance orientation through the mediating variables does not predict support for extremist attitudes, even if the effect through collective narcissism when controlling for all other variables, did.

Online group identity also had an indirect effect on extremist attitudes via collective narcissism. A stronger online group identity predicted increased collective narcissism, which then predicted greater support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect was not statistically significant, meaning online group identity does not predict extremism when considering all the relationships to the mediating variables.

Figure 15. Respecified model for Serbia

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants was associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Additionally, holding more trust in the Polish government was also linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia and Russian culture. Increased endorsement of extremism also predicted more negative attitudes towards Russia. In contrast, holding a more populist ideology was linked with improved attitudes towards Russia.

None of the variables of interest (i.e. social dominance orientation, online group identity, collective narcissism, anomie, individual and group relative deprivation, social cohesion, social alienation, populism, political trust, perceptions of migrants as realistic threats, support for extremist attitudes) reliably predicted attitudes towards Russian migrants. In contrast, perceiving that migrants in general were a greater threat towards Serbia and its resources was linked with worsening attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the past twelve months.

Situating the findings within the Serbian context

The radicalisation patterns in Serbia are deeply rooted in its past, particularly in the turbulent 1990s, which is why it is necessary to glance back at those past events. During this time, the country faced ethnic intolerance, separatist ambitions, political instability, and international isolation, along with violent episodes and participation in ethnic wars. As a result, xenophobic views among the Serbian population were prevalent. The overthrow of Slobodan Milošević's regime in 2000 marked a significant turning point, leading to comprehensive political, economic, and cultural transformations. The assassination of Serbian Prime Minister Zoran Djindjić in 2003 hindered the government's ability to sustain its reforms. Furthermore, Kosovo's unilateral declaration of independence in 2008 fuelled ethnic tensions and frustrations in Serbian society. Thus, ethnoreligious polarisations fuelled by legacies of wars, collective grievances, conflicting historical narratives, identity crisis, and lack of opportunities emerge as dominant drivers of radicalisation in Serbia, which is a manifestation of the “socially embedded culture of extremism” (Halilovic Pastuovic et al., 2022, p. 5).

Since 2012, Serbia has experienced a slide into authoritarianism under the rule of the Serbian Progressive Party (SNS), resulting in its lowest democracy score in twenty years and the normalisation of extremist discourses (Tatalović, 2021). Far-right extremism, legitimised during Milošević's rule, shifted focus to internal enemies like minorities, LGBT+, and migrants after being strengthened by the ruling party SNS.

Traditional and conservative attitudes are predominant in villages and smaller towns, while in some larger urban areas, more liberal thoughts oppose conservative and far-right stances. People living in rural areas tend to trust the church more and prefer populist leadership than those living in urban areas (Vucicevic & Jovic, 2020). Regional inequality and urban-rural economic disparities are quite pronounced in Serbia; thus, financial setbacks and poverty in rural areas are related to the growing populism in society (RTS, 2018). Though populism is stronger in peri-urban areas, a rise in populist and far-right attitudes has been noted throughout Serbia recently, especially in the capital city.

In geographical terms, radicalisation trends are more visible going from the country's north towards its central and southern regions. Northern parts of Serbia (Vojvodina region) are populated with different minorities, which could explain higher tolerance towards migrants and less extremist stances. The far-right is concentrated in Belgrade and the central part of the country, while Islamist extremists are located primarily in the Southern region of the country (Sanžak region), in Novi Pazar as a political seat, though they tend to attract Muslims in other parts of the country to spread their influence (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023; Halilovic Pastuovic et al., 2022). The youth, especially in the South and South-West regions, are susceptible to Islamic radicalisation due to religious identity, socioeconomic challenges, and perceived discrimination.

Both right-wing and Islamist extremism can reinforce each other, further exacerbating the situation. As the latest research indicates, far-right extremism in Serbia is on the rise while violent Islamist extremism is in decline, though its non-violent forms are experiencing an

increase (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023; RAN, 2022). The particular danger stems from online spaces and social media, where extremist narratives are being proliferated, normalised and mainstreamed, which is especially obvious since the outbreak of the pandemic and war in Ukraine (RAN, 2022). Since 2020 and 2021, Serbia has been experiencing a wave of protests against lockdowns, vaccines, migrants (coming from the Middle East), EuroPride (September 2022), as well as rallies in support of Russia (starting in March 2022), all organised by far-right extremist groups and political parties. Many of the far-right groups have close links with the ruling party and enjoy the support of the Government, which uses them for different purposes (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023). Furthermore, following the onset of the Ukrainian war in February 2022, a large number of Russian and Ukrainian migrants and refugees came to Serbia. Understanding this complex context is essential for interpreting the D.Rad survey results.

D.Rad survey findings indicate a direct positive correlation between collective narcissism and increased support for extremist attitudes. In the context of Serbian radicalisation, the prevailing narrative suggests that Serbs consider themselves genetically superior, more intelligent, stronger, and better-looking than others, particularly when compared to Muslims (BIRN, 2014). “Serbs are a heavenly people”, as claimed by the Serbian nationalist narrative (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023, p. 10). The notion of Serbian supremacy over others is embraced by certain right-wing groups that are actively present in today's society, especially those whose primary rhetoric revolves around glorifying the conflicts of the 1990s and war criminals. Some of the right-wing extremist groups that advocate white supremacy are Blood and Honour Serbia and the *National Serbian Front* (Buljubašić, 2022).

Higher levels of Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) and a stronger online group identity were found to predict heightened collective narcissism. Consequently, both SDO and online group identity had a small, indirect, positive impact on the support for extremist attitudes through collective narcissism. At the same time, other mediators did not significantly influence the results. Stronger online group identity was found to predict increased social cohesion, but it did not directly impact extremism. Participants who belonged to one or more discriminated groups displayed a stronger online group identity than those who were not part of any discriminated groups. As mentioned earlier, online group identity exhibited only an indirect positive effect on supporting extremist attitudes via collective narcissism. However, surprisingly, this survey did not establish a connection between online group identity and the perception of migrants as a threat to Serbia. The D.Rad survey findings come as a surprise as online radicalisation in Serbia is on the rise as extremists use ethnic identity, hate and conspiracies to proliferate extremist narratives and fake news, particularly regarding the coronavirus pandemic and the war in Ukraine, especially in the existing climate where elites rely upon “manipulation of collective traumas to promote *otherness*” (RAN, 2022, p. 3). Moreover, anti-immigration rhetoric is central to online content shared by far-right (Buljubašić, 2022; RAN, 2022). The sudden increase in these narratives coincides with the pandemic outbreak as people went online more than ever before, and it was the most efficient way to attract vulnerable people to join them.

One such extremist group is *Narodna patrola (People's Patrol)*. The group is very active on social networks, where its members share hateful anti-immigrant content, calling for violence and protests against migrants (Sejdinović, 2021). Extremist propaganda is being legitimised on social media, highlighting the danger of Islamisation of Serbia due to migrant settlements (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2022; Jakovljević, 2021). For example, the Facebook group *STOP Naseljavanju migranata (STOP Migrant Settlement)*, which advocated the expulsion of migrants due to the danger of population and culture change, had 330,000 followers (Rogač, 2021). Current research indicates that ethnic and religious polarisations, as well as political and societal divisions, are being reinforced by hate narratives in online space, which stem from the legacies of past wars. This is particularly evident regarding Muslim migrants as the Balkans and Serbia have been marked as the latest line of defence of Christian frontiers (Buljubašić, 2022; RAN, 2022). As far-right extremists use online groups to share hate narratives, there is a growing threat of online recruitment for participating in the war in Ukraine on the side of Russia (Buljubašić, 2022; RAN, 2022).

Unlike online group identity, SDO also directly influences extremism. There exists a clear positive correlation between SDO and support for extremist attitudes. Higher SDO levels predict greater endorsement of nationalism, racism, sexism, discrimination, and violence as a means of maintaining the established group hierarchy (Vukčević Marković, Nicović & Živanović, 2021). The main narrative of Serbian nationalists revolves around historical rights and the establishment of Greater Serbia. This far-right project is rooted in the belief that parts of Serbian land, along with its people, were taken away during the wars of the 1990s, particularly the Kosovo War in 1999. Consequently, the unification of these lost territories is regarded as the ultimate goal, fuelling extremist ideas and actions (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023; Buljubašić, 2022). This nationalist rhetoric is predominantly utilised by the leading Serbian Progressive Party and the Serbian President Vučić (until recently, he occupied the position of the Party's leader), who exercises considerable control over almost all media in Serbia, constantly shaping public opinion (Ruge, 2023). Despite variations in their discourses, far-right movements and groups find common ground in their focus on the issue of Kosovo, which serves as a unifying force and mobilises the entire far-right spectrum. Kosovo is vital in Serbian national identity, and the prolonged tensions surrounding it have further escalated far-right sentiments. This trend was evident during the 2022 parliamentary elections, where such views gained legitimacy and significant media attention, leading to the normalisation of far-right discourse and rhetoric, especially in the statements of the president himself, who, assuming an authoritarian and dominant political role, strategically employs nationalist discourse to consolidate his political power (Ruge, 2023). The example of Kosovo is frequently used to illustrate potential future scenarios for the rest of Orthodox Serbia, which has already experienced the loss of its cultural cradle (Kosovo and Metohija) to (primarily) Muslims, leading to concerns about the Serbian Orthodox people becoming a minority in the future.

Many populist initiatives, as well as far-right politicians, have been announcing for some time already that Serbia confronts a large number of migrants who will change the population structure of "white" Serbia and Europe (Pejić, 2020). These activities further fuel xenophobic attitudes that have been present since the 1990s. Consequently, there exists a complex

interplay of interconnected drivers, with ethnonationalism and religious factors emerging as the most potent predictors of extremism in Serbia. Furthermore, as numerous studies have confirmed, the religious component appears to exert significant influence, surpassing ethnic divisions and extending its impact beyond the boundaries of different ethnic groups (Halilovic Pastuovic et al., 2022; Vukčević Marković, Nicović & Živanović, 2021). Apart from the prevalent Serbian Orthodox Church and the Orthodox Christian identity that holds sway over the majority of Serbia, there is also a robust Muslim identity, particularly noticeable in the southern regions, primarily the Sandžak region, where Islamist radicalisation and extremism have been observed. In Serbia, two rival Islamic Communities are operating under the auspices of Belgrade and Sarajevo, respectively, where such division creates a breeding ground for fundamentalist influence from abroad (Halilovic Pastuovic et al., 2022). However, it is the perception of discrimination of the Bosniak community by the central government that ignites the radicalisation flame in the Sandžak region. This conflict dates back to the 1990s and has generated tensions, further reinforced by high youth unemployment and economic hardships (Cultural Centre DamaD, 2015). In broad terms, extremism in Serbia, whether originating from far-right or Islamist ideologies, possesses a strong religious component that contributes to polarisation.

As revealed by the D.Rad survey results, respondents who do not identify as part of any discriminated groups exhibit slightly higher levels of Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) than those who perceive themselves as discriminated. This aligns with the (far-right) extremist discourse that relies on discriminating against certain groups based on race, ethnicity, religion, or other characteristics. However, it is worth noting that discriminated against groups still demonstrate strong SDO, which could potentially lead to a shift in positions, resulting in the increasing dominance of groups previously discriminated against (Vukčević Marković, Nicović & Živanović, 2021). Among the targeted groups, the Roma community has faced significant discrimination from various extremist groups, making their situation a crucial human rights issue in Serbia. In this context, it is essential to draw attention to the problem of Roma radicalisation, which has been identified as a growing trend among Roma Muslims. (Djorić, 2021; Tatalović, 2021).

Perception of social injustice serves as a significant driver of radicalisation and extremism in Serbia. In light of these notions, it is crucial to highlight the findings of the D.Rad survey concerning social alienation, which identified a positive correlation between social alienation and support for extremist attitudes. According to the D.Rad survey, an increased perception of social exclusion directly predicts extremist attitudes. In the region of Sandžak, situated in one of the most economically disadvantaged areas of the country with high rates of youth unemployment, many young people are advocating for some level of regional autonomy or, in more extreme cases, even secession (Cultural Centre DamaD, 2015). The underlying reason for such attitudes lies in the perception of marginalisation and social injustice (Vukčević Marković, Nicović & Živanović, 2021), particularly concerning the rights of minorities in Serbia. In this specific case, the region is predominantly inhabited by the Bosniak ethnic group, who primarily identify as Muslims. As revealed in the research of Cultural Centre DamaD on extremism in Novi Pazar, some respondents expressed their views about the government in

Belgrade, stating, "...this government in Belgrade is a gang... People here in general, almost everyone, think of Belgrade as an enemy" (Cultural Centre DamaD, 2015, p. 27). This sentiment indicates a strong feeling of rejection towards Belgrade, which holds the political power, leading to increased dissatisfaction and fuelling extremist ideas and sentiments. It can be concluded that their extremist attitudes, fuelled by social alienation, are primarily directed towards the central government. Many research studies indicate that these extremists tend to isolate themselves from other groups, and many of them come from backgrounds with family dysfunction and have a history of exposure to hostile social environments (Cultural Centre DamaD, 2015; Vukčević Marković, Nicović & Živanović, 2021).

In addition to its direct and indirect impact (via collective narcissism) on support for extremist attitudes, higher SDO scores are also associated with negative attitudes towards immigrants. Even after controlling for any effects through collective narcissism, anomie, or perceived individual or group relative deprivation, the survey findings revealed a direct positive correlation between SDO and an increased perception that migrants pose a realistic threat to Serbia and its resources. Increased SDO predicts negative attitudes towards immigrants, as well as prejudice and resistance to their assimilation within the Serbian cultural context. The dominant Serbian Orthodox identity plays a significant role in Serbian society, and preserving its top position remains a priority (Buljubašić, 2022). From this standpoint, extremist attitudes and anti-immigration sentiments arise. Muslims have long been portrayed as wanting to suppress Christians and seize ancestral lands, fuelling fears that they might eventually become the majority in the country, leaving Serbians as a minority in their homeland (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2022). This far-right discourse aligns with broader far-right rhetoric in the European Union, where migrants are often perceived as threats to ethnic and religious identity. Conservative political discourses also aim to curb immigration. Respondents with higher SDO scores tend to view migrants as threatening the status quo they wish to preserve. There is a fear that once assimilated into the dominant culture, immigrants might exceed its boundaries and bring about change. The dominant narrative concerns the Islamisation of Serbia and complete demographic and cultural change due to migrants settling in Serbian land (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2022; Jakovljević, 2021). During 2020, there were many protests against migrants in cities like Belgrade, Požarevac, Šid, and Subotica organised by different populist initiatives like *Narodne patrole (People's Patrols)* (Rogač, 2021). Serbian citizens perceived migrants as one of the greatest threats to external and internal security (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2022). In 2022, there was a significant increase in the number of migrants coming from Afghanistan, Syria, and Pakistan who used the Balkan route to reach the European Union (FoNet, N1 Beograd, 2022), which revived far-right xenophobic narratives.

When it comes to the Russian and Ukrainian migrants, the perception is quite different. The Serbian Orthodox identity is projected as dominant and superior to immigrants who do not share the same religion. The perceived threat from migrants is related to those coming from the Middle East, while it is not the case with Russian and Ukrainian migrants. This observation further supports the hypothesis of the significant role of religious identity in shaping attitudes towards immigrants. The D.Rad survey results indicate that respondents in Serbia have developed more positive feelings towards Russian migrants over the past 12 months, while

their perceptions of Ukrainian migrants have remained relatively unchanged, hovering near a neutral standpoint. This favourable perception towards Russians can be attributed to shared religious identity (Christian Orthodox), historical connections with the Russian people, and a sense of having similar culture and traditional values. Interestingly, none of the variables tested could reliably predict changes in opinions towards Russian migrants over the mentioned period, implying that Russians are not perceived as a threat to Serbian national and religious identity.

On the contrary, increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat corresponded with worsened opinions towards Ukrainian migrants over the same 12-month period. The reasons behind this negative perception towards Ukrainians might vary and require further examination. Still, it is evident that this group of migrants is seen as posing a potential threat in some capacity, leading to unfavourable opinions among the respondents. The reason behind such attitudes might be found in pro-Russian media reporting, as well as the influence of far-right narratives regarding the war in Ukraine (Ranković, 2023).

While individual relative deprivation (individual relative deprivation) did not show statistical relevance, group relative deprivation (group relative deprivation) emerged as a highly significant predictor of extremism and anti-immigrant sentiments.

The D.Rad survey findings indicated a direct positive relationship between group relative deprivation and both the perception of migrants as a threat to Serbia and its resources and increased support for extremist attitudes. Notably, the perception of migrants from the Middle East and Russia/Ukraine has undergone a shift. Although Russian and Ukrainian migrants and refugees are generally perceived positively in terms of identity, migrants from Arab nations are not as favourably viewed. However, economic factors play a significant role in influencing sentiments towards these migrant groups. Migrants from the Middle East are often perceived as economically disadvantaged and more deprived than Serbian nationals, while Russian and Ukrainian migrants and refugees are seen as financially better off. Following the onset of the war in Ukraine in February 2022, numerous Ukrainians seeking refuge from the conflict and Russians evading conscription in their home country found solace in Serbia, where they sought opportunities to work and live. Many registered their businesses, while numerous companies that hired individuals from these countries also established branches in Serbia, primarily in Belgrade, enticing people to move to the country (Rakic, 2022). The influx of Russians and Ukrainians was so substantial during the initial months that rental prices skyrocketed. This surge in housing costs posed a significant challenge for Serbian citizens, who could not afford such exorbitant rents, leading to feelings of deprivation within their own country. Numerous students encountered considerable housing difficulties due to their inability to afford apartments in Belgrade. Moreover, many Serbian citizens, including families, were evicted from their rented apartments by landlords who opted to rent to wealthy Russians and Ukrainians, often without regard for the price (Matić, 2022). The dire housing situation that Serbian citizens face due to the arrival of Russian and Ukrainian migrants has heightened feelings of social injustice, marginalisation, and frustration. The inability to secure affordable

housing, directly attributed to the presence of these migrants, fuels negative sentiments and exacerbates existing grievances within the Serbian population.

The D.Rad survey also found that older participants perceived the economic situation of nationals compared to migrants worse, indicating a correlation between age and group relative deprivation. Similarly, the survey revealed that increased group relative deprivation, along with increased political trust and support for extremist attitudes, predicted worsened attitudes against Russia. The reasons behind such attitudes towards Russia might be related to the high inflation rate following the war in Ukraine and the influence of opposition forces (mainly centre-left) who advocate for the introduction of sanctions on Russia. The Democratic Party, the Party of Freedom and Justice, and the Green-left coalition are some of the opposition parties calling for imposing sanctions on Russia to align with the EU foreign policy (Pujkilović, 2022). These factors contribute to the complex interplay of perceptions and attitudes observed in Serbian society.

On the other hand, age was positively correlated with greater support for populism, which, in turn, was associated with improved attitudes towards Russia. In that context, it is relevant to mention that in March 2022, the first rally in support of Russia and the Russian invasion of Ukraine was held in Belgrade, gathering several thousand people, and it was initiated by the populist group *People's Patrol* (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023). Soon after, rallies in support of Russia were held in many other Serbian cities. Online space was flooded with different right-wing profiles and channels that spread propaganda, especially on the Telegram social network, and many far-right extremists from Serbia went to Ukraine to fight on Russia's side (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023). Polls from 2022 show that Serbs strongly support Russia and its leader, Putin, and attribute the blame for the war in Ukraine to NATO and the US, seeing Ukraine as a Western puppet (Ruge, 2022). Latest polls also show that most Serbian citizens are against joining the EU for the first time in history (Danas, 2022). The reason behind such attitudes is severe pressure regarding introducing sanctions against Russia and recognising Kosovo as a condition for entering the EU.

The most prominent finding of the D.Rad survey indicates that social domination orientation is one of the strongest predictors of both support for extremist attitudes and increased perception of migrants as a realistic threat. This relationship is both direct and indirect (via collective narcissism). As shown in the discussion above, the far-right in Serbia is on the rise and its extremist narratives are being mainstreamed and normalised thanks to the support of the ruling party, SNS and the Government. Strong national and religious identity shapes the perception of migrants as threats where migrants from the Middle East, who do not share the same values, are perceived as a severe security threat to Serbia and its population structure, which is not the case with Russian and Ukrainian migrants, who are more or less welcomed in Serbia. However, group relative deprivation emerged as a significant predictor of negative attitudes towards migrants and greater support for extremism. The reason behind such attitudes might be the frustration of Serbian citizens with economic setbacks (high inflation and unreasonably high rents) caused by the arrival of Russian and Ukrainian migrants, who are perceived as financially better off.

The radicalisation context in Serbia is inextricably related to political divisions, so the missing political attitudes dimension in the D.Rad survey would have provided essential insights into current radicalisation trends and enabled more profound conclusions regarding the researched topic.

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6.13. Slovenia

Slovenia had 19.38% of participants reporting not knowing their political attitudes. This variable was subsequently excluded from the model, keeping all participants and resulting in Social Dominance Orientation.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
23.56 (3.89)	159	49.69	161	50.31	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	207	64.69
Agnostic/Atheist	81	25.31
Muslim	22	6.88
Other	9	2.81
Jewish	1	0.31
Buddhist	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	73	22.92
No	217	63.10
Don't know	30	13.99

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n		%	
Sexuality	20		27.40	
Religion	17		23.29	
Nationality	15		20.55	
Colour or race	13		17.81	
Language	13		17.81	
Gender	13		17.81	
Other	9		12.33	
Ethnic group	8		10.96	
Age	7		9.59	
Disability	2		2.74	

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	79	24.69	137	42.81	104	32.50
Sport or recreational organization	108	33.75	93	29.06	119	37.19
Art, music or educational organization	84	26.25	96	30.00	140	43.75
Labour union	36	11.25	97	30.31	187	58.44
Political party	30	9.38	80	25.00	210	65.62
Environmental organization	47	14.69	81	25.31	192	60.00
Professional association	51	15.94	77	24.06	192	60.00
Humanitarian or charitable organization	75	23.44	91	28.44	154	48.12
Consumer organization	41	12.81	77	24.06	202	63.12
Self-help group or mutual help group	59	18.44	76	23.75	185	57.81
Women's group	70	21.88	61	19.06	189	59.06
Other organization	22	6.88	57	17.81	241	75.31

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	64	20.00	223	69.69	33	10.31
Worked in a political party or action group	33	10.31	255	79.69	32	10.00
Worked in another ideological organization	48	15.00	240	75.00	32	10.00
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	63	19.69	228	71.25	29	9.06
Signed a petition	133	41.56	157	49.06	30	9.38
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	62	19.38	216	67.50	42	13.12
Boycotted certain products	69	21.56	213	66.56	38	11.88
Posted or shared anything about politics online	90	28.12	196	61.25	34	10.62

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with stronger perceptions that migrants pose a threat to Slovenia and its resources. Perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived than migrants (group relative deprivation) was associated with stronger perceptions of threat. Feelings of anomie were also related to perceiving that migrants posed more of a threat to one's national ingroup.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with increased support for extremism. Additionally, perceiving one's ingroup as being more superior to other social groups (collective narcissism) was linked with more support for extremism. Perceiving one's ingroup to be more economically deprived relative to migrants (group relative deprivation) was linked with increased support for extremism.

Indirect predictors on extremism

Online group identity had an indirect effect on extremist attitudes via collective narcissism: a stronger online group identity predicted increased collective narcissism, which in turn predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect of online group identity (i.e., the sum of all indirect effects through other variables, even if these were not statistically significant on their own) was significant; a stronger online group identity predicted increased support for extremist attitudes via the combination of its relationship to the mediating variables in the model (thought note collective narcissism is explicitly responsible for over half of this total indirect effect).

Figure 16. Respecified model for Slovenia

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Greater social alienation was associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Support for extremist attitudes was also linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia and Russian culture. In contrast, a stronger social dominance orientation and experiencing more anomie were both separately associated with more positive attitudes towards Russia. In terms of attitudes towards Russian migrants, feeling more social alienation and endorsing more populist attitudes were both individually linked with worsening attitudes towards Russian migrants in the past twelve months.

In terms of attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants, greater social dominance orientation and endorsing more populist attitudes were both separately associated with worsening attitudes in the past twelve months. In contrast, having more trust in the Slovenian government was linked with improved attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the past twelve months. Additionally, holding more extremist ideologies was also associated with improved attitudes.

Situating the findings within the Slovene context

2022 was an important year for Slovenia. It saw the formation of a new government, with a notably high voter turnout of over 70%, contrasting sharply with the approximately 50% in the 2014 and 2018 elections. Slovenian voters demonstrated higher political participation and predominantly voted for center-left political options. The heightened electoral engagement was a response to the controversial administration of PM Janez Janša (2020-2022), marking a pause in Slovenia's era of populist, right-wing leadership (M. Novak, 2022, [Freedom House](#)). In his third term, 2020 - 2022, as a PM, Janša immediately renewed long-standing grievances with the press and critical media outlets upon assuming office; he further intensified his

previous attempts to control and politicise the media. Janša's term witnessed concerning democratic backsliding, including sidelining parliament, pressuring civil society/media, and adding Slovenia to the CIVICUS Watchlist (Freedom House, 2022; CIVICUS, 2020). The 2022 election turnout marked a pivot away from Janša's populism and towards liberal democracy under a new centre-left government led by PM Robert Golob and political newcomer, Freedom Movement. However, Golob faced challenges in implementing reforms, notably restructuring the national broadcaster RTV SLO. While the government changed, political polarisation persisted, with Janša's Slovenian Democratic Party (SDS) representing continued right-wing opposition. Slovenia's political landscape remains defined by divisions between new centre-left leadership versus Janez Janša's enduring right-wing populist base. Significant societal developments occurred in 2022, including legalising same-sex marriage and the historic election of the nation's first female president and the National Assembly's first female president. However, polarised views around progressive policies continue. Political shifts between the 2020 - 2022 government that left office on June 1st 2022, and the newly elected government provide essential context for interpreting the D.Rad Survey findings for Slovenia between October 2022 and February 2023.

Social Dominance Orientation and Attitudes toward Migrants

The survey results indicated that higher Social Dominance Orientation scores directly predicted stronger perceptions that migrants pose a realistic threat to Slovenia and its resources. This view was widely accepted and disseminated through different media outlets, including public broadcasters, during the 2015 refugee crisis when the media propagated narratives of migrants "flooding" the country as invaders and when Slovenia (at the time under the centre-left government of PM Cerar) started erecting razor wire on Croatia border and when migrants were primarily reinforced by the media as a threat, presented as a natural disaster, which all worked, as Pajnik (Abuse of Language, Media Collaboration in Solving the Migrant Question, 2015) to justify the migration policy.

Post-2015, SDS-affiliated outlets continued exploiting anti-migrant sentiment through sensationalised, racialised portrayals of non-white immigrants as criminals or extremists threatening Slovenia. A mutually reinforcing connection exists between SDS politicians, radicalised online supporters, and SDS-affiliated media, creating a vicious spiral of hateful anti-migrant rhetoric (Bulc, 2021). Enduring anti-immigrant rhetoric taps into dominant social ideologies that migrants pose a danger to the native Slovene population and society.

Social Dominance Orientation and Support for Extremism

The survey found that higher Social Dominance Orientation directly predicted greater extremist attitudes. The findings correlate with the affiliations between the Slovenian Democratic Party (SDS) and far-right entities. Given that the youth wing of SDS has well-established links to far-right groups, the survey results could indicate this relationship.

Investigative reporting reveals that the SDS maintains connections to Slovenian far-right and neo-Nazi organisations, creating an environment of implicit tolerance for their ideologies (Valenčič, 2022). For instance, MP Žan Mahnič publicly endorsed the extremist group

Generation Identity (GI). The connections between the mentioned MP and GI indicate the party's long-standing flirtation with radicals since Mahnič, as SDS youth wing leader, welcomed a GI representative as a guest at an SDS annual youth event in 2017. The SDS co-owned publishing house publishes books supporting GI far-right ideologies. Mahnič helped establish an SDS youth branch connected to, as Valenčič indicates, the neo-Nazi group Blood & Honor Slovenia, underscoring the role of SDS youth radicalisation.

In summary, the survey results linking higher SDO to extremism might reflect the SDS's ongoing direct and indirect engagement with extremist groups and ideologies and their impact on the radicalisation of youth through their offline and online reach out. Scrutinising the interconnections between the SDS and their impact on youth through online and offline presence, especially its youth wing and extremist organisations, remains critical.

Increased collective narcissism directly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. The survey findings indicate that increased collective narcissism directly correlates with heightened extremist attitudes. This might reflect the rhetoric from the Slovenian Democratic Party (SDS) and affiliated media. SDS leader Janša invokes pan-European far-right conspiracy theories like "cultural Marxism"—a narrative positing liberal elites conspire to undermine white Christian civilisation through multiculturalism (Valenčič, 2021).

By echoing European populists like Hungary's Viktor Orbán, Janša internationalises these extremist theories. As Valenčič notes, contemporary neo-Nazis in Slovenia increasingly come from Serbian, Bosnian, or Macedonian migrant backgrounds, united by white European identity. They adhere to theories like "cultural Marxism" that position liberalism and diversity as threats to European culture (Valenčič, 2021).

As a PM, Janša articulated his views through national public television, arguing that cultural Marxism represents the greatest threat to the EU (example, RTVSLO, 2020). SDS media outlets reinforce these narratives. This politicises narcissistic biases, fueling defensive extremism to protect the privileged ingroup. In summary, SDS propaganda glorifies the ingroup, denigrates outsiders, and politicises identity grievances. This caters to collective narcissism, increasing extremism divorced from factual threat assessments.

Developing media literacy and intergroup cooperation initiatives among youth could be beneficial to counter such radicalisation. Media literacy education can build critical thinking to identify extremist messaging. Positive intergroup contact facilitates understanding between youth from diverse backgrounds, mitigating prejudices rooted in collective narcissism. Combining these approaches can reduce risks from extremist propaganda and outgroup distrust.

Online Group Identity

In the context of Slovenia, the survey findings suggest that online group identity plays a significant role in influencing extremist attitudes, mainly through the mediator of collective narcissism. Specifically, the path model accounted for 25.5% of the variance in extremist

attitudes. While Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) did not influence extremism indirectly, it had a direct, positive relationship with extremist views.

In light of the national context of Slovenia, our survey findings resonate with pre-existing concerns about far-right extremist activities both online and offline. As Valenčič points out (Valenčič, E., 2021), far-right extremist groups in Slovenia intertwine street activities with self-promotion online and pinpoint the strategic use of social media platforms to proliferate hate-based ideologies. Not only in Slovenia but internationally, a major shift has occurred in the far-right extremist (FRE) landscape from offline to online activism, as outlined in the document "Trends & Challenges" by Nikki Sterkenburg.

The high level of activity from far-right groups online in Slovenia might shed some light on our findings that stronger online group identity significantly correlates with collective narcissism, ultimately fostering extremist attitudes. In a society where collective narratives shared through official governmental channels, and SDP's affiliated media outlets emphasise that traditional values and social cohesion are under threat from ideologies (cultural Marxism in Janša's case), our model shows that these narratives may be feeding extremist tendencies, accounting for 25.5% of the variance in extremism scores. Notably, the language and sentiment from official sources, including the 2020 - 2022 Prime Minister, validate and perpetuate these extremist attitudes, potentially catalysing collective narcissism and, by extension, support for extremist ideologies.

In deradicalisation efforts, an area that needs attention is the relationship between online group identity, the radicalisation of youth in Slovenia, and the online space. This relationship is under-researched in the Slovenian context, making it crucial to commission targeted studies to fill this knowledge gap. Furthermore, media literacy aimed at youngsters is an important prevention measure.

Ukraine and Russian migrants

Participants reported that their attitudes towards Russian migrants in the last 12 months had not changed significantly. On the other hand, participants reported their attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the previous 12 months to have become a little better. The reason for the slight betterment towards the Ukrainian migrants might be attributed to the general support towards Ukraine from the ruling and opposition parties in Slovenia, as they have shown solidarity and readiness to accommodate Ukrainian refugees.

This unified stance towards supporting Ukraine deviates from the typical anti-migrant rhetoric often employed by the ruling SDS party. The break from SDS's traditional anti-migrant narrative could explain why the survey found mildly improved public sentiment towards Ukrainian migrants - the Slovenian public may be responding to a narrative that differs from the usual rhetoric, which often breeds radicalisation and extremist views.

Interestingly, increased support for extremist attitudes also predicted improved attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants, parallel to the position on Ukraine held by both left and right-wing

parties. In summary, the rare alignment between typically opposed parties in support of Ukraine and deviation from typical anti-migrant rhetoric provides insight into why the survey found slightly improved public attitudes, specifically towards Ukrainian migrants, versus steady attitudes towards Russian migrants. The complex interplay between political messaging, extremism, and public attitudes highlights the potential to shape narratives to de-escalate rather than breed inter-group tensions.

In summary, analysing the D.Rad Survey findings in the context of Slovenia's political developments in 2022 provides valuable insights into the factors influencing the country's radicalisation, extremism, and potential deradicalisation efforts. Understanding these dynamics is important for fostering a more inclusive and tolerant society. In light of these findings, efforts to counter radicalisation in Slovenia should prioritise media literacy and intergroup cooperation initiatives among youth. Media literacy education can equip young individuals with critical thinking skills to identify extremist messaging, while positive intergroup contact can foster understanding and reduce prejudices rooted in collective narcissism. Additionally, the relationship between online group identity, youth radicalisation, and the online space warrants further research in the Slovenian context. Commissioning targeted studies in this area is essential for effective deradicalisation efforts.

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6.14. Turkey

Only 1.57% of participants in Turkey did not know their political attitudes. Thus, these participants were dropped, and the variable was kept, resulting in a sample of $n = 315$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
26.27 (4.68)	157	49.06	163	50.94	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Muslim	285	89.06
Agnostic/Atheist	25	7.81
Other	8	2.50
Christian	2	0.62
Jewish	0	0.00
Buddhist	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	93	18.04
No	205	75.95
Don't know	22	6.01

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Religion	33	35.48
Gender	28	30.11
Nationality	24	25.81
Language	19	20.43
Ethnic group	14	15.05
Colour or race	13	13.98

Other	12	12.90
Age	9	9.68
Sexuality	9	9.68
Disability	2	2.15

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	38	11.88	60	18.75	222	69.38
Sport or recreational organization	105	32.81	81	25.31	134	41.88
Art, music or educational organization	111	34.69	61	19.06	148	46.25
Labour union	57	17.81	65	20.31	198	61.88
Political party	59	18.44	55	17.19	206	64.38
Environmental organization	70	21.88	65	20.31	185	57.81
Professional association	64	20.00	66	20.62	190	59.38
Humanitarian or charitable organization	85	26.56	80	25.00	155	48.44
Consumer organization	48	15.00	66	20.62	206	64.38
Self-help group or mutual help group	70	21.88	67	20.94	183	57.19
Women's group	57	17.81	54	16.88	209	65.31
Other organization	38	11.88	56	17.50	226	70.62

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	63	19.69	242	75.62	15	4.69
Worked in a political party or action group	40	12.50	266	83.12	14	4.38
Worked in another ideological organization	42	13.12	260	81.25	18	5.62
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	48	15.00	247	77.19	25	7.81
Signed a petition	111	34.69	189	59.06	20	6.25
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	76	23.75	222	69.38	22	6.88
Boycotted certain products	109	34.06	187	58.44	24	7.50
Posted or shared anything about politics online	108	33.75	193	60.31	19	5.94

Predictors of realistic threat

Feelings of anomie were associated with an increased perception of threat from migrants to one's national ingroup and its access to resources, welfare, and power. Perceiving that one's ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants was also linked with increased perceived threat from migrants.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with more support for extremist attitudes. Additionally, a stronger online group

identity was also linked with more support for extremist attitudes. Perceiving one’s social group as being superior to other groups was associated with increased support for extremism. Interestingly, increased perceptions that migrants pose a threat to Turkey and its resources (realistic threat) predicted less support for extremist attitudes. This was the only country where this relationship was observed; for other country samples, if there was a relationship between realistic threat and extremism, it tended to be a positive relationship such that increased realistic threat predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing more social alienation was linked with greater support for extremism. Unexpectedly, experiencing more social cohesion acted as a buffer in that increased social cohesion was associated with more support for extremism.

Figure 17. Respecified model for Turkey

Indirect predictors on extremism

Social dominance orientation had a significant indirect effect on extremist attitudes via social cohesion and group relative deprivation and subsequently realistic threat. The total indirect effect of social dominance orientation was significant in the negative direction (i.e., as social dominance orientation increased, extremism decreased). However, looking at the direct effect, greater social dominance orientation was linked with increased support for extremist attitudes. The total effect (i.e. the sum of the total indirect effect and the direct effect) was ultimately significant and positive. This happened despite the mediating effects of social dominance orientation on extremism being buffered so that greater social dominance orientation (SDO) indirectly predicted decreased extremism because SDO increased people’s experiences of social cohesion (protecting against extremism). Still, the direct relationship between higher

SDO and higher extremism was strong enough to override any indirect relationships that may lower support for extremist attitudes.

Online group identity had significant indirect effects on extremist attitudes via collective narcissism, social cohesion, and social alienation, and the total indirect effect was significant (i.e., as online group identity increased, so did extremism). A stronger online group identity also directly predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. The total effect (i.e., the sum of the indirect and direct effects) was positive: a stronger online group identity predicted increased support for extremist attitudes directly and through its effect on other variables, which then predicted greater support for extremist attitudes.

Political attitudes had a positive mediating effect on extremism via anomie and, subsequently, realistic threat. However, the total indirect effect was insignificant, indicating that political attitudes did not predict support for extremist attitudes when considering all combined mediating effects.

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Perceiving that one's ingroup was superior to other social groups was linked with increased negative attitudes towards Russia. Additionally, increased support for extremist attitudes was linked with greater negative attitudes towards Russia. Perceiving migrants as a threat to Turkey and its resources was linked with more positive attitudes towards Russia.

Situating the findings within the Turkish context

Findings of the survey results of Turkey need to be evaluated within the overall radicalisation context of Turkey and the conditions during the period the survey was conducted (December 2022- February 2023). In the last two decades, the Turkish political landscape has been increasingly polarised under the Justice and Development Party (Adalet ve Kalkınma Partisi, AKP) governments. The decades-old conflict between the state security forces and the Kurdish minority had evolved into a social conflict long before AKP came to power. In the 2011-2015 period, AKP engaged in negotiation with the leadership of the Kurdish social movement; however, the peace talks failed to bring resolution. On the contrary, AKP, in alliance with the far-right Nationalist Action Party (*Milliyetçi Hareket Partisi, MHP*), fuelled the racist attitudes towards the Kurds while undermining the movement's organisational power through imprisonment. AKP's expanding Islamization policies reinforced the fault lines in Turkish politics by deepening the secular-Islamist cleavage. The period in which the survey was conducted was shaped by both these two major politicised cleavages, exacerbating economic crises, and the forthcoming presidential and parliamentary elections, which were later held on the same day, May 14, 2023.

AKP's election campaign was built upon an aggressive nationalist-Islamist discourse. The party and its more minor partner, MHP, accused the opposition led by the social democratic Republican People's Party (Cumhuriyet Halk Partisi, CHP) of being complicit with PKK (the Kurdish militia) and the foreign powers at the same time. At the time, the opposition's

presidential candidate was not determined. Istanbul metropolitan mayor Ekrem İmamoğlu was considered to be among the strongest potential candidates. A December 14, 2022 court decision put a political ban on İmamoğlu based on fabricated evidence to prevent him from running for presidency (France 24, 2022). The amended Internet Law further pressured national and international media platforms to induce self-censorship. Furthermore, the misinformation law passed in October 2022 started to be executed to intimidate journalists and academics by accusing them of spreading misinformation (“Turkey: Dangerous, Dystopian New Legal Amendments”, 2022).

The survey findings provide intriguing insight and raise further questions about the radicalisation trends in Turkey. Those who reported being members of one or more discriminated groups both reported stronger perceptions of anomie and had greater populist attitudes compared to participants who were not members of any discriminated groups. That is, those who feel discriminated against also perceive a breakdown in the social fabric and leadership and believe that society is ultimately separated between the people (who are “pure and good”) and the elite (who are “corrupt and evil”), arguing that politics should be an expression of the general will of the people. These findings, especially when considered with the descriptive statistics, appear counter-intuitive. Those who feel discriminated against refer to religion, gender, nationality and language. In other words, these people are probably Alevi, women, Kurdish, and/or Arab. It is difficult to understand why a person from a minority group would feel that the social fabric or leadership is being broken. Similarly, there does not seem to be any reason to justify the argument that minorities would argue that the majority should rule politics. In fact, it is the people belonging to the majority groups who identify themselves as natives or locals tend to cling to dichotomic categorisations at the societal level and be in constant fear of threats to the social fabric and political leadership (Ionescu, Tavani, and Collange 2021). In the Turkish case, we also know that especially the Alevis and the Kurds tend to vote for social democratic and socialist parties rather than far-right populist parties (Başlevent, Kirmanoğlu, and Şenatalar 2005; Shankland 2003).

Findings on the predictors of attitudes and views about Russia are interesting: 1) Increased collective narcissism and increased support for extremist attitudes predicted increased attitudes against Russia (e.g., “We should break all cooperation with Russian academics, artists, and athletes.”). 2) Increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat predicted decreased attitudes against Russia (i.e., improved attitudes towards Russia). The first finding about attitudes against Russia is pretty straightforward. If one thinks that their group is superior to other groups, as a Turkish person, they might have negative attitudes towards Russia and the Russians. However, the following finding adds a new layer. Those who think that migrants pose a threat to the welfare and resources, the political and economic power, and the physical and material well-being of the local group appear to be more positive towards Russia. In fact, we observe an increasingly positive attitude towards the Russian and Ukrainian migrants in Turkish society, especially when the locals make this evaluation in comparison to other migrant groups with lower education and income levels, such as Syrians and Afghans.

In terms of the predictors of extremist attitudes, the survey finds that having a higher SDO, a stronger online group identity, increased collective narcissism, increased perceptions of social cohesion and increased feelings of social alienation predicted stronger support for extremist attitudes. However, analysing the paths to extremism in Turkey yields some contradictory and counter-intuitive findings. Increased perceptions that migrants pose a realistic threat to Turkey and its resources predicted less support for extremist attitudes. This was the only country where this relationship was observed; for other country samples, if there was a relationship between realistic threat and extremism, it tended to be a positive relationship such that increased realistic threat predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. In a similar vein, increasingly right-wing political attitudes predicted decreased perceptions of anomie.

Survey findings on Turkey in the period from December 2022 to February 2023 show that people mostly feel discriminated against in terms of their religious, gender, national and language belongings. Extremist attitudes tend to be more common among people who approve of social hierarchies, identify strongly with certain online groups, believe that their group is superior to others, and desire social conformity and cohesion. Especially when these people feel socially alienated due to the changes (e.g. due to migration), they tend to become extremists.

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6.15. UK

In the UK, 15.14% of participants reported not knowing their political attitudes. This variable was subsequently excluded from the model, keeping all participants and resulting in a final sample of $n = 317$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
25.10 (5.66)	149	47.00	168	53.00	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	114	35.96
Agnostic/Atheist	102	32.18
Muslim	79	24.92
Other	13	4.10
Sikh	6	1.89
Buddhist	2	0.63
Hindu	1	0.32
Jewish	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	104	32.22
No	193	60.18
Don't know	20	7.60

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Colour or race	60	57.69
Religion	55	52.88
Ethnic group	38	36.54
Nationality	31	29.81
Gender	26	25.00

Language	11	10.58
Sexuality	9	8.65
Disability	9	8.65
Age	4	3.85
Other	3	2.88

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	86	27.13	95	29.97	135	42.59	1	0.32
Sport or recreational organization	116	36.59	84	26.50	116	36.59	1	0.32
Art, music or educational organization	103	32.49	78	24.61	135	42.59	1	0.32
Labour union	61	19.24	78	24.61	177	55.84	1	0.32
Political party	54	17.03	79	24.92	183	57.73	1	0.32
Environmental organization	65	20.50	65	20.50	186	58.68	1	0.32
Professional association	86	27.13	67	21.14	163	51.42	1	0.32
Humanitarian or charitable organization	83	26.18	68	21.45	165	52.05	1	0.32
Consumer organization	68	21.45	65	20.50	183	57.73	1	0.32
Self-help group or mutual help group	70	22.08	72	22.71	174	54.89	1	0.32
Women's group	70	22.08	66	20.82	180	56.78	1	0.32
Other organization	30	9.46	47	14.83	239	75.39	1	0.32

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	104	32.81	190	59.94	23	7.26
Worked in a political party or action group	50	15.77	244	76.97	23	7.26
Worked in another ideological organization	64	20.19	234	73.82	19	5.99
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	94	29.65	202	63.72	21	6.62
Signed a petition	211	66.56	87	27.44	19	5.99
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	78	24.61	218	68.77	21	6.62
Boycotted certain products	121	38.17	165	52.05	31	9.78
Posted or shared anything about politics online	155	48.90	139	43.85	23	7.26

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was linked with greater perceptions of threat from migrants to the UK and its resources.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with more support for extremist attitudes. Increased perceptions of threat from migrants were linked with increased support for extremist attitudes. In addition, holding stronger beliefs that one's ingroup is superior to other social groups (collective narcissism) was associated with increased endorsement of extremism. Regarding political ideology, holding more populist beliefs was linked with greater support for extremism. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing more social alienation was linked with increased support for extremism. Interestingly, experiencing less anomie was linked with more extremist beliefs.

Indirect predictors on extremism

Social dominance orientation had indirect effects on extremist attitudes via populism, realistic threat, and anomie. Increased social dominance predicted decreased populism, which, in turn, predicted decreased support for extremist attitudes. Increased social dominance orientation predicted increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat, which in turn predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. Finally, increased social dominance predicted decreased anomie, which in turn predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect of social dominance orientation was significant in a positive direction.

Online group identity had a mediating effect via social alienation, collective narcissism, and anomie. A stronger online group identity predicted increased social alienation and increased collective narcissism, and these, in turn, predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. On the other hand, a stronger online group identity predicted increased anomie, which in turn predicted decreased support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect ultimately was significantly positive, with a stronger online group identity indirectly predicting increased support for extremist attitudes.

Figure 18. Respecified model for the UK

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies were associated with more negative attitudes towards Russian culture. Additionally, holding a stronger online group identity was also linked with more negative attitudes towards Russian culture. Finally, feeling more embedded in one's community (social cohesion) was also linked with more negative attitudes towards Russian culture. Regarding attitudes towards Russian migrants, greater trust in the UK government (political trust) was linked with improved attitudes towards Russian migrants in the past twelve months. Additionally, perceiving that one's economic situation was more deprived relative to migrants was linked with worsening attitudes towards both Russian and Ukrainian migrants in the past twelve months. Finally, a stronger online group identity was associated with improved attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the past twelve months.

Situating the findings within the UK context

The findings of the UK sample are situated within mainstream government and media narratives which serve to reinforce intersubjective representations of idealised national identity. We focus on right-wing extremism within the UK cultural context which is one of the biggest current threats in terms of political violence, with 49% of terror arrests in 2022 linked to suspected right-wing extremism (Hope not Hate, 2023a). One of the pillars of right-wing extremism is supremacism, which is the belief that "a certain group of people sharing a common element (nation, race, culture, etc.) is superior to all other people. Seeing themselves in a supreme position, the particular group considers it to be their natural right to dominate the rest of the population" (Europol, 2019, p. 65). We tie this belief to one of the main explanatory

variables of extremism, social dominance orientation, which also exerts an indirect effect on increased support for extremist attitudes via realistic threat, anomie, and populism.

Looking at national media, and as outlined in a previous report (Ozduzen et al., 2021), mainstream UK media bolster ideologies of far-right groups in the UK through making ingroup-outgroup boundaries salient, promoting an idealised and superior 'British identity', and denying dominating racial hierarchies (Cabrera, 2014). Furthermore, we argue that the UK media, which was perceived as being the most right-wing by its populace in a survey of seven European countries (Dahlgreen, 2016), perpetuates racial and religious hierarchies which legitimise "the threat of right-wing ideology whilst simultaneously disseminating the seeds of white superiority" (Ozduzen et al., 2021, p. 15). We posit that these trends in media narratives can be understood as cultural artefacts of collective narcissism and social dominance orientation which serve to echo back and reinforce perceptions of threat from outgroups.

Narratives of realistic threat – that migrant outgroups pose a threat to the UK and its resources are reinforced in the UK media, which out of seven European countries was perceived as the most negative towards migrants; taken together that the UK was also the only country where there was indication of polarised attitudes towards media in that 29% of the sample saw media as being too right-wing on topics of refugees and immigration, 24% saw it as too left-wing (18% of the sample perceived it as about right) (Dahlgreen, 2016). This division is more recently echoed in public attitudes towards migration which are becoming more salient, with 32% of respondents surveyed seeing immigration as a very bad or a bad thing for Britain, and 52% believing that immigration should be reduced (Richards, Fernández-Reino, & Blinder, 2023).

Turning towards the government, the UK political landscape has experienced a marked upheaval as evidenced by three Prime Ministers and four different Home Secretaries holding office in 2022, with a gradual shift towards the right. This is particularly evidenced around issues of migration and refugees and asylum seekers. For example, in 2022 then Home Secretary Suella Braverman described illegal immigration as an "invasion" of the southern coast of the UK during a Commons statement, paralleling extremist language of the far-right. More recently, a policy which makes stark ingroup-outgroup boundaries and prime grievances has been calling for 'British homes for British people', which would prioritise British nationals for social housing (Stacey, 2024). Such policies and discourse reflect collective narcissism narratives. Collective narcissism centres on the conviction that the exceptionality of one's ingroup is not appreciated by others, which also underlies populist rhetoric such as that used by the Conservative party (Golec de Zavala, Dyduch-Hazar, Lantos, 2019). Thus, our findings of collective narcissism predicting increased support for extremist attitudes parallel government policies and the Conservative party contemporary playbook.

Traditional far-right and mainstream right political narratives espoused by the Conservative government are converging in their focus on issues and often use the same language (Hope not Hate, 2023a). Importantly, far-right engagement has increased as a result of government policies and their coverage by tabloid media (Hope not Hate, 2023b). Indeed, research suggests that the government is "not taking the far-right threat seriously, but actively feeding it through their rhetoric... with each Government announcement, cracking down on small boat

crossings... or sending people thousands of miles away to Rwanda, far-right activity spikes every time.” (Hope not Hate, 2023b). The Conservative party is using increasingly populist rhetoric, such as its focus on nativism, which displays far-right markers (Henley, 2023). These markers are conveyed effectively to the public, as a recent YouGov poll indicates that the Conservative party is now viewed as being as right-wing as the UK Independence Party (UKIP) in its 2014-2016 era in the lead up to the EU referendum in 2016 (Smith, 2024). UKIP, a radical right-wing party which emerged into prominence through galvanizing public discourse around the UK’s membership in the EU played a key role in mobilizing the 2016 vote for Brexit (Whiteley et al. 2019).

In this vein, we can situate our findings of social dominance orientation predicting increased extremism: the positioning of the British ingroup and its social identity by British right-wing parties and UK media as being in conflict with, and under threat from other outgroups such as the EU, and within borders, by migrant outgroups. Indeed, our findings parallel other research which has found that social dominance orientation predicts increased prejudice and perceived threats from migrants, and in turn, pro-Brexit attitudes, voting for Brexit, and greater support for UKIP (Golec de Zavala, Guerra, & Simão, 2017; Van Assche, Dhont, & Pettigrew, 2019). Additionally, social dominance orientation should activate dislike towards outgroups who are low in power (to justify superiority and dominance) and those who are perceived as competing for the same position and status (Duckitt & Sibley, 2010), something that is reflected in the ethnic stratification of the UK’s labour market and the hierarchies imposed on migrant groups (Consterdine, 2023; Fox, 2013; Narkowicz, 2023; Wills et al., 2009; Zwysen & Demireva, 2018).

Looking at the extremism variable overall, our measure may reflect public attitudes in the UK today; for example, 73% of 20,000 respondents surveyed reported that they felt that the UK is heading in the wrong direction (Hope not Hate, 2023). Our findings linking populism with support for extremism is echoed in wider public opinion, with a recent poll of 20,000 British individuals by Hope not Hate (2023a) showing that 67% of respondents believing that the political system is broken and politicians do not speak to them. Further, 27% would support an authoritarian leader who eschews democratic processes such as parliament or elections. This parallels other research which reveals that only 35% of the UK population trust the national government, at a rate lower than the OECD average (ONS, 2022).

One group difference on scores of extremism that we would like to highlight is for sex, with men reporting more support for extremist attitudes than women. As extremism was measured using a general measure, we argue that it can pertain to specific ideologies such as misogyny. This difference may reflect the increase of misogynistic extremist ideologies in the UK. For example, a recent poll by NGO Hope not Hate found that half of their male sample had positive views of Andrew Tate, with the main reason given that Tate “wants men to be real men” (Hope not Hate, 2023a), implying dissatisfaction with contemporary perceived progressive gender roles and their representation in British society. Our measure captures the desire to dismantle existing societal structures, which parallels the misogynistic rhetoric that is spread by Tate and his followers. Tate, an online influencer who rose rapidly to fame in 2022 through his

promotion of toxic masculinity disguised as traditional masculine virile narratives, has become a key concern for extremist attitudes in young men and boys, with many teachers in the UK reporting that schools are unprepared with dealing with the overwhelming infiltration of Tate's misogyny (Weale, 2023).

Finally, we can tie some of our findings of the indirect effect of online group identities on increased extremism via increased collective narcissism. Online extremism is increasing (Vali, 2023) with right-wing content on social media platforms such as TikTok “a symptom and symbol of wider mainstream patterns and... widespread systemic racist discourse within the British public sphere (Ozduzen, Ferenczi, & Holmes, 2023, p. 846). A qualitative analysis of far-right content on TikTok revealed themes of nostalgic reinterpretations of historical events, idealised white British culture, and neo-colonialism (Ozduzen et al., 2023), which embody collective narcissism narratives of British in-group superiority and discontent that the exceptionality of the British ingroup is not appreciated sufficiently. Additionally, recent research on fifteen cases of extremism in the UK that online spaces provided more opportunities for radicalisation through enabling communication and connection with like-minded others and through serving as an echo chamber (von Behr, Reding, Edwards, & Gribbon, 2013), supporting the importance of online group identities for endorsement of extremist attitudes.

In conclusion, the UK findings can be situated within the increasingly right-wing public and political sphere bolstered by UK media narratives which make salient an idealised British identity rooted in nostalgia, ingroup-outgroup boundaries, and outgroup threat. The individual-level processes reported in the model parallel the populist scripts that have been adopted by a right-wing government and perpetuated by mainstream media. Our findings can also be interpreted from the perspective of the increasing threat of online misogyny, represented by Tate, which is reaching young men and schoolchildren. Taken together, the patterns of variables show several processes through which outgroups are perceived as threats and extremist attitudes such as dismantling the status quo come to be endorsed.

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